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List of abbreviations

AEI	Agro Environmental Initiatives
BM	Business model
BMC	Business Model Canvas
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CEC	Cation exchange capacity
CS	Case study
DFCI	Defence of forests against fire risks
ESs	Ecosystems
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
GAEC	Good agricultural and environmental conditions
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GMO	Genetic modified organisms
IFS	International Featured Standard
LENs	Landscape Enterprise Network
MAEC	Measures for agro environmental and climate
PES	Payments for Ecosystem Services
RDP	Rural Development Plan
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SGQ	Quality management system
SMEs	Small and medium enterprises
SOM	Soil organic matter
UGI	Urban green infrastructure
WFD	Water Framework Directive

1 Summary

This document reports on activities carried out under Task 3.1, "Mapping of existing incentives for sustainable soil health business models," in the framework of WP3, "Testing and development of a toolbox for incentives," of the NOVASOIL project.

In cooperation with WPs 2 and 5, and through national partners, this WP aims to clarify the concept of soil health business models by conducting an inventory and mapping that links the concept to existing models.

The question at hand is how soil health business models can lead to the maintenance of sustainable and competitive agriculture. A structured approach was developed for spatial mapping of existing incentives for delivering various ecosystem services. The assessment also explored how existing incentives can be combined with soil restoration technologies. Based on the conceptual framework, a typology of incentives for delivering ecosystem services was defined, and the Business Model Canvas (BMC) was modified for the purposes of incentives mapping. The inventory of existing incentives in each NOVASOIL partner country completed the information related to soil health issues for the planning period 2014-2022. The focus on this period is because of the possibility to be evaluated their implementation.

2 Introduction

This document includes an inventory analysis of existing incentives and incentives mapping regarding case studies in the project.

At the beginning of this task, partners were asked to complete a questionnaire in their respective countries. Incentives related to soil health exist in different forms and can be implemented in various types, ranging from regulatory to voluntary, including public programs and private initiatives. Combining these incentives can increase ecosystem service outcomes at lower social costs.

Based on the questionnaire (Q1-Q6), the incentives, land use classification, and NUTS level were identified. Information was gathered about whether the incentives are policy-driven or voluntary, the national policies supporting the application of these incentives, and the financial support provided for their application. The analysis also examined the relationship between case study incentives and the main goals of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development objectives and the key objectives of the new CAP 2023-2027. The last part of this analysis was dedicated to ecosystem services and the relation with incentives. Ecosystem services were not considered as part of any business models for the purposes of the inventory. The business model type was taken into consideration during the incentives mapping process.

The incentives were analyzed in terms of their relation to nine important soil health indicators. Another important part of the analysis was researching how the incentives influence land use. The analysis shows that 25% of the incentives don't change land use (Fig. 10). Almost half of the incentives (48%) are not focused on land use. On the other hand, 27% affect land use.

Based on the information received from Questionnaire 1, the analysis examined the relations connected with incentives at the case study level and their alignment with sustainability development goals, which focus on economic, social, and environmental goals—the foundation of the new CAP 2023-2027 and soil health strategies.

The incentives mapping will categorize incentives conducted on the social, economic, and environmental building blocks of soil health business models within the agricultural and forestry sector. The simplified version of the Business Model Canvas is used for business model estimation. For the purposes of mapping NOVASOIL business model building blocks can be additionally divided into two large groups: socioeconomic block (customer value proposition, channels and partnerships, and revenue and cost structure) and environmental/technology block (key resources and key activities). The socioeconomic block and the environmental/technology block, together with soil health estimation, are the main directions of the mapping process.

The analysis of ecosystem services focuses on thirteen main areas enhanced by the incentives in each case study (CS). Considering that the analysis of the incentives focuses on those affecting soil health, 165 out of 223 incentives influence soil health, 130 influence biodiversity, and 106 influence climate regulation in terms of carbon storage.

3 Conceptual framework

3.1 Ecosystem services

The concept of ecosystem services is relatively new, tracing back to the late 1960s (e.g., King 1966; Helliwell 1969). Research on ecosystem services has significantly grown since the 1990s. Ecosystems (ESs) are living systems that interact with one another and their surroundings, providing benefits or services to the world. Ecosystem services encompass the multitude of benefits that nature provides to society, connecting ecosystem benefits to human well-being (FAO, ITPS, GSBI, CBD and EC, 2020). These benefits can be positive or negative. The World Resources Institute in 2009 defines ecosystem services as the planet's life support systems, without which human survival would be impossible.

The term "ecosystem services," as described by Smith et al. (2013), refers to the diverse benefits derived from the natural environment. Examples include the supply of food, water, and timber (provisioning services); the regulation of air quality, climate, and flood risk (regulating services); opportunities for

recreation, tourism, and education (cultural services); and essential underlying functions such as soil formation and nutrient cycling (supporting services).

Ecosystem services can be classified in various ways depending on the focus of the analysis. While there is no universally agreed method of categorizing all ecosystem services, the functional classification (MEA 2005) is widely accepted as a useful starting point. It differentiates services into four broad categories: (1) provisioning, such as the production of food and water; (2) regulating, such as the control of climate and disease; (3) supporting, such as nutrient cycles and crop pollination; and (4) cultural, such as spiritual and recreational benefits. Ecosystem services can also be classified according to their geographical scale (local, regional, global), value to society (direct or indirect), origin (services from natural ecosystems or modified ecosystems), or the type of natural ecosystem providing the service (forest, coral reef, wetlands, etc.) (Tallis et al., 2016; Raudsepp-Hearne et al., 2010). These classifications help understand the complex relationships between ecosystems and human well-being, informing ecosystem management decisions.

Agricultural systems ensure provisioning ecosystem services essential to human well-being. They also provide and consume other ecosystem services, including regulating services and services that support provisioning. Agroecosystems produce a variety of ecosystem services such as soil and water quality regulation, carbon sequestration, support for biodiversity, and cultural services. Depending on management practices, agriculture can also be a source of numerous disservices, including loss of wildlife habitat, nutrient runoff, sedimentation of waterways, greenhouse gas emissions, and pesticide poisoning of humans and non-target species (Power, 2010, p. 2959).

Apart from agriculture also forestry and farmer-owned urban areas businesses provide a wide range of ecosystem services.

The forestry ecosystem services include the provision of timber and non-timber forest products (Newton et al., 2013), carbon sequestration (Nabuurs et al., 2013), climate regulation (Bonan, 2008), biodiversity conservation (FAO, 2010), soil protection and nutrient cycling (Nair, 2012) and water purification (Vidon et al., 2010). Forests act as carbon sinks, regulate local climates, support biodiversity, protect soil, purify water, and offer valuable resources for human use. These findings highlight the significant and vital role of forests for the well-being of both human societies and the environment. The multifunctionality of forests needs a broader understanding of ecosystem services that goes beyond timber production in forestry management and policymaking.

The linkage of farmer-owned urban areas businesses with the ecosystem services is a relatively new scientific and practical topic. While there is a limited number of studies specifically focused on the ecosystem services provided by farmer-owned urban areas businesses, there is a growing recognition of their potential contributions. These businesses, involved in urban agriculture, offer various ecosystem services such as local food production, urban greening, improved air quality, and community engagement. They promote sustainable

urban practices, support food security, enhance biodiversity, and contribute to social well-being, while fostering community engagement and social cohesion (Lin et al., 2018; Smith et al., 2020). Farmer-owned urban area businesses play a crucial role in creating resilient and livable cities by integrating agricultural activities into urban landscapes, benefiting both the environment and local communities. Jones et al. (2022) conducted an in-depth analysis of farmer-owned urban area businesses and their contributions to ecosystem services. The researchers found that these enterprises play a crucial role in urban food production, ensuring a local and sustainable supply of fresh produce. Through innovative farming practices such as vertical farming, rooftop gardens, and community-supported agriculture, farmer-owned businesses contribute to urban food security while reducing the carbon footprint associated with long-distance food transportation. Furthermore, the study highlights the importance of these businesses in conserving biodiversity within urban areas. Farmer-owned urban area businesses often incorporate agroforestry systems, native plantings, and pollinator-friendly practices, creating habitat corridors and supporting urban wildlife. These initiatives enhance urban biodiversity, promote ecological balance, and provide valuable pollination services for surrounding ecosystems. The research also underscores the role of farmer-owned businesses in sustainable soil and water management. By utilizing organic farming techniques, composting, and responsible irrigation practices, these enterprises help minimize soil erosion, improve soil health, and reduce water pollution in urban environments (Niemeyer et al., 2017). Additionally, urban agriculture can contribute to stormwater management by reducing runoff and improving water infiltration, thus mitigating the risks of flooding. In terms of climate regulation, farmer-owned urban area businesses contribute to carbon sequestration through urban greening initiatives. Their integration of green roofs, vertical gardens, and urban forests enhances carbon capture, mitigates the urban heat island effect, and improves air quality. These efforts have a positive impact on urban microclimates, reducing energy consumption for cooling and providing multiple co-benefits for local residents. Farmer-owned urban area businesses foster social cohesion and community engagement. These enterprises often provide educational programs, community gardens, and opportunities for local residents to connect with nature and participate in food production, direct sales, farmers' markets. Such initiatives enhance social interactions, improve mental well-being, and strengthen the sense of belonging within urban communities (Blay-Palmer et al., 2021).

According to Swinton et al. (2007), globally, most landscapes have been modified by agricultural activities, and most natural, unmanaged ecosystems exist within a matrix of agricultural land uses. The conversion of undisturbed natural ecosystems to agriculture can strongly impact the system's ability to produce important ecosystem services, but many agricultural systems can also be important sources of services. Agricultural land use can be seen as an

intermediate stage in a human impact continuum between wilderness and urban ecosystems.

Soils provide multiple benefits for human well-being, most of which are often invisible to the beneficiaries. Soil serves as the foundation of terrestrial ecosystems, and the majority of ecosystem services necessary for human survival arise from it (Kibblewhite et al., 2008). Ecosystem services provided by soil can be supporting (e.g., primary production and biodiversity) or regulatory (e.g., erosion control, water infiltration, nutrient retention, atmospheric gas regulation and pest control). By definition, ecosystem services benefit human welfare and represent nature's capital (Costanza et al., 1997; Robinson et al., 2012). For example, the economic value of soil microbial metabolic pathways in removing greenhouse gases from the atmosphere, abating nutrients, eradicating pathogens, and degrading organic pollutants has been estimated to be double that of the gross annual product (Guimaraes et al., 2010). Barrios, 2007 and Brussaard, 2013 pointed out that many ecosystem services inherently depend on soil health and biodiversity of the soil biota.

Soil health refers to the capacity of soil to sustain or improve the productivity and health of plants and higher trophic levels, as well as air and water quality in natural and managed ecosystems (Kibblewhite et al., 2008).

Holling and Meffe (1996) and many others after them have demonstrated that the exploitation of soil has led to the collapse of civilizations and irreversible reductions in the productive capacity of ecosystems. These events have been instrumental in revealing the most obvious ecosystem service provided by soil: the production of food, fiber, and fuel for a growing human population. Extractive farming practices can result in soil degradation, reducing crop yields due to erosion, diminished nutrient supply from soil with low organic matter stocks, and degraded soil structure, all of which can worsen drought stress (Lal, 2009). The second most obvious ecosystem service is water infiltration. Converting wetlands to agricultural and urban areas exacerbates flooding and damages people's lives, property, and local economies. Undegraded soil in natural systems provides disturbance regulation, such as flood control, estimated to have a value of US \$1.8 trillion per year (Costanza et al., 1997).

The shift toward soil health in policy and science emphasizes the positive impacts of managing for soil health on soil structure and function, productivity, and environmental outcomes. The growing interest in soil health reflects advancing science and a reframing of traditional issues, illustrating the importance of framing effects, where the language used to discuss an issue can influence behaviour (Stevens, 2018). Another challenge is the growing recognition that soil conservation practices result in multiple private and public goods.

3.2 Incentives for ecosystem services

Incentives, in general, represent a complex and multifaceted concept with different understandings depending on the context and application. Incentives are often defined as any factor that motivates or encourages an

individual or group to take a particular action (Ariely, 2016). According to this definition, incentives can take different forms, including monetary rewards, recognition, penalties, and social status. Another definition of incentives emphasizes the role of rewards in shaping behaviour (Deci, Koestner, & Ryan, 1999). In this view, incentives are defined as external rewards or reinforcements that can influence behaviour but do not necessarily change one's underlying motivation or beliefs. Incentives are often defined as rewards or punishments that influence behavior or motivate individuals to take certain actions (Gneezy & Rustichini, 2000). According to this definition, incentives can take many forms, including monetary rewards, penalties, recognition, or social status. Fehr & Gächter (2000) highlight that incentives can be shaped by social norms and values, which can determine what is considered desirable or acceptable behaviour. This view focuses on the role of social norms and values in shaping incentives.

Therefore, they are widely used instruments in various contexts, including economic, social, and environmental spheres, to motivate and encourage desired behaviours. In economic contexts, incentives are often used to align individual and collective interests and achieve efficient outcomes (Mankiw, 2014). In social contexts, incentives are used to motivate and encourage positive behavior, such as charitable giving or volunteering (Gneezy & List, 2016). In environmental contexts, incentives can be used to encourage sustainable practices and conservation efforts (Pagiola, 2008). Often, incentives are seen as a key tool used by governments and organizations to encourage certain behaviours or actions. They can take many forms and can be used to align individual and collective interests, shape preferences and beliefs, and ensure the fair distribution of benefits and costs.

Bryan (2013) defines incentives for ecosystem services as packages that aim to support farmers in the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices that will benefit the environment. In agricultural ecosystems, incentives influence ecosystem services through motivating changes in land use and management. Payment for Ecosystem Services represents a type of incentive for ecosystem services. Its definition varies widely, from narrow market-based definitions with direct transactions between providers and beneficiaries (including schemes where private buyers and sellers arrange voluntary and conditional transactions for the delivery of ecosystem services) to broader schemes in which those who benefit from the ecosystem services pay (usually indirectly) those who provide the services (Duram, 2015; Vetter et al., 2017; Pagiola et al., 2005; Bryan, 2013; Liu et al., 2018; Wunder, 2005; Lubell et al., 2016).

In agricultural ecosystems, incentives influence ecosystem services through motivating changes in land use and management. This chain of influence is complex because incentives can cause multiple intended and unintended changes in land use and management, each potentially having co-benefits and trade-offs across multiple ecosystem services. More often than not, multiple incentives coexist. These incentives interact, providing price signals for multiple land use and management changes, thereby compounding the effect on ecosystem services. Hence, the linkages between incentives and

land use, and between land use and ecosystem services can be one-to-many, many-to-one, or many-to-many. These effects are typically heterogeneous across both space and time and can be non-linear. Changes in the supply of ecosystem services may also have a dynamic feedback effect on incentive prices, depending on instrument design. Understanding these effects can lead to substantial gains in the efficiency of policy and management in agro-ecosystems and avoid negative outcomes (Huberman 2008; Snilstveit et. all 2019; Bryan 2013, Ishii, 2014.).

Bryan (2013) developed an integrated assessment of incentive interactions on land use and ecosystem services, encompassing all the linkages depicted (see; figure 1).

Source: Bryan 2013, p. 126.

Figure 1. Linkages between incentives, land use, and ecosystem services

According to Bryan (2013), financial incentives can have both synergies (positive) and tensions (negative) in changing land use and management. These, in turn, have a range of co-benefits (positive) and trade-offs (negative) across multiple ecosystem services. The relationships between incentives and land use, as well as between land use and ecosystem services, vary across space and time and can exhibit non-linear patterns. These relationships can be many-to-one, one-to-many, or many-to-many. The bottom link in the assessment represents the potential dynamic effect of changes in the supply of ecosystem services on incentive prices.

Garrett and Neves (2016) have identified different sources of short- and long-term incentive mechanisms and provided examples of their implementation (Figure 2).

Source: Garrett, L. and Neves, B. (2016) |

Figure 2 Incentives, investments, and mechanisms

3.3 Soil health business models

To perform the following analysis, it was used the theoretical framework developed in *D1.1 Baseline conceptual framework*. The presented business model framework was concretized in terms of the incentives' influence on soil health and the relation with the soil health strategies.

This research aims to identify and assess the incentives that can help make a business model sustainable from the perspective of soil health. This is achieved by exploring the incentives that drive farmers to take action towards improving soil health. These factors (incentives) are then applied to the Business Model Canvas (BMC). The assessment process assists in estimating the effectiveness of incentives for both soil health and the business model. By consolidating these incentives into a map, a comprehensive overview is created to understand how they contribute to the current state of the business model and the improvement of soil health. Through this process, we aim to address the question of how soil health business models can effectively contribute to the maintenance of sustainable and competitive agriculture. Our objective is to examine the role and impact of incentives for soil health in the creation of sustainable and competitive agricultural practices. To answer this question, we conduct a review of previous research on business models and their relationship to soil health and sustainable innovation. We also adopt a mapping methodology to assess the influence of different factors (incentives) on business models and soil health (Rieksta, M., Bazbauers, et al., 2021; Thomas B. Long, et al., 2017; Schoneveld, G., Di Matteo, F., Brandao, F. et al., 2015).

The aim is to identify how incentives influence business models for the case studies in the project. By reviewing and assessing the key incentives for soil health, we produce a provisional set of critical incentives mapped onto the BMC. Previous investigations into business models have focused on different contexts than agriculture.

Table 1 Canvas business model building blocks

Key partnership	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationship	Customer segments
Access to partners necessary to provide value proposition, i.e. suppliers, investors etc.	Activities connected with soil health required to carry out the other business model functions	Compelling and relevant to the case study (CS).	Ensure successful diffusion of CS. Encourage wider CS consistent behaviour.	Highlighting the users or customers of using a soil health.
Key resources		Channels		
Access to sufficient resources to provide value proposition.		Access to customers who demand CSATIs.		
Cost structure		Revenue streams		
Allow competitive pricing, and economic viability to the CS producer.		Encourage move to 'jobs done' rather than 'per unit' pricing.		

Source: Adapted from Thomas B. Long, et al., 2017.

In the context of sustainable soil health, the nine blocks of the BMC can be interpreted as follows:

- The 'Value proposition' articulates how value is created (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2009). It should address the problems faced by end-users. Without a well-developed, articulated, and demonstrable value proposition that addresses end-user concerns, incentives may fail in terms of user acceptance.
- 'Customer relationships' describe the relationship that a business has with its customers. In the context of incentives, it is important to consider whether an incentive will have a one-time impact on the sale of a product or if further 'after-sale' services are offered. This building block also articulates the extent to which customers and end-users provide input to the development of a sustainable soil health environment. In the BMC, customer relationships should encourage wider sustainability actions and could also act to minimize rebound effects. Additionally, stakeholder engagement during the development process can increase market acceptance of soil health incentives.
- 'Customer segments' are important to consider as consumer variables impact the success of sustainable agriculture. Consumer attitudes and

cognitive processes affect adoption and are related to contextual and demographic factors.

- 'Channels' link a business to its customers. Having well-developed channels is a requirement for the successful implementation of sustainable soil health policies, as they include marketing and awareness-raising activities and strategies.
- 'Key resources' are required to provide any product or service. This factor alone is of critical importance. However, the resources available to provide sustainable soil health will also affect price and quality.
- 'Key activities' are connected with soil health technology, as improved productivity and/or reduced greenhouse gas emissions are key considerations in sustainable innovations that take into account environmental, social, and economic aspects (Larson, 2011).
- 'Key partners' are necessary as firms do not operate in isolation. Other actors often hold the resources required for the delivery of the value proposition. The 'delivery chain,' highlighted by Jabbour (2008) and Jabbour et al. (2013), confirms the importance of this block for sustainable soil health. Additionally, connections to wider networks could enhance the probability of a supportive regulatory environment (Ceschin, 2013).
- 'Revenue streams': Business models for soil health should seek to develop more innovative revenue models, including shifting towards pricing based on 'jobs done' rather than per product (Boons and Lüdeke-Freund, 2013).
- The 'cost structure' should be minimized to maximize the chance for profit. For sustainable soil health business models, the revenue model should at least allow the firm to be economically viable, ensuring that their products are priced competitively, as price is still a key consideration for end-users (Brécard et al., 2009; Brouhle and Khanna, 2012).

Soil health business models are applied to upstream value chain activities, which, in this context, involve the cultivation of crops. The sustainability of such business models subsequently depends on their long-term economic viability and their ability to assimilate green growth strategies, such as 'climate-smart' and 'low emission' agriculture. Mapping these incentives onto the BMC allows us to create an initial framework that can be used to explore and research wider factors (incentives) within the context of soil health. In this sense, we use this business model framework as a lens through which to explore critical issues for the applicability of soil health incentives.

4 Methodology and source of data

4.1 Inventory of Incentives

Incentives related to soil health exist in various forms and can be implemented through different types of mechanisms. They can range from regulatory to voluntary, including public programs and private initiatives. Additionally, they encompass regulated offsets and emissions trading, direct Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES), certification, marketing labels, and adherence to cultural norms. These mechanisms can provide disincentives, such as use prohibition, fines, and taxes, as well as positive incentives, such as training, direct payment for land set aside, and improved market access. By combining these incentives, ecosystem service outcomes can be enhanced at lower social costs.

The project aims to develop a comprehensive understanding of the different incentives and ecosystems provided by soil health in each case study, the services they deliver, and their beneficiaries. Figure 2 illustrates different types of public and voluntary incentives and mechanisms. For inventory purposes, they are not considered as part of any business models. The business model type will be taken into consideration during the mapping process.

Additionally, Table 2 presents an incentive typology based on the information from Figure 2. Due to the wide variety of existing incentives in each country, Table 2 provides an exemplary typology. However, it should be noted that individual countries may adopt and implement their own specific incentives. Accordingly, each project indicated other existing incentives at the chosen NUTS level.

Table 2 Typology of incentives

Type of actions	Group of regulations	Incentives groups
1. Policy-driven incentives	1.1. Farmers and companies fulfilling government regulations (Mandatory regulations)	1.1.1 Prohibition of use
		1.1.2 Property use rights
		1.1.3 Taxes/charges
		1.1.4 Mandatory farm set-asides
		1.1.5 Other
	1.2. Pre-compliance to save costs or position private actors in a new emerging market (Flexible regulation)	1.2.1 Subsidies
		1.2.2 Conservation easements
		1.2.3 Permits and quotas
		1.2.4 Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)
		1.2.5 Offsets
		1.2.6 Impact funds
		1.2.7 Responsible sourcing of agriculture products and services
		1.2.8 Corporate social responsibility
1.2.9 Other		
	2.1.1 Green bonds	

Type of actions	Group of regulations	Incentives groups
2. Voluntary incentives	2.1. Voluntary actions with direct return on investment	2.1.2 Voluntary farm set-asides
		2.1.3 Conservation concessions
		2.1.4 Direct Payment for Ecosystem Services
		2.1.5 Other
	2.2. Voluntary action is de-linked from environmental outcomes	2.2.1 Rewards for Ecosystem Services
		2.2.2 Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)
		2.2.3 Other

Source: Garrett, L. and Neves, B. (2016) *Incentives for Ecosystem Services: Spectrum*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome, Italy.

To conduct the necessary analysis, a survey questionnaire was prepared for evaluating and describing incentives. The questionnaire is divided into two parts. The first part (Q1-Q6) consists of general questions about the surveying organization and country, identification of the incentive, land use classification, and NUTS level. The second part (Q7-Q15) collects information on whether the incentive is policy-driven or voluntary, the national policies supporting the application of such incentives, and the policies providing financial support for the incentive. It also explores the connection between the case study incentives and the main goals of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development objectives, as well as the key objectives of the new CAP 2023-2027. The final part focuses on gathering information about ecosystem services and their relationship with the incentives.

4.2 Incentives Mapping

The incentives mapping aims to categorize incentives that have been implemented within the agricultural and forestry sector to promote soil health business models, encompassing social, economic, and environmental aspects.

The goal of these soil health business models is to foster sustainable and competitive agriculture. A structured approach was developed to spatially map existing incentives and their delivery of various ecosystem services through different business models in NOVASOIL case studies. These issues raise questions regarding the social and environmental viability of soil health business models that produce safe food, as well as how existing incentives can be combined with soil restoration technologies. However, many of these investments fail to adequately address the three pillars of sustainable development: economic growth, environmental stewardship, and social inclusion.

To describe the business models, the Business Model Canvas was adopted. For analysis purposes, the nine principal canvas building blocks were merged into five blocks, aiming to enhance clarity in the mapping process. The five blocks are named as follows: Customer Value Proposition, Channels and Partnerships, Revenue and Cost Structure, Key Resources, and Key Activities. Figure 3 illustrates the transition between the Business Model Canvas building blocks and the NOVASOIL building blocks. Through this transformation, the content of the NOVASOIL business model building blocks remains unchanged, while the number of blocks is reduced to facilitate a clearer analysis. During the assessment process, the influence of incentives on sustainability and competitiveness is measured by evaluating the NOVASOIL building blocks. In the context of the business model, sustainability is interpreted through the socioeconomic blocks and the environmental/technical blocks from the NOVASOIL business model building blocks. Competitiveness is measured by the Revenue and Cost Structure block of the NOVASOIL business model building blocks.

Source: Authors' figure

Figure 3 Business Model Canvas to NOVASOIL building blocks transition.

The simplified version of the Business Model Canvas is utilized for estimating the business model (Figure 3). For the mapping purposes, the NOVASOIL business model building blocks can be further grouped into two main categories. The first category is the socioeconomic block, which comprises the customer value proposition, channels and partnerships, and revenue and cost structure. The second category is the environmental/technology block, which encompasses key resources and key activities. These two groups, along with soil health, serve as the key elements in the mapping process.

Source: Authors' figure

Figure 4 Four phases of the mapping process.

The mapping process is divided into four phases (fig. 4):

- **Identifying**

Mapping incentives is both a visual exercise and an analysis tool that helps determine the most useful incentives based on established criteria. Through mapping, it becomes possible to assess the position of incentives in relation to one another and evaluate them according to the same key criteria. This process aids in visualizing the intricate interconnections between issues and relationships. In this phase, the incentives related to each business model (BM) in various NOVASOIL case studies were identified.

- **Analyzing**

For the analysis, incentives will be mapped based on their application to soil health and business models. The research focuses on three main aspects: soil health, the socioeconomic block, and the technology block. In the project case studies, incentives will be identified and their impact on the soil health strategy, the socioeconomic block, and the environmental/technology block will be assessed. The assessment will be conducted using a three-level scale (low, medium, and high).

- **Visualizing**

To visualize the estimated incentives, a coordinate system in the form of a circle (Figure 5) will be used. The y-axis represents the influence of an incentive on the soil health strategy, while the x-axis represents the influence on the socioeconomic block of the business model.

The y-axis is directly assessed by experts. The x-axis influence is calculated as the average of its three components: customer value proposition, channels and partnerships, and revenue and cost structure. The size of the circle

indicates the influence of the incentive on the environmental/technology block, calculated as the average of key resources and key activities.

Source: Authors' figure

Figure 5 Visualisation of the mapping incentives

- Prioritizing

The incentives will be rated based on these criteria, resulting in the formation of 9 quadrants (Figure 6). Table 3 provides a description of the characteristics of each quadrant. In the graphic, additional information is conveyed through the size of the balloons. The largest size indicates a strong influence of the incentive on the environmental/technology block, while medium and small size bubbles indicate medium and low influence, respectively. The bottom left quadrants represent the lowest influence of the incentives, while the top right quadrants (VI, VIII, and IX) indicate the highest influence.

Source: Authors' figure

Figure 6 Quadrants distribution of the mapping incentives

Table 3 Characterisation of the quadrants

Quadrants	Characteristics of the quadrant
Quadrant 1	The incentive has low influence on soil health strategies and low influence on socioeconomic block of the business model
Quadrant 2	The incentive has low influence on soil health strategies and medium influence on socioeconomic block of the business model
Quadrant 3	The incentive has low influence on soil health strategies and high impact on socioeconomic block of the business model
Quadrant 4	The incentive has medium influence on soil health strategies and low influence on socioeconomic block of the business model
Quadrant 5	The incentive has medium influence on soil health strategies and medium influence on socioeconomic block of the business model
Quadrant 6	The incentive has high influence on soil health strategies and medium influence on socioeconomic block of the business model
Quadrant 7	The incentive has high influence on soil health strategies and low influence on socioeconomic block of the business model
Quadrant 8	The incentive has high influence on soil health strategies and medium influence on socioeconomic block of the business model
Quadrant 9	The incentive has high influence on soil health strategies and high influence on socioeconomic block of the business model

Source: Authors' table

4.3 Data collection

The data collection process of the incentives began in December 2022 with the preparation of instructions. Two questionnaires were created: one for the incentives inventory at national level and another focused on evaluating how the incentives enhance the business models of the case studies.

The incentives inventory database contains information for all incentives related to the soil health on national/regional level. For those incentives that affect the case studies described in the grand agreement of this project it is evaluated their relationship with SDG and new CAP objectives.

The process was facilitated by several technical meetings. The first meeting took place on March 1, 2023, with all partners in attendance, during which the analysis and expected results were presented. Additionally, three one-on-one meetings were conducted on March 10, 2023, May 12, 2023, and June 2, 2023, to provide support for the process in specific countries and to address any clarifications related to the mapping process. It is worth mentioning that the Danish partner provided the needed information for inventories in Denmark even if it is not planned in the NOVASOIL grand agreement. Based on activities in WP 5, T 5.3 Community of Practice were defined incentives for inventory and mapping analysis in each NOVASOIL country. Each project partner team completed the following two questionnaires.

The questionnaire 1 for incentive inventory is presented below:

Q1. Please, provide the name of the partner that complete the information the incentive:

Q2. Identification of the incentive:

Q3. Please indicate the hierarchical land use classification (artificial surfaces/ agricultural lands/ forest and seminatural areas/ wetlands):

Q4. Please indicate the current land use(s) of the area where the incentive is applied (Corine Land Cover 2018 Nomenclature):

Q5. Complete the country in which this incentive is applied:

Q6. NUTS level code:

Section 1. Incentive description and policies connections

Q7. Is the incentive a policy-driven incentives or a voluntary incentive?:

Q8. If the incentive is policy-driven, please check the corresponding group:)

Q9. If the incentive is policy-driven, please check the corresponding indicators:

Q10. If the incentive is voluntary, please check the corresponding group:

Q11. If the incentive is voluntary, please check the corresponding indicators:

Q12. Indicate national policies that support the application of this type of incentives:

Answer:...

Q13. Indicate policies that financially support the application of this type of incentive in Europe

Answer:...

Q14. Under the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development objectives, the business case and the application of the incentive relates with the following goals:

SDG1. End poverty in all its forms everywhere		SDG2. End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture	
SDG3. Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages.		SDG4. Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.	
SDG6. Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all		SDG7. Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all	
SDG8. Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all		SDG9. Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation	
SDG10. Reduce inequality within and among countries		SDG11. Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable	
SDG12. Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns		SDG13. Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts	
SDG15. Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss.		SDG17. Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalise the global partnership for sustainable development	

Q15. As you know, the new CAP 2023-2027 is built around 10 key objectives, which focus on economic, social, and environmental goals. Select the key policy objectives in relation with the business case and the application of the incentive.

to ensure a fair income for farmers		to increase competitiveness	
to improve the position of farmers in the food chain		climate change action	
environmental care		to preserve landscapes and biodiversity	
to support generational renewal		vibrant rural areas	
to protect food and health quality		fostering knowledge and innovation	

Section 2. Ecosystem services delivery

Q16. Did land use change because of the implementation of incentive? In what way:

Answer:

Q17. Specify the main soil health indicators in relation:

Soil Organic matter		pH	
Cation exchange capacity (CEC)		Soil structure	
Water drainage		Tonnes CO2 sequestered	
Vegetation cover		Landscape heterogeneity	
Area of forest and other wooded lands			

Q18. Specify the main ecosystem services enhanced by incentive:

Landscape and scenery		Soil quality	
Recreational access / Improvements to physical and mental health		Water quality	
Cultural heritage		Climate regulation - carbon storage	
Biodiversity		Water quantity (e.g. water retention)	
Quality and security products		Resilience to natural hazards	
Air Quality		Climate regulation	
Farm animal health and welfare			

Q19. How does the application of this incentive improve these ecosystem services?

Answer:

-----END OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE -----

The following information pertains to the **mapping evaluation**. The analysis aims to determine how incentives enhance the business models of the case studies.

The provided form establishes connections between incentives, soil-restoring strategies, and business models for soil health. The evaluation employs a

three-point scale ranging from 1 to 3 (low/medium/high). A score of 1 indicates a low influence of the incentive on the indicator, 2 signifies a medium influence, and 3 represents a high influence between the incentive and the respective indicator.

Incentives	Soil health influence	Influence over soil health strategy		Soil health business model/Case study				
		Fertilization yes/no	Remediation yes/no	Customer value proposition	Channels and partnerships	Revenue and cost structure	Key resources	Key activities
(that column will be filled after the inventory)								
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

5 Results

5.1 Incentive analysis

Based on the collected information from our partners regarding incentives in different countries, we can classify them into three groups (Table 4). The results reveal variations among the countries, leading to their categorization into distinct groups according to the number of incentives.

The first group comprises countries with fewer than 10 incentives. These include Bulgaria, Denmark, Estonia, Latvia, and Spain. Among these countries, Denmark, Spain, and Latvia have the highest number of incentives, with 10 each. It is worth noting that Bulgaria, Latvia, and Estonia have a relatively balanced distribution between policy-driven and voluntary incentives, whereas Spain exclusively relies on policy-driven incentives.

The second group consists of Germany, England, France, and Italy, with a range of 16 to 30 incentives. Germany possesses the highest number of incentives within this group, with 30 in total. France and Italy also have a significant number of incentives, with 22 and 16 respectively. In this group, voluntary incentives dominate over policy-driven incentives, except for France, which does not have any policy-driven incentives.

The third group consists of the Netherlands, which stands alone with 76 incentives. The Netherlands exhibits a significantly higher number of incentives compared to the other countries. The focus in the Netherlands is primarily on policy-driven incentives, with 70 out of the 76 falling into this category. Only six incentives are voluntary in nature.

Table 4 Number of incentives by country

	Total	Policy-driven incentives	Voluntary incentives
Netherlands	76	70	6
Germany	30	4	26
England	31	4	27
France	22	0	22
Italy	16	4	12
Bulgaria	10	5	5
Denmark	10	7	3
Latvia	10	7	3
Spain	10	10	0
Estonia	8	6	2
Total	223	117	106

Source: Own calculations

The distribution of incentives varies among the countries. The Netherlands stands out with a high number of predominantly policy-driven incentives. In contrast, countries like Germany, England, France, and Italy have a considerable number of voluntary incentives. The rest of the countries in the dataset have a smaller number of incentives, and their distribution is relatively balanced between policy-driven and voluntary approaches.

5.1.1 General overview

This section analyses the relation between the incentives and soil health indicators, the effect on the land use, and the financing sources of the incentives.

5.1.1.1 Financial support of the applied incentives

In **France**, National rural development program supports financially the application of the incentives. CAP finances all 22 of the incentives. National legislation and CAP (LAW 42/2007, of December 13, on Natural Heritage and Biodiversity, Decree 23/2012, of February 14, which regulates the conservation and sustainable use of wild flora and fauna and their habitats) cover the application of the incentives.

CAP finances 8 incentive in **Spain**, 1 is without any financial support, and FEDER finances 1 incentive.

In **United Kingdom**, CAP finances 28 out of 31 incentives, 3 have no financial support.

In **Germany**, CAP finances 21 out of 31 incentives, 1 is financed from Energie- und Klimafonds (EKF) der Bundesregierung and 8 does not have any financial support.

In **Bulgaria**, CAP finances all 10 incentives and National Rural Development Program regulates the rules for financing.

In **Netherlands**, CAP finances 15 incentives, CAP together with European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (AEFRD) finance 43 incentives, and 8 have no financing.

In **Estonia**, CAP finances 7 incentives, and 1 is financed by Baltic Sea Actin Plan.

In **Italy**, Rural Development Programme - Tuscany RDP 2014-20 finances 7 incentives, CAP finances 5 incentives, 1 has no financing and 3 are financed by local legislation.

In **Denmark**, 3 are financed by CAP, 5 are financed by Rural development (Ecoschemes), and 2 have no financing.

In **Latvia**, CAP finances 7 incentives, 2 have no financing and national legislation finances 1 incentive.

5.1.1.2 Soil health indicators in relation to the analysed incentives

The incentives are analysed in terms of relation to nine important soil health indicators. The focus is on the following:

- Soil Organic matter;
- pH;
- Cation exchange capacity (CEC);
- Soil structure;
- Water drainage;
- Tonnes CO₂ sequestered;
- Vegetation cover;
- Landscape heterogeneity;
- Area of forest and other wooded lands.

In general, the most important indicators are soil structure, soil organic matter, and tonnes CO₂ sequestered, which reflects the focus of the analysis and the adopted measures related to the climate change (fig. 7). Less significant are pH, and area of forest and other wooden lands. In the middle are landscape heterogeneity, vegetation cover, water drainage, and cation exchange capacity (CEC).

Source: Own calculations

Figure 7 Soil health indicators evaluated for all countries.

There is no difference between policy-driven and voluntary incentives in terms of soil organic matter, soil structure, pH, and Area of forest and other wooded lands.

In terms of soil health indicators, policy-driven incentives influence CEC, tonnes CO2 sequestered, and vegetation cover (fig. 8).

Source: Own calculations

Figure 8 Soil health indicators evaluated for policy-driven incentives.

In addition, it should be noted that other indicators, such as reduced cultivation, lower greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, improved area quality, land set aside, nitrogen loss reduction, and increased diversity in cropping, are also considered.

On the other hand, voluntary incentives are related to water drainage, vegetation cover, and landscape heterogeneity (fig. 9).

Source: Own calculations

Figure 9 Soil health indicators evaluated for voluntary incentives.

There are other defined indicators such as soil fertility, soil erosion, soil coverage, less soil removal, nutrient conservation.

5.1.1.3 Land use change due to implementation of incentives

Another important aspect of the analysis is to research how incentives influence land use. The analysis shows that 24% of the incentives do not change land use (fig. 10). Nearly half of the incentives (47%) are not specifically focused on land use. On the other hand, 29% of the incentives have an impact on land use.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 10 Share of the incentives that affect land use.

The ways that affect the land use could be summaries as follows:

- Moving from urban or degraded areas to green areas.
- Conversion to grasslands.
- Grasslands on the edge of the arable lands.
- Increasing soil fertility.
- Soil conservation.
- Improvement of the soil management.
- Moving to organic production.
- Delayed loss of nitrogen.
- Helping the transition for a better compliance of CAP 2023-2027 requirements.

5.1.2 Analysis of incentive by country

Netherlands

In the Netherlands under the "Mandatory" group, there are 9 incentives, specifically related to mandatory farm set-asides (table 5). In the "Flexible" group, there are 60 incentives, primarily in the form of subsidies, along with 1 incentive for permits and quotas. The group where "Voluntary action is de-linked from environmental outcomes" consists of 6 incentives, including rewards for ecosystem services and marketing labels without certifications or standards. This diverse range of incentives reflects the Netherlands' approach to incentivizing environmental practices and promoting sustainable actions across various sectors.

Table 5 Number of the incentives in Netherlands by group of regulation and incentive group

Group of regulation	No	Incentive group	No
Mandatory	9	Mandatory farm set-asides	9
Flexible	60	Subsidies	63
		Permits and quotas	1
Voluntary action is de-linked from environmental outcomes	6	Rewards for Ecosystem Services	5
		Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	1

Source: Own calculations

Germany

In Germany, within the "Mandatory" group, there are 3 incentives specifically associated with the prohibition of use (Table 6). In the "Flexible" group, there is 1 incentive categorized as "Other". The group labeled as "Voluntary actions with a direct return on investment" comprises 19 incentives, which include green bonds (1), conservation concessions (2), and direct payments for ecosystem services (16). Lastly, the group referred to as "Voluntary action de-

linked from environmental outcomes" consists of 7 incentives, primarily focused on rewards for ecosystem services. Additionally, there are 3 incentives categorized as "Other," which may include compensatory payments.

Table 6 Number of incentives in Germany by group of regulations and incentive group

Group of regulation	No	Incentive group	No
Mandatory	3	Prohibition of use	3
Flexible	1	Other	1
Voluntary actions with direct return on investment	19	Green bonds	1
		Conservation concessions	2
		Direct Payment for Ecosystem Services	16
Voluntary action is de-linked from environmental outcomes	7	Rewards for Ecosystem Services	4
		Other (compensatory payments)	3

Source: Own calculations

United Kingdom

In the United Kingdom, the most prevalent group of incentives is the "Voluntary actions with direct return on investment," consisting of 27 incentives that primarily involve direct payments for ecosystem services (table 7). Alongside, there are 2 incentives categorized under the "Mandatory" group, which pertain to property use rights, and 2 incentives within the "Flexible" group, encompassing subsidies, permits, and quotas. This diverse range of incentives exemplifies the United Kingdom's approach to promoting environmental sustainability by employing a combination of mandatory, flexible, and voluntary measures.

Table 7 Number of the incentives in United Kingdom by group of regulation and incentive group

Group of regulation	No	Incentive group	No
Mandatory	2	Property use rights	2
Flexible	2	Subsidies	1
		Permits and quotas	1
Voluntary actions with direct return on investment	27	Direct Payment for Ecosystem Services	27

Source: Own calculations

France

In France, the "Voluntary actions with direct return on investment" group consists of 22 incentives, including conservation concessions, direct payments for ecosystem services, cultural and social norms, and compensatory payments (table 8).

Table 8 Number of the incentives in France by group of regulation and incentive group

Group of regulation	No	Incentive group	No
Voluntary actions with direct return on investment	22	Conservation concessions, Direct Payment for Ecosystem Services Cultural and social norms, Compensatory payment	22

Source: Own calculations

Italy

In Italy, "Mandatory" group includes one incentive related to the prohibition of use (table 9). Within the "Flexible" group, there are 3 incentives, including subsidies and marketing labels with certificates or sustainability standards. The "Voluntary actions with direct return on investment" group consists of 10 incentives, encompassing voluntary farm set-asides, direct payments for ecosystem services, compensatory payments, and rewards for ecosystem services. Additionally, there are two incentives categorized under "Voluntary action is de-linked from environmental outcomes," specifically related to marketing labels without certificates or standards. This range of incentives highlights Italy's efforts to encourage a combination of mandatory and voluntary actions, as well as direct financial incentives, to promote environmental sustainability across various sectors.

Table 9 Number of the incentives in Italy by group of regulation and incentive group

Group of regulation	No	Incentive group	No
Mandatory	1	Prohibition of use	1
Flexible	3	Subsidies	1
		Marketing labels (certificates/ sustainability standards)	2
		Voluntary actions with direct return on investment	10
Voluntary actions with direct return on investment	10	Voluntary farm set-asides	1
		Direct Payment for Ecosystem Services	8
		Compensatory payments	1
		Rewards for Ecosystem Services	
Voluntary action is de-linked from environmental outcomes	2	Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)	2

Source: Own calculations

Bulgaria

In Bulgaria, within the "Mandatory" group, there is one incentive specifically related to the prohibition of use (table 10). The "Flexible" group comprises four incentives, all of which are subsidies aimed at providing financial support for

environmentally beneficial actions. The "Voluntary actions with a direct return on investment" group includes five incentives, all of which focus on direct payments for ecosystem services. This distribution of incentives showcases Bulgaria's approach to promoting environmental sustainability by combining mandatory regulations, flexible financial support, and voluntary actions with direct financial incentives.

Table 10 Number of the incentives in Bulgaria by group of regulation and incentive group

Group of regulation	No	Incentive group	No
Mandatory	1	Prohibition of use	1
Flexible	4	Subsidies	4
Voluntary actions with direct return on investment	5	Direct Payment for Ecosystem Services	5

Source: Own calculations

Denmark

In Denmark, the "Flexible" group consists of 7 incentives, all of which are subsidies aimed at providing financial support for environmentally beneficial activities (table 11). The "Voluntary action is de-linked from environmental outcomes" group includes 3 incentives, with 2 incentives related to voluntary farm set-asides and 1 incentive categorized as "Other". This distribution of incentives reflects Denmark's approach to promoting environmental sustainability by providing financial support through subsidies and encouraging voluntary actions that contribute to positive environmental outcomes such as farm set-asides.

Table 11 Number of the incentives in Denmark by group of regulation and incentive group

Group of regulation	No	Incentive group	No
Flexible	7	Subsidies	7
Voluntary action is de-linked from environmental outcomes	3	Voluntary farm set-asides	2
		Other (Compensatory payments)	1

Source: Own calculations

Latvia

In Latvia, the "Flexible" group consists of 7 incentives, all of which are subsidies (Table 12). The "Voluntary action de-linked from environmental outcomes" group includes 3 incentives, with 1 incentive specifically focused on rewards for ecosystem services, and 2 incentives falling under the category of "Other". This distribution of incentives highlights Latvia's approach to promoting environmental sustainability by providing financial support through subsidies

and encouraging voluntary actions that contribute to positive environmental outcomes, including the provision of rewards for ecosystem services.

Table 12 Number of the incentives in Latvia by group of regulation and incentive group

Group of regulation	No	Incentive group	No
Flexible	7	Subsidies	7
Voluntary action is de-linked from environmental outcomes	3	Rewards for Ecosystem Services	1
		Other	2

Source: Own calculations

Estonia

In Estonia, within the "Mandatory" group, there is 1 incentive related to the prohibition of use (table 13). The "Flexible" group consists of 6 incentives, primarily subsidies, aimed at providing financial support for environmentally beneficial actions. Additionally, within the "Flexible" group, there are 3 incentives categorized as compensatory payments. The "Voluntary actions with direct return on investment" group includes 2 incentives specifically related to green bonds and offsets. This distribution of incentives reflects Estonia's approach to promoting environmental sustainability by combining mandatory regulations, flexible financial support, and voluntary actions with direct financial returns on investment.

Table 13 Number of the incentives in Estonia by group of regulation and incentive group

Group of regulation	No	Incentive group	No
mandatory	1	Prohibition of use	1
Flexible	6	Subsidies	3
		Compensatory payment	3
Voluntary actions with direct return on investment	1	Green bonds	1
		Offsets	1

Source: Own calculations

Spain

In Spain, the "Mandatory" group includes 2 incentives, one related to the prohibition of use and another categorized as "Other" (table 14). The "Flexible" group consists of 8 incentives, one of them specifically focused on marketing labels with certificates or sustainability standards. Seven of the incentives are subsidies. This distribution of incentives suggests that Spain utilizes a combination of mandatory regulations and flexible measures, such as marketing labels and subsidies, to promote environmental sustainability and regulate specific activities.

Table 14 Number of the incentives in Spain by group of regulation and incentive group

Group of regulation	No	Incentive group	No
Mandatory	2	Prohibition of use	1
		Other (compensatory payment)	1
Flexible	8	Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)	1
		Subsidies	6

Source: Own calculations

5.2 Incentive mapping

5.2.1 General overview

The incentive mapping is made based on the incentives that influence the case study reported in the NOVASOIL grand agreement using questionnaire 2 presented in section 4.3.

In addition, from questionnaire 1, presented in the same section, was analysed the relation between those incentives and sustainability development goals. These goals encompass economic, social, and environmental aspects, forming the foundation of the new CAP 2023-2027 and soil health strategies.

5.2.1.1 Mapping identification

There are thirteen case studies defined under the project NOVASOIL grand agreement (table 15).

Table 15 Case studies included in the NOVASOIL project

Country	Number of case studies
Bulgaria	1
Estonia	1
Germany	3
Italy	3
Latvia	1
Netherlands	1
Spain	2
United Kingdom	1
Total	13

Source: Own calculations

Some of the case studies are not suitable for mapping the business model, such as the *Rabo Carbon Bank* in the Netherlands and *CiRAA LTEs* on conventional and organic agriculture in Italy.

Rabo Carbon Bank is a private (bank) pilot initiative that remunerates farmers for carbon credits. The case study will investigate the willingness to participate in the scheme among farmers and the potential for upscaling. The status of the case study makes unreliable the evaluation of the business model.

CiRAA LTEs are a series of long term experiments (LTEs) carried out at large plots/field scale at the Centre for Agrienvironmental Research "Enrico Avanzi" of the University of Pisa. Two field experiments are focusing on the application of conservation agriculture techniques (i.e. reduced or no tillage, cover crops), whereas the third one dealt with organic vs conventional farming systems. Taking into consideration these facts, it could not be evaluated its business model.

Others were not evaluated, including Integrated production in Spain and *AgoraNatura* in Germany. Therefore, the mapping of the business models is conducted on nine case studies (table 16). For these case studies, the incentives that have a direct influence on the business model are evaluated. A total of 61 incentives were identified in 7 countries.

Table 16 Case studies included in mapping evaluation.

Nº	Country	Business model type	Name	code	Incentives
1	Spain	Value chain	Organic wine in Rueda, Spain (Rueda)	ES_ECOSCH_PD31	Direct payment for soil cover in permanent crops
<i>Spain total number of incentives</i>					7
2	Bulgaria	Value chain	Integrated production in the vineyards with vinery and rural tourism	BG_CSOILER_PERMPLANT	Direct payments for conversion of arable agricultural land into permanent grass areas
			Integrated production in the vineyards with vinery and rural tourism	BG_CSOILER_DRAINAGE	Direct payments for conversion of arable agricultural land into permanent grass areas
<i>Bulgaria total number of incentives</i>					2
3	Italy ¹	Collective and value chain	District of the Sands - Emilia-Romagna	IT_GLOBAL_GAP_IFA	GLOBALGAP
				IT_SQNPI_LABLE	SQNPI
				IT_QUALSCHEME_AGRIPROD	PSR measure 3 (quality systems)
				IT_AGRI_ENV_CLIM_PAYMENT	PSR measure 10 (agro-environmental payments)
			IT_NAT2_WATER_PAY	PSR measure 12 (Natura2000)	

Nº	Country	Business model type	Name	code	Incentives
				IT-ORG_FARMING	PSR measure 11 (organic)
4	Italy 2	Collective and value chain	A model for multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas - Tuscany Region	IT_GREENING	Greening
				IT-ORG_FARMING	Organic farming
				IT_AGRI_ENV_CLIM_PAYMENT	Agri-environmental-climate payments
				IT_INTEGR_SUPPLY_CHAIN	Integrated projects supply chain - Progetti integrati di filiera (PIF) - Tuscany 2014-2020
<i>Italy total number of incentives</i>					10
5	Latvia	Value chain	Crop production and animal farming	LV_AGRF_FORESTRY	Agroforestry transition to forestry/optimising farm economy during transformation degraded land to forestry
				LV_ESH_DPAY_TILLAGE	Eco-scheme (Direct payments for Ecosystem services) - Minimal soil tillage technologies
<i>Latvia total number of incentives</i>					2
6	Switzerland/ Germany / Austria	Agricultural production	Soil Fertility Fund	DE_KULAP_B30	KULAP-B30 (extensive Grassland)
				DE_KULAP_B32	KULAP-B32/33/34 (watercourse and erosion control strips)
				DE_KULAP_B35	KULAP-B35/36 (winter greening / intercropping)
				DE_KULAP_B37	KULAP-B37 (mulch sowing for row crops)
				DE_KULAP_B38	KULAP-B38 (stripe-/Direkt sowing for row crops)
				DE_KULAP_B43	KULAP-B43/44/45 (diverse crop rotation with flowering species, protein plants or large grain legumes)
				DE_KULAP_B19	KULAP-B19-23 (extensive grassland use for ruminants)
				DE_VNP_H11	VNP-H11 (extensive cropland management for

Nº	Country	Business model type	Name	code	Incentives
					field breeders and field wild herbs)
				DE_VPN_H12	VNP-H12-14 (fallow on arable land with self-vegetation for species protection reasons)
				DE_VPN_H20	VNP-H20 (conversion of arable land to grassland)
				DE_VPN_H30	VNP-H30 (result-based grassland use)
				DE_GRE_CROP_DIV	Greening (crop diversification)
				DE_CO2_LAND	Federal programme for boosting energy efficiency and CO2 savings in agriculture and horticulture (Bundesprogramm zur Steigerung der Energieeffizienz und CO2-Einsparung in Landwirtschaft und Gartenbau)
				DE_KULAP_B10	KULAP-B10 (organic farming)
				DE_SOIL_PROT_LAW	BBodSchG, BBodSchV (Soil Protection Law and accompanying Soil Protection Directive)
				DE_FER_LOW_PAST	DüV DüngG - Fertilizer Directive (Düngemittelverordnung – DüV) and Fertilizer Law (Düngegesetz – DüngG)
				DE_FER_DIR_AGR	DüMV Fertilizer directive (Verordnung über das Inverkehrbringen von Düngemitteln, Bodenhilfsstoffen, Kultursubstraten und Pflanzenhilfsmitteln - DüMV)
				DE_PRES_PERM_GRAS	Greening (preservation of permanent grassland)

Nº	Country	Business model type	Name	code	Incentives
				DE_FAKT1_D1	FAKT 1-D1 (no chemical-synthetic pesticides and fertilizer)
				DE_PAULA_CULT_BRE AK	PAULa (cultivation break)
				DE_FUL13	FUL-13 (10-year-set-aside)
7	Germany	Agricultural production/value chain	CO2-Land	DE_KULAP_B30	KULAP-B30 (extensive Grassland)
				DE_KULAP_B32	KULAP-B32/33/34 (watercourse and erosion control strips)
				DE_KULAP_B35	KULAP-B35/36 (winter greening / intercropping)
				DE_KULAP_B37	KULAP-B37 (mulch sowing for row crops)
				DE_KULAP_B38	KULAP-B38 (stripe-/Direkt sowing for row crops)
				DE_KULAP_B43	KULAP-B43/44/45 (diverse crop rotation with flowering species, protein plants or large grain legumes)
				DE_KULAP_B19	KULAP-B19-23 (extensive grassland use for ruminants)
				DE_VNP_H11	VNP-H11 (extensive cropland management for field breeders and field wild herbs)
				DE_VPN_H12	VNP-H12-14 (fallow on arable land with self-vegetation for species protection reasons)
				DE_VPN_H20	VNP-H20 (conversion of arable land to grassland)
				DE_VPN_H30	VNP-H30 (result-based grassland use)
				DE_GRE_CROP_DIV	Greening (crop diversification)
				DE_CO2_LAND	Federal programme for boosting energy efficiency and CO2 savings in agriculture and

Nº	Country	Business model type	Name	code	Incentives
					horticulture (Bundesprogramm zur Steigerung der Energieeffizienz und CO ₂ -Einsparung in Landwirtschaft und Gartenbau)
				DE_KULAP_B10	KULAP-B10 (organic farming)
				DE_SOIL_PROT_LAW	BBodSchG, BBodSchV (Soil Protection Law and accompanying Soil Protection Directive)
				DE_FER_LOW_PAST	DüV DüngG - Fertilizer Directive (Düngemittelverordnung – DüV) and Fertilizer Law (Düngegesetz – DüngG)
				DE_FER_DIR_AGR	DüMV Fertilizer directive (Verordnung über das Inverkehrbringen von Düngemitteln, Bodenhilfsstoffen, Kultursubstraten und Pflanzenschutzmitteln - DüMV)
				DE_PRES_PERM_GRAS	Greening (preservation of permanent grassland)
				DE_FAKTI_D1	FAKT 1-D1 (no chemical-synthetic pesticides and fertilizer)
				DE_PAULA_CULT_BREAK	PAULa (cultivation break)
				DE_FUL13	FUL-13 (10-year-set-aside)
<i>Germany total number of incentives</i>					42
8	Estonia	Agricultural production	Crop production	EE_ENV_FRE_ECOPLAN	Environment friendly production eco plan (specify).
				EE_SINGLE_PAYSCHEME	Single Area Payment Scheme + green direct payment.
				EE_LAND_MELIORATION	Support for land melioration. (Investment support for the development and maintenance of

Nº	Country	Business model type	Name	code	Incentives
					agricultural and forestry infrastructure)
<i>Estonia total number of incentives</i>					3
9	United Kingdom	Value chain	Crop production	UK_LENS	Direct payments for adoption of alternative land management practices
<i>United Kingdom total number of incentives</i>					1
Total number of the evaluated incentives					61

Source: Own calculations

5.2.1.2 Sustainable development goals

In terms of the relationship between incentives and sustainability, as measured by the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), a significant number of incentives are focused on SDG 15: "Protect, restore, and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss" (Fig. 11). Other important goals include SDG 6: "Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all" and SDG 13: "Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts."

Source: Own calculations

Figure 11 Numbers of incentives per sustainable development goal.

Bulgarian incentives are focused on *SDG2. End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture* and *SDG3 Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages* (table 17).

Estonia influence on *SDG2. End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture*, *SDG6. Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all*, and *SDG15. Protect, restore, and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss*.

Germany and Latvian incentives enhance mainly *SDG15. Protect, restore, and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss*.

Italian incentives work for *SDG2. End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture*, *SDG13. Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts.*, and *SDG15. Protect, restore, and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss*.

The evaluated Spanish incentives are focused on *SDG2. End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture*, *SDG11. Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable*, *SDG13. Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts*, and *SDG17. Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development*.

The English incentives affect *SDG13. Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts* and *SDG15. Protect, restore, and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss*.

Table 17 Incentive influence on SDG per country.

Country	SDG2	SDG3	SDG6	SDG7	SDG8	SDG9	SDG10	SDG11	SDG12	SDG13	SDG15	SDG17	Total incentives
Bulgaria	2	2											2
Estonia	3		3		1	1	1	1	2	2	3		3
Germany	2	4	16					2	6	4	42		42
Italy	8	6	4	4	2	4	1	3	7	10	10	2	70
Latvia		1							1	1	2	1	2
Spain	1							1		1		1	7
United Kingdom										1	1		7
													67

Source: Own calculations

5.2.1.3 New CAP 2023-2027

Additionally, the influence of the incentives related to the case studies on the 10 key objectives, which focus on economic, social, and environmental goals and form the basis of the new CAP 2023-2027, was analysed (fig. 12). The incentives have the most significant impact on *landscape and biodiversity preservation* and *environmental care*. They also affect *climate change action* and *the protection of food and health quality*.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 12 Numbers of incentives per key CAP objectives.

5.2.1.4 Soil health strategies

In cooperation with WP 2 concerning review of available technologies and practices for soil health management and improvement was defined the most common soil management strategies for improvement soil health – remediation and fertilization.

Remediation is the process of improving a contaminated site to prevent, minimize, or mitigate damage to human health and/or the environment. Contamination may be present in soils, surface water, and/or ground water. Soil remediation refers to a wide range of strategies that remove, destroy, contain, transform, or reduce availability of soil contaminants to humans and other receptors in the environment. These strategies may be conducted in situ or ex situ.

Fertilization strategy aims to reduce nutrient losses by increasing uptake by plants. For implementation of this strategy is require an understanding of the relationship between soil and plant. The estimation of crop requirements ensures that the crop needs are respected to maximise yield and reduce plant stress in a context of soil health maintenance. This strategy aims to maintain correct functioning of soil that requires all nutrients are available at a correct

rate, or one might limit soil life, or deplete soil reserves in a way that menace its future.

The following analysis assess how existing incentives can be combined with soil restoration technologies. For that purpose, the soil restoration technologies are generalized in two soil health strategies: fertilization and remediation. The analysis of the influence of the incentives over the soil health strategies show that 45.8% of the incentives have influence over the remediation soil health strategy (fig. 13). Respectively 54.2% have influence over fertilization strategy. Although, similar number of incentives covers both soil health strategies, the fertilization strategy is influenced by 8.4% more incentives.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 13 Share of the incentive by soil health strategy.

Fertilization strategy

39 incentives were identified in the Fertilization strategy represented in fig. 14 and table 18. For the socioeconomic block of the business model, the incentives: A, B, C, D, E, G, H, I, J have low influence; Incentives F, K, L, have high influence and incentives E, I, J have medium influence.

Figure 14 Mapping incentives fertilization strategy

Regarding soil health, the incentives: A, and B, have low influence. The incentives C, D, E, and F showed medium influence on soil health. Incentives G, H, I, J, K and L have high influence on soil health.

For the technology block, the following incentives had a low influence: A, B, C2, C3, C4, C5, C6, C7, C8, D1, D2, E1, G1, G2, G3, G4, G5, G6, G7, G8, H2, H3, I2, I3; Incentives C1, C9, H1, have medium influence and incentives C10, E2, F, G9, I1, I4, J1, J2, K1, K2, K3, L1, and L2 have high influence on the technology block and incentives.

Based on the quadrant classification for fertilization strategy can be prioritized incentives F, K, and L as the main which have positively important influence.

Table 18 Incentives fertilization strategy

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
A	VNP-H30 (result-based grassland use)	DE_VPN_H30	Low (1.0)	Low (1.0)	Low (1.0)	I
B	VNP-H30 (result-based grassland use)	DE_VPN_H30	Low (1.3)	Low (1.0)	Low (1.0)	I
C1	Eco-scheme (Direct payments for Ecosystem services) - Minimal soil tillage technologies	LV_ESH_DPAY_TIL LAGE	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	IV
C2	KULAP-B19-23 (extensive)	DE_KULAP_B19	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
	grassland use for ruminants)					
C3	VNP-H11 (extensive cropland management for field breeders and field wild herbs)	DE_VNP_H11	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
C4	VNP-H12-14 (fallows on arable land with self-vegetation for species protection reasons)	DE_VPN_H12	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	IV
C5	KULAP-B37 (mulch sowing for row crops)	DE_KULA_P_B37	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
C6	KULAP-B38 (stripe-/Direkt sowing for row crops)	DE_KULA_P_B38	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
C7	KULAP-B43/44/45 (diverse crop rotation with flowering species, protein plants or large grain legumes)	DE_KULA_P_B43	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	IV
C8	KULAP-B19-23 (extensive grassland use for ruminants)	DE_KULA_P_B19	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
C9	VNP-H11 (extensive cropland management for field breeders and field wild herbs)	DE_VNP_H11	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	IV
C10	VNP-H12-14 (fallows on arable land with self-vegetation for species protection reasons)	DE_VPN_H12	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	High (3.0)	IV
D1	KULAP-B37 (mulch sowing for row crops)	DE_KULA_P_B37	Low (1.3)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	IV
D2	KULAP-B38 (stripe-/Direkt sowing for row crops)	DE_KULA_P_B38	Low (1.3)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	IV

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
E1	KULAP-B43/44/45 (diverse crop rotation with flowering species, protein plants or large grain legumes)	DE_KULAP_B43	Medium (1.7)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	V
E2	Single Area Payment Scheme + green direct payment.	EE_SINGL EA_PAYS CHEME	Medium (1.7)	Medium (2.0)	High (2.5)	V
F	GLOBALGAP	IT_GLOBA L_GAP_IF A	High (2.7)	Medium (2.0)	High (3.0)	VI
G1	DüMV Fertilizer directive (Verordnung über das Inverkehrbringen von Düngemitteln, Bodenhilfsstoffen, Kultursubstraten und Pflanzenhilfsmitteln - DüMV)	DE_FER DIR_AGR	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
G2	Greening (preservation of permanent grassland)	DE_PRES PERM_G RAS	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VII
G3	FUL-13 (10-year-set-aside)	DE_FUL13	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
G4	KULAP-B35/36 (winter greening / intercropping)	DE_KULAP_B35	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VII
G5	Greening (crop diversification)	DE_GRE_CROP_DI V	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
G6	KULAP-B10 (organic farming)	DE_KULAP_B10	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VII
G7	DüMV Fertilizer directive (Verordnung über das Inverkehrbringen von Düngemitteln, Bodenhilfsstoffen, Kultursubstraten und Pflanzenhilfsmitteln - DüMV)	DE_FER DIR_AGR	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
G8	Greening (preservation of permanent grassland)	DE_PRES_PERM_G RAS	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
G9	FUL-13 (10-year-set-aside)	DE_FUL13	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VII
H1	PSR measure 10 (agro-environmental payments)	IT_AGRILE NV_CLIM_ PAYMENT	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	Medium (2.0)	VII
H2	Direct payment for soil cover in permanent crops	ES_ECOS CH_PD31	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
H3	Direct payment for soil cover in permanent crops	ES_ECOS CH_PD31	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
I1	PSR measure 12 (Natura2000)	IT_NAT2_ WATER_P AY	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VIII
I2	KULAP-B35/36 (winter greening / intercropping)	DE_KULA P_B35	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VIII
I3	Greening (crop diversification)	DE_GRE_ CROP_DI V	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VIII
I4	Environment friendly production eco plan (specify).	EE_ENV_F RE_ECOP LAN	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VIII
J1	Agri-environmental-climate payments	IT_AGRILE NV_CLIM_ PAYMENT	Medium (2.3)	High (3.0)	High (2.5)	Medium (2.3)
J2	SONPI	IT_SQNPL LABLE	Medium (2.3)	High (3.0)	High (2.5)	VIII
K1	PSR measure 11 (organic)	IT- ORG_FAR MING	High (2.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	IX
K2	Integrated projects supply chain - Progetti integrati di filiera (PIF) - Tuscany 2014-2020	IT_INTEG R_SUPPL Y_CHAIN	High (2.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	IX
K3	Direct payments for adoption of alternative land management practices	UK_LENS	High (2.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	IX
L1	Organic farming	IT- ORG_FAR MING	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	IX

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
L2	KULAP-B10 (organic farming)	DE_KULAP_B10	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	IX

Remediation strategy

38 incentives were identified in the remediation strategy represented in fig. 15 and table 19. For the socioeconomic block of the business model, the incentives: A, B, C, and D have low influence. Incentive G have high influence and incentives E and F have medium influence.

Figure 15 Mapping incentives remediation strategy

Regarding soil health, the incentives: A, and B, have medium influence. The incentives C, D, E, F and G showed high influence on soil health.

For the technology block, the following incentives had a low influence: A2, A3, A4, A5, A7, A8, A9, A10, B2, B3, C1, C2, C3, C4, C6, C7, C8, and D1. Incentives A1, A6, A11, B1, B4, D3, D4, D5, and E2, have medium influence and incentives C5, D2, E1, E3, E4, F, G1, and G2 have high influence on the technology block.

Based on the quadrant classification for fertilization strategy can be prioritized incentives E, F, and G as the main which have positively important influence.

Table 19 Incentives remediation strategy

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
A1	Eco-scheme (Direct payments for Ecosystem services) - Minimal soil tillage technologies	LV_ESH_DPAY_TILLAGE	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	IV
A2	KULAP-B32/33/34 (watercourse and erosion control strips)	DE_KULAP_B32	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
A3	KULAP-B19-23 (extensive grassland use for ruminants)	DE_KULAP_B19	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
A4	Federal programme for boosting energy efficiency and CO2 savings in agriculture and horticulture (Bundesprogramm zur Steigerung der Energieeffizienz und CO2-Einsparung in Landwirtschaft und Gartenbau)	DE_CO2_LAND	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
A5	PAULa (cultivation break)	DE_PAULA_CULT_BREAK	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
A6	KULAP-B32/33/34 (watercourse and erosion control strips)	DE_KULAP_B32	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	IV
A7	KULAP-B37 (mulch sowing for row crops)	DE_KULAP_B37	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
A8	KULAP-B38 (stripe-/Direkt sowing for row crops)	DE_KULAP_B38	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
A9	KULAP-B19-23 (extensive grassland use for ruminants)	DE_KULAP_B19	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
A10	Federal programme for boosting energy efficiency and CO2 savings in agriculture and horticulture (Bundesprogramm zur Steigerung der	DE_CO2_LAND	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
	Energieeffizienz und CO ₂ -Einsparung in Landwirtschaft und Gartenbau)					
A11	PAULa (cultivation break)	DE_PAULA_CULT_BREAK	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	IV
B1	FAKT 1-D1 (no chemical-synthetic pesticides and fertilizer)	DE_FAKT1_D1	Low (1.3)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	IV
B2	KULAP-B37 (mulch sowing for row crops)	DE_KULAP_B37	Low (1.3)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	IV
B3	KULAP-B38 (stripe-/Direkt sowing for row crops)	DE_KULAP_B38	Low (1.3)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	IV
B4	FAKT 1-D1 (no chemical-synthetic pesticides and fertilizer)	DE_FAKT1_D1	Low (1.3)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	IV
C1	KULAP-B30 (extensive Grassland)	DE_KULAP_B30	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C2	BBodSchG, BBodSchV (Soil Protection Law and accompanying Soil Protection Directive)	DE_SOIL_PROT_LAW	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C3	DüV DüngG - Fertilizer Directive (Düngemittelverordnung – DüV) and Fertilizer Law (Düngegesetz – DüngG)	DE_FER_LAW_PAST	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C4	DüMV Fertilizer directive (Verordnung über das Inverkehrbringen von Düngemitteln, Bodenhilfsstoffen, Kultursubstraten und Pflanzenhilfsmitteln - DüMV)	DE_FER_DIR_AGR	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C5	VNP-H20 (conversion of arable land to grassland)	DE_VPN_H20	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VII

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
C6	BBodSchG, BBodSchV (Soil Protection Law and accompanying Soil Protection Directive)	DE_SOIL_PROT_LAW	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C7	DüV DüngG - Fertilizer Directive (Düngemittelverordnung – DüV) and Fertilizer Law (Düngegesetz – DüngG)	DE_FER_LAW_PAST	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VII
C8	DüMV Fertilizer directive (Verordnung über das Inverkehrbringen von Düngemitteln, Bodenhilfsstoffen, Kultursubstraten und Pflanzenhilfsmitteln - DüMV)	DE_FER_DIR_AGR	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
D1	Direct payment for soil cover in permanent crops	ES_ECOSCH_PD31	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
D2	Direct payments for conversion of arable agricultural land into permanent grass areas	BG_CSOILER_PERMPLANT	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	High (2.5)	VII
D3	PSR measure 10 (agro-environmental payments)	IT_AGRLENV_CLIMPAYMENT	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	Medium (2.0)	VII
D4	Agroforestry transition to forestry/optimizing farm economy during transformation degraded land to forestry	LV_AGRF_FORESTRY	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	Medium (2.0)	VII
D5	VNP-H20 (conversion of arable land to grassland)	DE_VPNLH20	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	Medium (2.0)	VII
E1	PSR measure 12 (Natura2000)	IT_NAT2_WATERPAY	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VIII

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
E2	KULAP-B30 (extensive Grassland)	DE_KULAP_B30	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	Medium (2.0)	VIII
E3	Environment friendly production eco plan (specify).	EE_ENV_FRE_ECOP_LAN	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VIII
E4	Support for land melioration. (Investment support for the development and maintenance of agricultural and forestry infrastructure)	EE_LAND_MELIORATION	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VIII
F	SQLPI	IT_SQLPI_LABEL	Medium (2.3)	High (3.0)	High (2.5)	VIII
G1	PSR measure 11 (organic)	IT_ORG_FARMING	High (2.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	IX
G2	Direct payments for adoption of alternative land management practices	UK_LENS	High (2.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	IX

5.2.2 Case studies

Italy CS 1 –District of the Sands

The coastal area of the Emilia-Romagna Region is known for its strong agricultural vocation and high-quality horticultural production. However, soil health in this region faces significant challenges due to the high percentage of sand components, salinization, subsidence, loss of organic matter, and contamination.

Figure 16 presents the estimation and distribution of the incentives identified in the District of the Sands case study. Table 20 provides a detailed description of each incentive, including its name, estimated impact, and the quadrant in which it falls.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 16 Mapping incentives of Italy - District of Sands

Six incentives are identified in the BM District of the Sands. Four of them – C, D, E, F show a high degree of influence on soil health strategies. The remaining two incentives – B and A respectively have medium and low influence. Two incentives (F and B) have high influence on the socioeconomic block of the business model. Three incentives (D, E and A) have medium influence and one – C has low influence on socioeconomic block. The influence over the technology block of the business model is strong. Two incentives have medium influence (A and C) and the influence is estimated as high for the rest of the incentives (B, D, E and F). For this BM incentives B, D, E and F can be prioritized as the main ones which have positively important influence.

Table 20 Classification of the incentive by quadrant for District of Sands case study

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
A	PSR measure 3 (quality systems)	IT_QUALS_CHEME_AGRIPROD	Medium (2.3)	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	II
B	GLOBALGAP	IT_GLOBAL_GAP_IFA	High (2.7)	Medium (2.0)	High (3.0)	VI
C	PSR measure 10 (agro-environmental payments)	IT_AGRILENV_CLIM_PAYMENT	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	Medium (2.0)	VII
D	PSR measure 12 (Natura2000)	IT_NAT2_WATER_PAY	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VIII
E	SQNPI	IT_SQNPI_LABEL	Medium (2.3)	High (3.0)	High (2.5)	VIII
F	PSR measure 11 (organic)	IT_ORG_FARMING	High (2.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	IX

Source: Own calculations

Italy CS 2- A model for multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas

Hilly areas of the Tuscany Region are considered marginal due to their conventional extensive agriculture and limited agricultural value. These areas face various environmental and socio-economic constraints that negatively impact crop productivity and environmental quality, resulting in low farmer incomes. The prevailing cropping systems in these areas are winter cereal-based, leading to soil degradation and a decline in ecosystem services. Issues such as soil erosion, nutrient leaching, and reduction of carbon content in soils are of significant concern. The main objective of the project was to redesign the existing farming systems by introducing perennial medicinal and aromatic crops and transitioning from conventional to organic agricultural models. Simultaneously, new supply chains for organic aromatic plants with high-value final products have been developed to support the multifunctional development of the area. This involves integrating agriculture, processing, and other economic activities.

This case study aims to learn from the project's experiences by assessing the effectiveness of actions taken to improve soil fertility and health, increase productivity, enhance resilience, and valorise the landscape. The focus will be on exploring the development of business models that add value to agronomic management aimed at conserving soil health through innovative crop products, certification, and production standards.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 17 Mapping incentives of Italy - A model for multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas

Six incentives are identified in the BM for multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas (fig. 17 and table 21). Three of them – B, C, D show a high degree of influence on soil health. The remaining two incentives – A respectively have medium level of influence. Two incentives (C and D) have

high influence and two – A and B have medium influence on socioeconomic block. The influence over technology block of the business model is strong. Three incentives have medium influence (A, B and C) and the influence is estimated as high for the rest of the incentives (D, E and F). For this BM can be prioritized incentives D, E and F as the main ones to have positively important influence.

Table 21 Classification of the incentive by quadrant for A model for multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
A	Greening	IT_GREENING	Medium (1.7)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	V
B	PSR measure 10 (agro-environmental payments)	IT_AGRILENV_CLIM_PAYMENT	Medium (2.3)	High (3.0)	High (2.5)	VIII
C	Integrated projects supply chain - Progetti integrati di filiera (PIF) - Tuscany 2014-2020	IT_INTEGR_SUPPLY_CHAIN	High (2.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	IX
D	PSR measure 11 (organic)	IT_ORG_FARMING	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	IX

Source: Own calculations

Spain CS- Organic wine in Rueda

Organic wine in the Rueda case study is associated with a winery called Herederos del Marqués de Riscal, S.A., which specializes in producing organic wines and plays a significant role in the region. The winery only purchases grapes that are produced using ecological methods. Although grape producers are not directly associated in this case study, they are integrated into the value chain by adhering to the winery's standards. They undergo regular quality and residue checks and follow a strict protocol for organic production, maintaining high standards.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 18 Mapping incentives of Spain - Organic wine in Rueda case study

One incentive is identified in the BM for Organic wine in Rueda (figure 18 and table 22). It shows a high degree of influence on soil health strategies. It has low influence on socioeconomic block of the business model. The influence over technology block of the business model is low. For this BM incentives cannot be prioritized.

Table 22 Classification of the incentive by quadrant for Organic wine in Rueda case study

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
A	Direct payment for soil cover in permanent crops	ES_ECOS CH_PD31	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII

Source: Own calculations

Bulgaria CS - Integrated production in the vineyards with vinery and rural tourism

The Bulgarian case study focuses on managing the viticultural potential of the country, including overseeing the rights for planting new vineyards, replanting, and vineyard eradication. The effective functioning of this system in recent years has led to improvements and stabilization within the sector. As a result, the quality and competitiveness of Bulgarian wines have increased, both in domestic and foreign markets.

The Program for Local Traditional and Regional Traditional Products for the period 2021-2023 aims to recognize the potential of local and regional traditional products in the wine sector. It seeks to strengthen their connection with communities to foster the development of the local economy and

agricultural sector. These local and regional traditional products offer Bulgarian citizens and visitors a diverse range of tastes, quality experiences, and a connection to the culture, traditions, and local economy of the communities.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 19 Mapping incentives of Bulgaria - Integrated production in the vineyards with winery and rural tourism

Two incentives have been identified in the BM for Integrated Production in Vineyards with Winery and Rural Tourism (Fig. 19 and Table 23). Both of these incentives show a high degree of influence on soil health strategies. However, when it comes to the socioeconomic block of the business model, both incentives (A and B) have a low influence. The influence on the technology block of the business model varies, with the incentives having a medium influence, while incentive B is estimated to have a high influence. Therefore, it is not possible to prioritize the incentives for this business model.

Table 23 Classification of the incentive by quadrant for Integrated production in the vineyards with winery and rural tourism case study

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
A	Direct payments for control of soil erosion construction and maintenance of drainage furrows and across the slope	BG_CSOIL ER_DRAINAGE	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Medium (2.0)	VII
B	Direct payments for conversion of	BG_CSOIL ER_PERMPLANT	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	High (2.5)	VII

arable agricultural land into permanent grass areas					
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Source: Own calculations

Latvia CS - Crop production and animal farming

Agriculture crop (winter wheat, barley, rape seed oil, legumes) production and animal husbandry requires smart farming technologies to follow the environmental measures defined by Green Deal and from Farm to Fork strategy to ensure sustainable farming practices by effective soil management. Increase of the soil fertility, organic matter, nutrient circle management investigated through the project activities and business models.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 20 Mapping incentives of Latvia - Crop production and animal farming

Two incentives are identified in the BM for Crop production and animal farming (figure 20 and table 24). They have different influence on soil health strategies. Incentive A shows a medium degree of influence and incentive B shows high degree. All of incentives (A and B) have low influence on socioeconomic block of the business model. The influence over technology block of the business model is the same. All incentives have medium influence. Therefore, it is not possible to prioritize the incentives for this business model.

Table 24 Classification of the incentive by quadrant Crop production and animal farming case study

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
A	Eco-scheme (Direct payments for Ecosystem services)	LV_ESH_DPAY_TIL LAGE	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	IV
B	Agroforestry transition to forestry	LV_AGRF_FORESTR Y	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	Medium (2.0)	VII

Source: Own calculations

Switzerland /Germany/ Austria CS - Soil Fertility Fund

The Soil Fertility Fund is an initiative started in Switzerland with the main objectives of preserving soil fertility, raising public awareness, and developing concepts for increasing society’s participation in the soil fertility challenge. Hereby, the initiative focuses on farm-individual measures to foster soil fertility on organic farms. The case study will explore viability, success factors, and the potential to upscale the project.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 21 Mapping incentives of Switzerland /Germany/ Austria - Soil Fertility Fund

21 incentives have been identified in the business model for the Soil Fertility Fund in Switzerland, Germany, and Austria (Figure 21 and Table 25). Four of these incentives, namely E, F, G, and H, show a high degree of influence on soil health strategies. The remaining three incentives, B, C, and D, have a medium influence, while incentive A has a low influence. One incentive, H, has a high

influence on the socioeconomic block of the business model. Two incentives, C and D, have a medium influence, and five incentives, A, B, C, E, and F, have a low influence on the socioeconomic block. When it comes to the technology block of the business model, there is a strong influence. Six groups of incentives, namely B, C, D, E, F, and G, have a medium influence. The influence is estimated as high for incentive H and low for incentive A. Therefore, the main prioritized incentive for this BM is H, as it has a significant positive influence.

Table 25 Classification of the incentive by quadrant for Soil Fertility Fund case study

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
A	VNP-H30 (result-based grassland use)	DE_VPN_H30	Low (1.3)	Low (1.0)	Low (1.0)	I
B1	KULAP-B32/33/34 (watercourse and erosion control strips)	DE_KULA_P_B32	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
B2	KULAP-B19-23 (extensive grassland use for ruminants)	DE_KULA_P_B19	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
B3	VNP-H11 (extensive cropland management for field breeders and field wild herbs)	DE_VNP_H11	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
B4	VNP-H12-14 (fallows on arable land with self-vegetation for species protection reasons)	DE_VPN_H12	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	IV
B5	Federal programme for boosting energy efficiency and CO2 savings in agriculture and horticulture (Bundesprogramm zur Steigerung der Energieeffizienz und CO2-Einsparung in Landwirtschaft und Gartenbau)	DE_CO2_LAND	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
B6	PAULa (cultivation break)	DE_PAULA_CULT_BREAK	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
C1	KULAP-B37 (mulch sowing for row crops)	DE_KULA_P_B37	Low (1.3)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	IV
C2	KULAP-B38 (stripe-/Direkt sowing for row crops)	DE_KULA_P_B38	Low (1.3)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	IV
C3	FAKT 1-D1 (no chemical-synthetic pesticides and fertilizer)	DE_FAKTI_D1	Low (1.3)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	IV
D	KULAP-B43/44/45 (diverse crop rotation with flowering species, protein plants or large grain legumes)	DE_KULA_P_B43	Medium (1.7)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	V
E1	BBodSchG, BBodSchV (Soil Protection Law and accompanying Soil Protection Directive)	DE_SOIL_PROT_LAW	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
E2	DüV DüngG - Fertilizer Directive (Düngemittelverordnung - DüV) and Fertilizer Law (Düngegesetz - DüngG)	DE_FER_LAW_PAST	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
E3	DüMV Fertilizer directive (Verordnung über das Inverkehrbringen von Düngemitteln, Bodenhilfsstoffen, Kultursubstraten und Pflanzenhilfsmitteln - DüMV)	DE_FER_DIR_AGR	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
E4	Greening (preservation of permanent grassland)	DE_PRES_PERM_GRASS	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VII
E5	FUL-13 (10-year-set-aside)	DE_FUL13	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
F	VNP-H20 (conversion of arable land to grassland)	DE_VPN_H20	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	Medium (2.0)	VII
G1	KULAP-B30 (extensive Grassland)	DE_KULA_P_B30	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	Medium (2.0)	VIII

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
G2	KULAP-B35/36 (winter greening / intercropping)	DE_KULAP_B35	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VIII
G3	Greening (crop diversification)	DE_GRE_CROP_DIV	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VIII
H	KULAP-B10 (organic farming)	DE_KULAP_B10	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	IX

Source: Own calculations

Germany CS - CO2-Land

"CO2-Land" is a recently established carbon farming initiative in south-western Germany that offers carbon credit certificates through carbon sequestration on partner farms. The case study aims to examine the initiative's experiences and identify success factors that can contribute to the development of similar projects across Europe. Additionally, it will explore the acceptance of the concept among farmers and society, as this acceptance is crucial for scaling up the initiative. The study will also explore strategies to enhance acceptance and facilitate the expansion of the concept.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 22 Mapping incentives of Germany - CO2-Land

21 incentives are identified in the BM CO2-Land (figure 22 and table 26). The group of incentives C shows a high degree of influence on soil health strategies. The remaining incentives – those from group B show medium level and incentive A has low influence on soil health strategies. All incentives have

low influence on socioeconomic block of the business model. It is not possible to prioritize the incentives for this business model.

Table 26 Classification of the incentive by quadrant for CO2-Land case study

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
A	VNP-H30 (result-based grassland use)	DE_VPN_H30	Low (1.3)	Low (1.0)	Low (1.0)	I
B1	KULAP-B32/33/34 (watercourse and erosion control strips)	DE_KULA_P_B32	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	IV
B2	KULAP-B37 (mulch sowing for row crops)	DE_KULA_P_B37	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
B3	KULAP-B38 (stripe-/Direkt sowing for row crops)	DE_KULA_P_B38	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
B4	KULAP-B43/44/45 (diverse crop rotation with flowering species, protein plants or large grain legumes)	DE_KULA_P_B43	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	IV
B5	KULAP-B19-23 (extensive grassland use for ruminants)	DE_KULA_P_B19	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
B6	VNP-H11 (extensive cropland management for field breeders and field wild herbs)	DE_VNP_H11	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	IV
B7	VNP-H12-14 (fallow on arable land with self-vegetation for species protection reasons)	DE_VPN_H12	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	High (3.0)	IV
B8	Federal programme for boosting energy efficiency and CO2 savings in agriculture and horticulture (Bundesprogramm zur Steigerung der Energieeffizienz und CO2-Einsparung in	DE_CO2_LAND	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
	Landwirtschaft und Gartenbau)					
B9	PAULa (cultivation break)	DE_PAULA_CULT_BREAK	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	IV
C1	VNP-H20 (conversion of arable land to grassland)	DE_VPNL_H20	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VII
C2	KULAP-B30 (extensive Grassland)	DE_KULAP_B30	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C3	KULAP-B35/36 (winter greening / intercropping)	DE_KULAP_B35	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VII
C4	Greening (crop diversification)	DE_GRE_CROP_DIV	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C5	KULAP-B10 (organic farming)	DE_KULAP_B10	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VII
C6	BBodSchG, BBodSchV (Soil Protection Law and accompanying Soil Protection Directive)	DE_SOIL_PROT_LAW	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C7	DüV DüngG - Fertilizer Directive (Düngemittelverordnung - DüV) and Fertilizer Law (Düngegesetz - DüngG)	DE_FERL_OW_PAST	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VII
C8	DüMV Fertilizer directive (Verordnung über das Inverkehrbringen von Düngemitteln, Bodenhilfsstoffen, Kultursubstraten und Pflanzenhilfsmitteln - DüMV)	DE_FER_DIR_AGR	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C9	Greening (preservation of permanent grassland)	DE_PRES_PERM_GRASS	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C10	FAKT 1-D1 (no chemical-synthetic pesticides and fertilizer)	DE_FAKTI_D1	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C11	FUL-13 (10-year-set-aside)	DE_FUL13	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VII

Source: Own calculations

Estonia CS - Crop production

ETKI is a state research and development institute in the area of governance of the Estonian Ministry of Rural Affairs.

Among others, ETKI researches impact of catch crops, tillage technologies and fertilizing on soil physical, chemical and biological properties. The crop production technologies and machinery use are analysed to assess their impact on the environment and farms economy.

ETKI cooperates with other organizations developing digital maps on the basis of soil properties. These tools help to choose crops on fields, show fields soil texture, carbon stock, moisture level or erosion level. The usability of these digital maps to develop new business models aiming at adding value to soil conservation should be investigated.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 23 Mapping incentives of Estonia - Crop production

Three incentives are identified in the BM Crop production (figure 23 and table 27). The group of incentives B shows a high degree of influence on soil health strategies. The remaining incentive A shows a medium level of influence on soil health strategies. All incentives have a medium influence on the socioeconomic block of the business model. Therefore, incentive group B can be prioritized as the main group, as it has a significantly positive influence.

Table 27 Classification of the incentive by quadrant for Estonia Crop production case study

Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model	Estimated influence of the incentive on	Estimated influence of the	Quadrant

			socioeconomic block	the soil health strategies	incentive on the technology block	
A	Single Area Payment Scheme + green direct payment.	EE_ENV_FRE_ECOP_LAN	Medium (1.7)	Medium (2.0)	High (2.5)	V
B1	Environment friendly production eco plan (specify).	EE_SINGL_EA_PAYS_CHEME	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VIII
B2	Support for land melioration. (Investment support for the development and maintenance of agricultural and forestry infrastructure)	EE_LAND_MELIORATION	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VIII

Source: Own calculations

United Kingdom CS - Crop production

A Landscape Enterprise Network is a governance model wherein multiple businesses co-procure environmental benefits that are co-produced by a collection of land managers, with a supply aggregator and demand aggregator facilitating the process. There are a number of initial LENs network operating in Cumbria and East Anglia that will be the focus on this case study.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 24 Mapping incentives of United Kingdom - Crop production

One incentive is identified in the BM for Crop production (figure 24 and table 28). It has high influence on soil health strategies and high influence on

socioeconomic block of the business model. For this BM incentive A can be prioritized as the main one, which has positively important influence.

Table 28 Classification of the incentive by quadrant for United Kingdom Crop production case study

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
A	Direct payments for adoption of alternative land management practices	UK_LENS	High (2.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	IX

Source: Own calculations

5.2.3 Type of business model

This analysis aimed to present the influence of all incentives connected with NOVASOIL BM types – Value chain, Collective and value chain, Agricultural production, and Agricultural production/value chain.

Business Models - Value chain

Business models under the value chain typology consist of different models where the producer or product is seen and managed as part of a larger system. It is a multistage process that allows for the application of various business models. Value chains can help increase efficiency in product creation or provide a competitive advantage by delivering unique products at the lowest possible price. Figure 25 provides a summary of the incentives that fall under the value chain type of business models, while Table 29 offers complete descriptions and ratings of these incentives.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 25 Mapping incentives for Business Models - Value chain

Six incentives have been identified in the value chain business model (Table 27). Three of them, namely B, C, and D, show a high degree of influence on soil health strategies. The remaining incentive, A, has a medium influence. One incentive, D, has a high influence on the socioeconomic block of the business model, while incentives A, B, and C have low influence in this block. The influence over the technology block of the business model varies. Two groups of incentives have a high influence, namely C and D, while the influence is estimated as low for incentives A and B. Therefore, the main prioritized incentive for this business model is D, as it has a significant positive influence.

Table 29 Classification of the incentive by quadrant for Business Models - Value chain

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
A	Eco-scheme (Direct payments for Ecosystem services)	LV_ESH_DPAY_TILLAGE	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	VII
B	Direct payments for conversion of arable agricultural land into permanent grass areas	BG_CSOILER_PERMPLANT	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Medium (2.0)	VII
C1	Direct payment for soil cover in permanent crops	ES_ECOSCH_PD31	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C2	Direct payments for conversion of arable agricultural land into permanent grass areas	BG_CSOILER_PERMPLANT	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	High (2.5)	VII
C3	Agroforestry transition to forestry	LV_AGRF_FORESTRY	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	Medium (2.0)	VII
D	Direct payments for adoption of alternative land management practices	UK_LENS	High (3.0)	High (2.7)	High (3.0)	IX

Source: Own calculations

Business Models - Collective and value chain

Collective and value chain business model adds a collective action in the business model. It can be in the form of regulation, certification, or other similar measures. The outcome of applying the model has an impact on society, resources, and technology. Figure 26 provides a summary of the incentives associated with Collective and Value Chain business models. Table 30 presents detailed descriptions and ratings of these incentives.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 26 Mapping incentives for Business Models - Collective and value chain

Ten incentives are identified in the BM Collective and value chain. Five of them - D, E, F, G, and H - show a high degree of influence on soil health strategies. The remaining three incentives - B, C, and D - have a medium influence, while A has a low influence. Among these incentives, G and H have a high influence on the socioeconomic block of the business model. Four incentives - A, B, F, and G - have a medium influence, and one - D - has a low influence on the socioeconomic block. The influence over the technology block of the business model is mixed. Three incentives - A, B, and D - have a medium influence, while the influence is estimated as high for the rest of the incentives - C, E, F, G, and H. Therefore, incentives C, E, F, F, G, and H can be prioritized as the main incentives, as they have a significantly positive and important influence.

Table 30 Mapping incentives for Business Models - Collective and value chain

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
A	PSR measure 3 (quality systems)	IT_QUALS CHEME_A GRIPROD	Medium (2.3)	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	II
B	Greening - IT3c.	IT_GREEN ING	Medium (1.7)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	V

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
C	GLOBALGAP	IT_GLOBAL_GAP_IFA	High (2.7)	Medium (2.0)	High (3.0)	VI
D	PSR measure 10 (agro-environmental payments)	IT_AGRILENV_CLIM_PAYMENT	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	Medium (2.0)	VII
E	PSR measure 12 (Natura2000)	IT_NAT2_WATER_PAY	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VIII
F1	SQLPI	IT_SQLPI_LABEL	Medium (2.3)	High (3.0)	High (2.5)	VIII
F2	PSR measure 10 - IT2	IT_AGRILENV_CLIM_PAYMENT	Medium (2.3)	High (3.0)	High (2.5)	VIII
G1	PSR measure 11 (organic)	IT_ORG_FARMING	High (2.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	IX
G2	PIF - IT2	IT_INTEGR_SUPPLY_CHAIN	High (2.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	IX
H	PSR measure 11 - IT3c	IT_ORG_FARMING	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	IX

Source: Own calculations

Business Models - Agricultural production

The agricultural production business model emphasizes farm-level measures to foster soil fertility. Within this model, various instruments can be employed, such as conservation agriculture techniques (e.g., reduced or no tillage, cover crops), crowdfunding for conservation projects, crop production technologies and machinery, and the use of measurement and digital tools that aid in improving soil health. Figure 27 provides a summary of the incentives associated with the agricultural production business model. For detailed descriptions and ratings of the incentives, please refer to Table 31.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 27 Mapping incentives for Business Models - Agricultural production

Twenty-four incentives are identified in the BM Agricultural production. Four of them - E, F, G, and H - show a high degree of influence on soil health strategies. The remaining three incentives - B, C, and D - have a medium influence, while A has a low influence. In terms of the socioeconomic block of the business model, incentive H has a high influence. Five incentives - A, B, C, E, and F - have a low influence, while D and G have a medium influence. The influence over the technology block of the business model is mixed. Four incentives - B, C, E, and F - have a medium influence, and the influence is estimated as high for incentives D, G, and H. Incentive A is estimated to have a low influence. Therefore, incentives G and H can be prioritized as the main incentives, as they have a significantly positive and important influence.

Table 31 Mapping incentives for Business Models - Agricultural production

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
A	VNP-H30 (result-based grassland use)	DE_VPN_H30	Low (1.3)	Low (1.0)	Low (1.0)	I
B1	KULAP-B32/33/34 (watercourse and erosion control strips)	DE_KULA_P_B32	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
B2	KULAP-B19-23 (extensive grassland use for ruminants)	DE_KULA_P_B19	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
B3	VNP-H11 (extensive cropland management for field breeders and field wild herbs)	DE_VNP_H11	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
B4	VNP-H12-14 (fallow on arable land with self-vegetation for species protection reasons)	DE_VPN_H12	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	IV
B5	Federal programme for boosting energy efficiency and CO2 savings in agriculture and horticulture (Bundesprogramm zur Steigerung der Energieeffizienz und CO2-Einsparung in	DE_CO2_LAND	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
	Landwirtschaft und Gartenbau)					
B6	PAULa (cultivation break)	DE_PAULA_CULT_BREAK	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
C1	KULAP-B37 (mulch sowing for row crops)	DE_KULAP_B37	Low (1.3)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	IV
C2	KULAP-B38 (stripe-/Direkt sowing for row crops)	DE_KULAP_B38	Low (1.3)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	IV
C3	FAKT 1-D1 (no chemical-synthetic pesticides and fertilizer)	DE_FAKT1_D1	Low (1.3)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	IV
D1	KULAP-B43/44/45 (diverse crop rotation with flowering species, protein plants or large grain legumes)	DE_KULAP_B43	Medium (1.7)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	V
D2	Single Area Payment Scheme + green direct payment.	EE_SINGL_EA_PAYS_CHEM	Medium (1.7)	Medium (2.0)	High (2.5)	V
E1	BBodSchG, BBodSchV (Soil Protection Law and accompanying Soil Protection Directive)	DE_SOIL_PROT_LAW	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
E2	DüV DüngG - Fertilizer Directive (Düngemittelverordnung - DüV) and Fertilizer Law (Düngegesetz - DüngG)	DE_FER_LAW_PAST	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
E3	DüMV Fertilizer directive (Verordnung über das Inverkehrbringen von Düngemitteln, Bodenhilfsstoffen, Kultursubstraten und Pflanzenhilfsmitteln - DÜMV)	DE_FER_DIR_AGR	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
E4	Greening (preservation of permanent grassland)	DE_PRES_PERM_GRASS	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VII

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
E5	FUL-13 (10-year-set-aside)	DE_FUL13	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
F	VNP-H20 (conversion of arable land to grassland)	DE_VPN_H20	Low (1.3)	High (3.0)	Medium (2.0)	VII
G1	KULAP-B30 (extensive Grassland)	DE_KULAP_B30	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	Medium (2.0)	VIII
G2	KULAP-B35/36 (winter greening / intercropping)	DE_KULAP_B35	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VIII
G3	Environment friendly production eco plan (specify).	EE_ENV_FRE_ECOP_LAN	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VIII
G4	Greening (crop diversification)	DE_GRE_CROP_DIV	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VIII
G5	Support for land melioration. (Investment support for the development and maintenance of agricultural and forestry infrastructure)	EE_LAND_MELIORATION	Medium (1.7)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VIII
H	KULAP-B10 (organic farming)	DE_KULAP_B10	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	IX

Source: Own calculations

Business Models - Agricultural production/value chain

Agricultural production/value chain business models combine the characteristics of both agricultural production business models and value chain business models. They focus on individual farm-level instruments to increase soil health, while also targeting the potential upscaling of the concept for soil health recovery within the value chain. Figure 28 summarizes the incentives associated with agricultural production/value chain business models, while Table 32 provides detailed descriptions and ratings of these incentives.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 28 Mapping incentives for Business Models - Agricultural production/value chain

A total of 20 incentives have been identified in the agricultural production/value chain business model. Among them, Group C exhibits a high degree of influence on soil health strategies, while Group B and Group A have medium and low influence, respectively. Group C incentives have a high influence on the socioeconomic aspect of the business model, while Group A has low influence and Group B has medium influence. In terms of the technology aspect of the business model, the influence is mixed. Two incentives (B and C) have a significant influence, while the influence of incentive A is estimated to be low. As a result, it is not possible to prioritize incentives for this business model.

Table 32 Mapping incentives for Business Models - Agricultural production/value chain

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
A	VNP-H30 (result-based grassland use)	DE_VPN_H30	Low (1.3)	Low (1.0)	Low (1.0)	I
B1	KULAP-B32/33/34 (watercourse and erosion control strips)	DE_KULA_P_B32	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	IV
B2	KULAP-B37 (mulch sowing for row crops)	DE_KULA_P_B37	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
B3	KULAP-B38 (stripe-/Direkt sowing for row crops)	DE_KULA_P_B38	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
B4	KULAP-B43/44/45 (diverse crop rotation with flowering species, protein)	DE_KULA_P_B43	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.5)	IV

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
	plants or large grain legumes)					
B5	KULAP-B19-23 (extensive grassland use for ruminants)	DE_KULA_P_B19	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
B6	Federal programme for boosting energy efficiency and CO2 savings in agriculture and horticulture (Bundesprogramm zur Steigerung der Energieeffizienz und CO2-Einsparung in Landwirtschaft und Gartenbau)	DE_CO2_LAND	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Low (1.0)	IV
B7	VNP-H12-14 (fallows on arable land with self-vegetation for species protection reasons)	DE_VPN_H12	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	High (3.0)	IV
B8	PAULA (cultivation break)	DE_PAULA_CULT_BREAK	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	IV
B9	VNP-H11 (extensive cropland management for field breeders and field wild herbs)	DE_VNP_H11	Low (1.0)	Medium (2.0)	Medium (2.0)	IV
C1	KULAP-B30 (extensive Grassland)	DE_KULA_P_B30	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C2	KULAP-B35/36 (winter greening / Intercropping)	DE_KULA_P_B35	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VII
C3	VNP-H20 (conversion of arable land to grassland)	DE_VPN_H20	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VII
C4	Greening (crop diversification)	DE_GRE_CROP_DIV	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C5	KULAP-B10 (organic farming)	DE_KULA_P_B10	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VII
C6	BBodSchG, BBodSchV (Soil Protection Law and accompanying	DE_SOIL_PROT_LAW	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII

	Incentive	Code	Estimated influence of the incentive on business model socioeconomic block	Estimated influence of the incentive on the soil health strategies	Estimated influence of the incentive on the technology block	Quadrant
	Soil Protection Directive)					
C7	DüV DüngG - Fertilizer Directive (Düngemittelverordnung - DüV) and Fertilizer Law (Düngegesetz - DüngG)	DE_FER_L OW_PAST	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.5)	VII
C8	DüMV Fertilizer directive (Verordnung über das Inverkehrbringen von Düngemitteln, Bodenhilfsstoffen, Kultursubstraten und Pflanzenhilfsmitteln - DüMV)	DE_FER_DIR_AGR	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C9	Greening (preservation of permanent grassland)	DE_PRES_PERM_G RAS	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C10	FAKT 1-D1 (no chemical-synthetic pesticides and fertilizer)	DE_FAKT1_D1	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	Low (1.0)	VII
C11	FUL-13 (10-year-set-aside)	DE_FUL13	Low (1.0)	High (3.0)	High (3.0)	VII

Source: Own calculations

5.3 Ecosystem services

The analysis of ecosystem services focuses on thirteen main areas that the incentives enhance:

- Landscape and scenery
- Recreational access / Improvements to physical and mental health
- Cultural heritage
- Biodiversity
- Quality and security products
- Air Quality
- Farm animal health and welfare
- Soil quality
- Water quality
- Climate regulation - carbon storage
- Water quantity (e.g. water retention)

- Resilience to natural hazards
- Climate regulation.

Taking into consideration that the analysis of the incentives is focused on those that affect soil health, 165 out of 223 incentives influence soil health, 130 influence biodiversity, and 106 influence climate regulation in terms of carbon storage (figure 29). The analysed incentives have a lesser influence on recreational access, cultural heritage, and quality and security products. The average number of incentives includes water quantity, water quality, and landscape and scenery.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 29 Areas of the incentives' enhancement

5.3.1 Bulgaria

All Bulgarian incentives contribute to enhancing soil quality, with five of them specifically targeting landscape and scenery as ecosystem services (figure 30). However, only two of these incentives have a direct effect on ecosystem services.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 30 Areas of the Bulgarian incentives' enhancement

The way that the application of this incentive improves these ecosystem services is as follows:

BG_CSOILER_GRAREAS

It contributes to improving the fertility, structure, and quality of the soil, decreases soil erosion, contributes to better landscape and scenery, and preserves desertification.

BG_CSOILER_PERMPLANT

It reduces the use of fertilizers and pesticides. It improves the soil structure and soil health through anti-erosion activities and contributes to better landscape and scenery.

BG_CSOILER_DRAINAGE

It improves the soil structure and soil health through anti-erosion activities and contributes to better landscape and scenery.

BG_BUF_STRIPS

It contributes to improving soil fertility, the structure and quality of the soil, decreases soil erosion, contributes to better landscape and scenery and preserves desertification.

BG_CROP_ROTATION

It contributes to improving soil fertility, the structure and quality of the soil, decreases soil erosion, contributes to better landscape and scenery, and preserves desertification.

BG_SOILEROS_PLANTCOVER

It contributes to improving the structure and quality of the soil, decreases soil erosion, increasing soil organic matter and contributes to better water retention and better landscape scenery and biodiversity.

BG_SOILEROS_WEEDING

It contributes to improving the structure and quality of the soil, decreases soil erosion, increasing soil organic matter and contributes to better water retention and better landscape scenery and biodiversity.

BG_SOILPROT_PROHBURNING

It contributes to preserving the structure and quality of the soil, decreases soil erosion, preserves soil organic matter, and contributes to better biodiversity.

BG_CROP_DIV

It contributes to preserving the structure and quality of the soil, decreases soil erosion, preserving soil organic matter and contributes to better biodiversity.

BG_PERM_GRASS

It contributes to preserving the structure and quality of the soil, decreases soil erosion, preserving soil organic matter and contributes to better biodiversity.

5.3.2 Denmark

Ten incentives were analysed for Denmark. Nine of them enhance soil quality and biodiversity (figure 31). Additionally, one incentive also affects the other eight ecosystem services. Furthermore, an incentive was provided to enhance lower greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 31 Areas of the Danish incentives' enhancement

The application of these incentives improves the ecosystem services in the following ways:

DK_BIODIVERSITY_IN_FOREST

Extensive forest management implies no (or reduced) soil preparation which leads to better soil quality.

DK_ORG_FARMING

This incentive provides both regulatory and provisioning ecosystem services. The use of organic amendments (soil improvers) can positively contribute to the physical, chemical, and biological properties of the soil by stabilizing its structure. This is particularly relevant in intensively specified agricultural areas such as cereals, orchards, and vineyards, where conversion to organic farming can help maintain or enhance soil carbon stocks and increase nutrient availability.

DK_PEAT_AREAS_CLIMATE

ES provides lower GHG emission (taking low lying areas out of production).

DK_GRASA AND NATURE

Ensure quality of area.

DK_SET_A_SIDE

Setting aside land lowers intensification and benefits several ecosystem services, including biodiversity and water quality.

DK_CLIMATE_GRASA

By not ploughing up grass, nitrogen loss is delayed.

DK_EXTENSIVE_GRASS

The removal of grass reduces nutrient loss over time.

DK_CROP_DIVERSIFICATION

More crops on the same field (increase biodiversity).

DK_SOIL_CA

This incentive promotes more crops, improved biodiversity, and enhanced soil quality.

DK_COVER_P

The use of grass covers reduces soil erosion.

5.3.3 Estonia

The analysed seven incentives enhance all the ecosystem services but mostly water quantity, climate regulation, resilience to natural hazards, water and soil quality, biodiversity, and landscape and scenery (figure 32).

Source: Own calculations

Figure 32 Areas of the Estonian incentives' enhancement

The application of this incentive improves the following ecosystem services:

EE_REG_SOILP_SUPPORT

Air quality: Decrease in GHGs and wind erosion.

- Farm animal health and welfare: Grazing is more limited, while the grazed area increases and the grazing load per hectare decreases. This can also enhance the welfare of the animals.
- Water quality: Reduction in leaching and nutrient removal.
- Water quantity (e.g., water retention): Retention of water retention capacity.
- Climate regulation - carbon storage: Preservation and increase in soil Corg.
- Resilience to natural hazards: Preservation of the soil's water-holding capacity and drought resistance.

EE_ENV_FRE_ECOPLAN

The purpose is to encourage the introduction and continued use of environmentally friendly management methods in agriculture, increase biodiversity and landscape diversity, and raise the environmental awareness of agricultural producers.

EE_CONT_ORG_FARM

Mostly due to changes in crop rotation, where a larger share of legumes and grassland species is utilized, as well as the avoidance of chemical pesticides, there are benefits in preserving the living organisms both in the soil and above it. Another goal is achieved through the use of organic amendments in the soil. Stocking rates are also restricted, which allows for extensive grazing that positively influences soil structure and contributes to the sequestration of organic carbon in the soil. Organic farming has a positive impact on the quality and safety of products, thus promoting the health of humans and animals. By avoiding the use of mineral fertilizers, there is a significant opportunity to minimize nutrient leaching and reduce the risk of nutrient runoff into water bodies, resulting in improved water quality.

EE_SINGLEA_PAYSCHEME

The purpose of this unified area subsidy is to ensure the preservation of valuable agricultural land and the main means of food production. It includes meeting greening support requirements, such as crop diversification, ecozone practices, and permanent grassland maintenance. These requirements contribute to soil and water quality maintenance, preservation of permanent grasslands, and enhancement of biodiversity.

EE_NATURA_FOREST

The purpose is to protect nature by preserving its diversity, ensuring favourable conditions for natural habitats, species of fauna, flora, and fungi, and preserving culturally-historically and aesthetically valuable natural environments or their elements.

EE_SEMINAT_BIOTIC_COMM

The purpose of semi-natural community support is to increase the surface area of maintained areas, improve the condition of semi-natural communities and their related species, and enhance biodiversity and landscape diversity.

EE_WATER_ACT

The main purpose of the Water Act is to safeguard open water bodies and groundwater. Adequate amounts of clean water are essential for promoting biodiversity and maintaining the health and welfare of farm animals. Furthermore, vital wetlands and forests play a crucial role in climate regulation and carbon storage. Effective water and water body management significantly contributes to resilience against natural hazards. All these factors have a direct impact on soil quality and the overall landscape.

EE_LAND_MELIORATION

Regulation of water quantity - it has impact also on water quality. Impact on soil quality and scenery.

5.3.4 France

Twenty-two French voluntary incentives were analysed (figure 33). Their enhancement is focused on biodiversity, soil quality, and water quantity.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 33 Areas of the French incentives' enhancement

The way in which the application of this incentive improves ecosystem services is as follows:

FR_RDNF001_C3

To address the issue of bare soils in the inter-rows under orchards or vines, the incentive promotes the installation of a perennial herbaceous cover. This helps reduce the risks of soil erosion, washout, and runoff. It contributes to protecting water quality by minimizing the impact of phytosanitary products and preserving soil health through erosion control. Additionally, the grassed strips in the inter-rows facilitate carbon storage in the soil and limit N₂O emissions. This practice is applicable in areas where grassing is not already a common practice.

FR_RDNF001_C4

To address bare soils in the inter-rows under vines, the incentive encourages the installation of a plant mulch made of bark. This helps reduce the risks of soil erosion and leaching or runoff. The spread bark forms a protective mulch that attenuates the impact of raindrops, reduces water speed, and enhances infiltration capacity. The mulch also improves soil structure by promoting microbial activity and increasing earthworm populations. Moreover, bark contains essential mineral elements, such as potassium and magnesium, contributing to soil fertility. Using a mixture of hardwood and softwood bark provides effective soil protection, while hardwood bark helps prevent soil

acidification. By eliminating the need for herbicides, this commitment aligns with the objective of protecting water quality from phytosanitary product pollution.

FR_RDNF001_C6

This incentive encourages farmers to establish and maintain perennial grass cover in areas facing significant environmental challenges. It goes beyond the mandatory cover required under cross-compliance, greening, and action programs related to the Nitrates Directive. The practice addresses water protection, landscape preservation, and biodiversity maintenance. Establishing grass cover, including grass strips, helps control erosion and limit input leaching (for erosion control and water quality objectives). It also provides refuge areas for fauna and flora (for biodiversity objectives) and enhances and protects certain landscapes (for landscape objectives). The selection of relevant locations for grass cover depends on spatial or agro-ecological diagnoses and targeted issues in the territory, such as catchment areas, watercourses, ditches, slope breaks, and ecological corridors, among others.

FR_RDNF001_C11

The objectives of this practice are to maintain natural soil cover in the vineyard inter-rows by eliminating weed control, primarily to reduce leaching, runoff, and soil erosion risks. This commitment is applicable in areas where inter-row cover is not a common practice. Additionally, grassed strips in the inter-rows contribute to carbon storage in the soil and help limit N₂O emissions.

FR_RDNF001_C16

Crushing and burying rice straws is a common practice in France with numerous agronomic and environmental advantages. However, it may not be feasible for all types of plots. Burying rice straws helps improve soil structure, increase organic matter content, and replenish elements like silica that are depleted by the plants. This practice is only feasible on upland, non-wet soils and requires the use of a shredder-spreader on the combine. This operation contributes to biodiversity conservation in rice-growing systems.

FR_RDNF001_H4

The objective of this operation is to enhance the management of remarkable environments, particularly in wetlands such as peat bogs and wet meadows. It involves limiting grazing pressure to prevent flora and soil degradation caused by compaction. The practice aims to maintain biodiversity and preserve landscapes. It also helps maintain and renew fodder resources in areas experiencing overgrowth dynamics, by avoiding undergrazing and overgrazing. By doing so, it contributes to the preservation of a mosaic of habitats.

FR_RDNF001_H11

This operation aims to maintain the biodiversity of meadows and remarkable wetlands such as the eutrophic meadows with Fritillary (*Bromion racemosi*) or the meadows sheltering the Corncrake. To avoid overgrazing and to preserve species sensitive to early grazing, this operation defines a period of prohibition of grazing and mowing in winter, since winter grazing is detrimental to wetland meadows, especially for the most organic soils, peaty, which are waterlogged at this time of year. Grazing can lead to soil destructuration and surface compaction, resulting in the development of vegetation of compacted soils that are not very nitrophilic (degrading rushes, Sardinian buttercup, etc.), and the grassland can emerge from the winter period very degraded (formation of holes and bumps that can compromise the future use of the plot).

FR_RDNF001_IR9

The ecosystems present in the Rhone basin, thanks to the practice of irrigating crops by submersion, offer a remarkably rich biodiversity of flora and fauna linked to the soils and the different degrees of salinity of the waters. The inflow of fresh water from the Rhone for agricultural purposes also plays an important role in the natural environment and in the preservation of species of great heritage interest. The interrelation between agricultural and natural environments is such that 66% of the rice fields are included within the perimeters of Natura 2000 sites. This operation targets any irrigated crop that maintains a water level over a long period of time, allowing the installation of specific floral and faunal biodiversity. However, in the Camargue, only rice cultivation, carried out according to good cultural practices, corresponds to these criteria. This operation aims to maintain surfaces irrigated by submersion in sufficient proportion to promote the particular biodiversity linked to the rice ecosystem and to avoid the risk of salinization of the land, which would be accompanied by extremely rapid erosion of the biodiversity in the Camargue.

FR_RDNF001_LL1

To ensure the maintenance of hedges, located in a favourable manner regarding the environmental issue at stake, compatible with the presence of a wealth of fauna. This maintenance must be considered relevant to the type of hedge present to ensure the renewal and sustainability of the hedges. Hedges have multiple environmental functions. Indeed, they constitute a physical obstacle that reduces the speed of runoff as well as that of the wind, thus limiting the transport of solid particles (silt and sand), fertilizing elements, and active materials (objectives against erosion and water quality). The dense, powerful, and deep root network of the ligneous plants composing the hedge brings up the mineral elements that have migrated in depth (water protection objective), favours the infiltration of excess water and stabilizes the soil (natural risk and erosion control objectives). FR_RDNF001_LL5

Preserve existing slopes and their continuity: Slopes constitute a physical obstacle to runoff and thus meet the objective of protecting water quality, fighting soil erosion, and limiting flooding. Their effectiveness is only real if

they are appropriately located and if there is continuity of these structures in the areas at risk. In addition, these uncultivated parts of the plot constitute areas of shelter and development for auxiliary flora and fauna when they are mechanically maintained at appropriate times. This operation, therefore, also contributes to the maintenance of biodiversity. Similarly, the maintenance of certain slopes can ensure continuity with other fire prevention measures, in time and space, to stop or slow the spread of fire. This operation can, therefore, also contribute to the defense of forests against fire risks (DFCI).

FR_RDNF001_LL9

The objective is to ensure the maintenance of the hedges located in the bocage territories which are aging and in the process of dying out. There is currently a great risk of the disappearance of these hedges, which are the very essence of the bocage, by lack of maintenance or on the contrary over-maintenance. These hedges are characterized by a multi-generational alternation between, on the one hand, tall trees that are partially or totally pruned, or that are trained as hedges, and, on the other hand, shrubs, the sequence of which is adapted to local soil and climate conditions. This type of hedge management allows for the development of the different strata of the hedge and improves the micro-climatic conditions of the parcel it borders, thus protecting the soil, the herds, and the crops from climatic excesses (climate objective).

FR_RDNF001_PH8

In market gardening in the open field or in tunnels (excluding greenhouses), mulching is unfavourable to the development of various bio-aggressors: weeds, flies, thrips, mildew. It thus makes it possible to limit the number of approved doses applied for these uses or to prohibit certain uses (water quality protection issue). It thus contributes to the preservation of water quality by reducing the impact of phytosanitary products. In addition, it meets the objective of water protection in quantitative terms, insofar as it preserves the useful reserve of the soil and can thus contribute to limiting the use of irrigation. It also protects the soil against erosion, as it is covered by mulch and not left bare after weeding. However, in order to meet the challenge of preserving water quality without undermining other challenges, in particular soil or landscape protection, mulching must be solely plant-based or biodegradable; plastic mulching is prohibited."

FR_RDNF001_SGC1

The objective is to support the sustainable change of practices on the whole farm system and to improve their overall environmental performance in the long term. This operation should take into account all environmental issues (water, soil, ordinary biodiversity, landscape, climate). It targets large-scale crop farms, mainly cereal and/or oilseed farms.

The target practices are characterized by:

- diversified crop rotation and long rotations, with the presence of legumes and alternating winter and spring crops;
- thrifty management of nitrogenous fertilization, particularly with regard to the splitting of inputs and control of the risks of nitrate leakage during intercropping periods;
- less use of phytosanitary products due to less sensitivity to bio-aggressors (lengthening of rotations and diversity of crops grown, adaptation of sowing dates and densities, AEI conducive to the development of crop auxiliaries).

This is a support operation for changing practices with two levels of ambition. The projects mobilizing this operation must target as a priority territory with water issues but must also take into account other territorial issues, whether it be the preservation of ordinary biodiversity (deficit of AEI, absence of crop diversity, disappearance of mesophilic plants, auxiliaries and pollinators) or soil quality (areas of silt poor in organic matter).

FR_RDNF001_SGC2

The objective is to support the sustainable change of practices on the whole farm system and to improve their overall environmental performance in the long term. This operation should consider all environmental issues (water, soil, ordinary biodiversity, landscape, climate). It is aimed at arable farms in areas with lower agronomic potential where simplified crop rotation is a proven risk. The target practices are the same as the ones mentioned for FR_RDNF001_SGC1.

This is an operation to support changes in practices. Projects mobilising this operation in so-called "intermediate" areas must consider the territorial issues, whether it be the preservation of ordinary biodiversity (lack of AEI, absence of crop diversity, disappearance of mesophilic plants, auxiliaries and pollinators), water quality or soil quality (areas of silt poor in organic matter).

FR_RDNF001_SGC3

The objective operation is to support the sustainable change of practices on the whole farm system and to improve their overall environmental performance in the long term. This operation considers all environmental issues (water, soil, ordinary biodiversity, landscape, climate) and responds to them. It targets farms specializing in arable farming and integrating high value-added production. The target practices are the same as the ones mentioned for FR_RDNF001_SGC1.

This operation aims to support changes in practices. The projects mobilizing this operation must prioritize territories with water issues but should also take into account other territorial issues, such as the preservation of ordinary biodiversity (lack of Agro-Environmental Initiatives (AEI), insufficient crop diversity, disappearance of mesophilic plants, auxiliaries, and pollinators) or soil quality (areas of silt poor in organic matter).

FR_RDNF001_SOL1

The objective is to support the sustainable change of practices in field crop production and improve their overall environmental performance in the long term. This operation addresses the challenges related to the sustainable management of agricultural soils, including erosion, organic matter, biological activity, and compaction. Thus, this measure encourages farmers to minimize tillage, establish year-round cover crops, and diversify crop rotations on arable land. Mechanical tillage is replaced by tillage performed by soil organisms (biological tillage) and by the plant root system. With this objective in mind, this measure for agro environmental and climate (MAEC) promotes the practice of direct seeding under living plant cover (which can provide nitrogen to the main crop, limit erosion, and compete with weeds without competing with the main crop) or under dead cover (crop residues or intercultural cover). This approach is a form of no-till farming, where direct seeding is done with a no-till drill without prior tillage. In this case, "soil disturbance" consists only of opening a thin furrow in the soil within a living or dead plant cover (mulch). Rolling can ensure proper "soil-seed" contact for successful crop emergence. However, minimal tillage is permitted in the following cases:

- Working the seed line with a "strip till" type tool, limited to one pass per year on the parcels involved.
- Mechanical destruction of cover crops or weeds through scalping with a tine tool, for farmers practicing organic farming on their field crop production unit or when the operation is combined with a reduction in herbicide IFT.

FR_RDNF001_SPE3

Multi-crop farms can also be farms with a monogastric workshop (pigs or poultry). These farms have a crop rotation composed of field crops. Only 1/4 of them produce part of their animal feed themselves.

The objective of this operation is to support the sustainable change of practices on the whole farm. The target practices are characterised by:

- diversified crop rotation and extended rotations, with the presence of legumes and alternating winter and spring crops
- thrifty management of nitrogenous fertilisation with the use of animal waste, which promotes the reproduction of soil fertility
- the supply of food to the animals by mobilising different plant productions;
- long crop rotations allowing for less pressure from diseases or pests and better weed control.

Such farming systems make it possible, above all, to improve water management through the limited use of inputs (DP 4B), and to participate in adapting to climate change through the reduction of emissions (DP 5A) and carbon conservation (DP 5B). To a lesser extent, they also help to improve soil management (DP 4C). The actual linkage of this operation to the priority areas is made by the Managing Authority when developing its regional intervention strategy."

FR_RDNF001_M11_1

This operation is one of the main drivers for supporting the development of areas at a time when the additional costs and income loss resulting from changes in practices are not compensated for by the market, as the higher value of products compared to those produced by conventional agriculture is delayed. It should be accessible to all farmers in France, following the same principles. Organic farming, characterized by the non-use of synthetic chemical inputs and GMOs, and practices aimed at the sustainable management of natural resources, soil and environmental preservation, respect for ecological balances, and animal welfare, has a proven overall positive impact on water, soil, biodiversity, and climate change.

FR_RDNF001_M11_2

This operation is essential to support farms that have converted to organic farming and to prevent the risks of reverting to conventional farming. Organic farming, characterized by the non-use of synthetic chemical inputs and GMOs, and practices aimed at the sustainable management of natural resources, soil and environmental preservation, respect for ecological balances, and animal welfare, has a proven overall positive impact on water, soil, biodiversity, and climate change. By developing organic farming areas and thus overall supply, this operation also contributes to sector structuring and strengthening the economic performance of the targeted farms.

FR_RDNF001_M10_42

The objective is to ensure the maintenance of groves in relation to the environmental issue at hand, while being compatible with the presence of diverse flora and fauna. This maintenance must be thoughtful and relevant to ensure the sustainability of these environments. Groves serve as shelters, habitats, and reproductive areas for numerous animal and plant species. They also play a role in landscape structuring by providing ecological corridors. Similar to shrub or tree hedges, groves protect against runoff and erosion, promote water quality (by limiting transfers), maintain biodiversity (through complex ecosystems of animal and plant species), and regulate climate. Non-intensive and targeted maintenance of these environments ensures their sustainability and enables them to fulfill these roles.

FR_RDNF001_SHP1

This operation aims to preserve the sustainability and agro-ecological balance of permanent grasslands with diversified flora, as well as certain targeted pastoral surfaces (TS). The environmental value of this type of surface has been indisputably demonstrated in the literature, including the study "Extensive management of forage surfaces: threats and risks of disappearing environmentally beneficial practices," commissioned by the Ministry of Agriculture in 2013. This operation commits to:

- ensuring the structural and functional integration of these areas into grazing systems for their sustainability and ecological status,

- acknowledging that the agricultural production systems concerned are based, at least in part, on ecological foundations, such as grazing or mowing of fodder from semi-natural environments.

Its maintenance within the permanent meadows and pastures of the farm is favoured because it contributes to water quality preservation through low-input management, biodiversity preservation as a favourable environment, preservation of topographic elements, mitigation of climate change by carbon storage in the soil, prevention of soil erosion, and protection of Mediterranean forests against fire (firebreaks).

FR_RDNF001_SHP2

The management of natural areas with high environmental value, such as mountain pastures, summer pastures, intermediate zones, marshes, and Mediterranean forest massifs heavily relies on the activity of collective pastoral entities. These collective spaces have significant environmental assets as they contribute to:

- preserving water quality through low-input management,
- preserving biodiversity both as a favourable environment and by maintaining topographical elements,
- mitigating climate change through carbon storage in the soil,
- limiting natural risks such as erosion, landslides, avalanches, and fire risks through continuous vegetation cover and open environments.

This operation aims to maintain existing practices and is therefore only appropriate if the environmental benefit of the practice is proven, and must be associated with a targeting of areas where there is a risk of the practice disappearing.

5.3.5 Germany

The analysed German 30 incentives' enhancement is focused on biodiversity, soil, and water quality (figure 34). It is worth mentioning that majority of the incentives are used primarily in Switzerland and Austria.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 34 Areas of the German incentives' enhancement

The way that the application of this incentive improves these ecosystem services is as follows:

DE_A_CKERWERT

Sustainable use systems are promoted in the project. This can mean, for example, that land is farmed organically. Another example is that arable land is converted to grassland to be used as pasture for species-friendly animal husbandry. Furthermore, the targeted creation of flowering areas can improve biodiversity.

DE_AGORA_NATURA

AgoraNatura provides an online marketplace for certified nature conservation projects. Land managers wanting to implement conservation projects can finance it through crowdfunding or partnerships with companies via the platform. Therefore, private investors and companies can promote biodiversity and ecosystem services by investing in nature conservation certificates. Projects' ecological impacts are certified according to the NaturPlus Standard.

DE_KULAP_B10

Organic farming often leads to a more diverse crop rotation. This beautifies the landscape and biodiversity can be improved. The absence of fertilizers often leads to increased cultivation of legumes. This can partly build up humus. As a result, C can be sequestered. The conditions for animal husbandry are better, compared to conventional husbandry.

DE_KULAP_B19

The measure subsidizes grazing. Grazing improves animal welfare and provides an attractive landscape. Grazing is limited to a certain number of

livestock units per hectare. This can reduce trampling damage and excreta. This can have a positive impact on soil quality and the resulting emissions.

DE_KULAP_B30

Extensive grassland use with the abandonment of any kind of fertilizer and herbicides primarily improves water quality. Nitrate leaching can be reduced. The pH value of the soil increases, and the absence of herbicides could increase biodiversity.

DE_KULAP_B32

By reducing erosion, less topsoil/humus is removed. This can increase soil quality. The higher humus content also has a positive effect on carbon storage. The soil is more resistant to weather extremes. Since erosion control is made by seeding a green strip, this also has a positive effect on biodiversity.

DE_KULAP_B35

Winter revegetation using catch crops or wild seeds builds a food supply for birds and insects in winter. At the same time, nitrate leaching is prevented, and groundwater quality is increased. Winter cover prevents erosion, which improves soil quality and water holding capacity. This generally makes the soil structure more stable.

DE_KULAP_B37

Mulch seeding in row crops means leaving plant residues from previous crops on the surface. Turning soil tillage is not used. Biodiversity is promoted through organic material. The soil is protected from erosion. The absence of turning tillage results in a more compact topsoil. This can have a positive effect on soil life but can also have a compacting effect. The structure of the soil is influenced.

DE_KULAP_B38

Direct seeding in row crops means leaving plant residues from previous crops on the surface. Turning tillage is not used. Biodiversity is promoted through organic material. The soil is protected from erosion. The absence of turning tillage results in a more compact topsoil. This can have a positive effect on soil life but can also have a compacting effect. The structure of the soil is influenced.

DE_KULAP_B43

The cultivation of flowering crops / legumes etc. offers an attractive food supply, which can increase biodiversity. At the same time, the crop rotation is loosened up and fewer humus-consuming crops are cultivated. This can increase the humus content of the soil, which has a positive effect on the soil structure. In the process, nitrogen is fixed in legumes, which further increases quality.

DE_SOIL_PROT_LAW

The law sets general guidelines for soil protection, e.g., prevent the deposition of potentially harmful substances, prevent soil erosion, preserving soil structure.

DE_BIO_BODEN

Organic farming often leads to a more diverse crop rotation. This beautifies the landscape and biodiversity can be improved. The absence of fertilizers often leads to increased cultivation of legumes. This can partly build up humus. As a result, C can be sequestered.

DE_BODENFRUCHTBARKEITSFONDS

The primary goal is to improve soil health. This includes the build-up of humus and an improvement in soil quality. This can also improve the water balance in the further course. Soils become more resilient, which can have a positive effect on their resilience. The build-up of humus also sequesters CO₂, which has a positive effect on the climate.

DE_CLIM_FRI_LAND_USE

The object of this funding is the revitalization of peatlands and the adaptation of dam management to achieve higher water levels. This involves various methods of introducing production, usage, and management methods that conserve and preserve peatlands. This protects peatland-typical species, restores peatlands, and renatures forest peatlands.

DE_CO2_LAND

The goal of the initiative is to build up humus and sequester CO₂ through certain measures. This improves soil quality and soil structure. This can lead to an improved water balance. At the same time, CO₂ sequestration removes climate-damaging CO₂ from the earth's atmosphere.

DE_FER_DIR_AGR

The directive governs the type and nature of materials and substances used as fertilizers and additives that are allowed to be marketed. It dictates that only substances that are of a certain nature and are conducive to soil health/fertility do not pose a threat to human or animal health.

DE_FER_LOW_PAST

The law prevents the use of too much fertilizer. This can lead to an improvement of the soil structure if, for example, the use of acidic fertilizers is reduced. Water quality can also increase due to reduced nitrate leaching. A ban on the application of organic fertilizers in the winter months also prevents leaching. The plan also stipulates that farm manure must be applied close to the ground. This reduces ammonia and nitrous oxide emissions. Liquid manure must be incorporated into uncultivated fields. This reduces emissions that are harmful to the climate.

DE_FAKTI_D1

If no synthetic chemical pesticides and fertilizers are used, water quality can be improved. The soil can benefit from less acidification and emissions from application can be avoided. By not using herbicides, the proportion of field weeds increases, which can improve biodiversity.

DE_FUL13

Long-term set-aside can relieve ecosystems by reducing the discharge of fertilizers and pesticides. Likewise, new (more extensive) biotopes can form on the set-aside areas (fallow fields) that last several years. In addition, the set-aside areas form refuge areas for various wild animals.

DE_GRE_CROP_DIV

Growing multiple crops within the rotation can reduce sole cultivation of intensive species. This can improve soil health and enhance the landscape. It can also create higher attractiveness for animal life.

DE_PRES_PERM_GRAS

Permanent grassland is important for soil and water conservation and makes an important contribution to climate protection. The humus content of the soil stores carbon (which is thus removed from the atmosphere) and serves as a carbon sink. Grassland fulfils multiple functions in the agricultural landscape beyond agricultural production. It provides opportunities for recreation and leisure and has high aesthetic natural value. More than half of all animal and plant species observed in Germany occur on grassland sites. They are thus of great importance for species conservation and the preservation of species diversity (biodiversity).

DE_VNP_H11

Cultivation of crops that are less humus consuming can reduce humus depletion. This increases the quality of the soil. The diverse crop rotation leads to a more attractive landscape, both visually and as a habitat and food source. This can also increase biodiversity. Extensive farming reduces the amount of chemically produced pesticides in the soil, which can improve water quality.

DE_VPN_H12

Fallow land followed by self-vegetation allows for natural wildflower vegetation typical of the site. Biodiversity can be increased due to the quietness of the soil and the natural vegetation. This can also enhance the landscape. By avoiding the use of fertilizers and pesticides, leaching of substances into the groundwater can be avoided. This also increases water quality, especially groundwater.

DE_VPN_H20

Conversion of arable land to grassland results in areas being covered even in winter. This can increase biodiversity and reduce erosion.

DE_VPN_H30

Result-oriented grassland means that through extensive use (few cuts, no fertilizer and plant protection), flowering species appear in permanent grassland. This increases biodiversity. By using fewer input factors, soil and water quality can be improved.

DE_MOOR_FUT

This incentive provides carbon certificates for the financing of climate protection projects in bogs and peatlands, which are the largest and most effective carbon deposits on Earth. The projects help manage bogs and peatlands to store carbon effectively and protect the natural flora and fauna.

DE_PAULA_CULT_BREAK

Cultivation breaks of intensive crops reduce disease pressure. This can reduce the use of pesticides, which can improve water quality. A lower proportion of intensive crops can also prevent the depletion of humus. A more diverse crop rotation also increases biodiversity and enhances the landscape.

DE_AUKM

The objective of the funding is the implementation of targeted climate protection or biodiversity measures by agricultural cooperatives. This contributes to climate change mitigation and adaptation, by reducing greenhouse emissions and improving carbon sequestration.

DE_REG_AG_CIT

In addition to many other businesses such as restaurants or nurseries, agricultural businesses are also supported. The focus here is primarily on organic farming. Organic farming often leads to a more diverse crop rotation. This beautifies the landscape and biodiversity can be improved. The absence of fertilizers often leads to increased cultivation of legumes. This can partly build up humus. As a result, C can be sequestered.

DE_TIRE_PRESS_CSYS

A tire pressure control system reduces the weight per area that acts on the ground. This can reduce compaction, which can improve the soil structure. A loose soil structure also improves water holding capacity.

5.3.6 Italy

Sixteen Italian incentives were analysed (figure 35). All of them enhance water quantity and soil quality. A significant number influence biodiversity, water quality, and climate regulation.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 35 Areas of the Italian incentives' enhancement

The way the application of this incentive improves these ecosystem services is as follows:

IT_QUALSCHEME_AGRIPROD

Regulating ES: By implementing sustainable soil management practices, it is possible to prevent erosion and hydrogeological risks, while conserving soil biodiversity. Provisioning ES: Through the limited use of chemical inputs such as fertilizers and plant protection products, and the adoption of agronomical management and natural remedies for plant protection, soil and water pollution can be reduced. This, in turn, contributes to the production of healthier food. Cultural ES: Preserving soil health also helps to safeguard the historical and cultural heritage of the region. Healthy and fertile soils enable the long-term conservation of local historical, cultural, and enogastronomic values.

IT_SQNPI_LABLE

SNQPI label affects different ES. Regulating ES: by sustainably managing soil, erosion and hydrogeological risk can be prevented and soil biodiversity can be conserved. Provisioning ES: limited use of chemical inputs (fertilizers and plant protection products) when possible, by applying agronomical management and natural plant protection remedies; a lower use of chemical products implies less soil and water pollution, thus production of healthier food.

IT_GLOBAL_GAP_IFA

The GLOBALGAP IFA standard adopts a holistic approach of responsible farming practices and is touching regulating ES and provisioning ES: food security; environmental sustainability and biodiversity; health, safety and workers wellbeing (GRASP); animal welfare; legal transparency and traceability; production processes; Integrated crop management and pest

control (ICM, IPC); quality management system (SQ) and risk assessment (HACCP). For producers, the International Featured Standard (IFS) helps improve farm management, increase operational efficiency, protect environmental resources, and provide access to international markets by complying with a globally recognized standard. For all actors in the food supply chain, the IFS label ensures food safety, protects product integrity, mitigates reputation risks, and demonstrates a commitment to responsible agricultural practices, thereby providing consumers with trustworthy products. In the case study of the Sand district, GLOBALGAP is one of the main certifications adopted by farmers.

IT_ORG_FARM_LABEL

The goal of organic farming is to conserve and improve agricultural soils, making it a positive contributor to several ecosystem services (ES), particularly on a long-term scale. It regulates ES by enhancing soil organic matter (SOM) and thereby improving physical soil stability, reducing erosion and desertification risks. It also enhances biological diversity, promoting healthier plants with improved nutrient availability and resistance to biotic and abiotic stress. Provisioning ES include increased water capacity of the soil and human health benefits such as healthier plants with reduced pesticide use and higher food quality, including in public canteens. Cultural ES are also provided, as organic farming helps preserve local agricultural knowledge and encourages the creation of producer-consumer networks.

IT_ORG_FARM_DISTRICTS

Biodistricts aim to conserve and improve agricultural soils through the application of organic farming practices. They create synergies among territorial actors, including those across provinces and regions. Biodistricts provide similar ES as the organic farming label, but with additional benefits. Provisioning ES include larger areas of organic farming, which reduce the risk of conventional pesticide contamination and contribute to healthier soil and water, resulting in healthier food and inhabitants. Collaboration with local administrations and other actors can also provide cultural ES, such as innovation and rural development, valorization of historical heritage, and territorial synergies with agricultural, tourist, and social operators (source: <https://www.lexalimentaria.eu/legge-italiana-sul-biologico-parte-i/>).

IT_AGRI_ENV_CLIM_PAYMENT

In terms of the Agri-Environment Climate Payments, they contribute to regulating ES by increasing SOM through integrated production techniques. These payments help improve soil fertility and stability by reducing the risk of erosion and preventing hydrogeological risks. Increasing SOM also enhances and preserves soil biodiversity. Provisioning ES include improved plant vegetation, which becomes more resilient to climate change and requires fewer chemical products, resulting in healthier food and reduced water and soil pollution.

IT-ORG_FARMING

Organic amendments (soil improvers) play a crucial role in providing regulatory and provisioning ES. They positively contribute to the physical, chemical, and biological properties of soils by stabilizing their structure. This is particularly relevant in intensively cultivated agricultural areas such as cereal crops, orchards, and vineyards, where conversion to organic farming can help maintain or enhance soil carbon stocks and improve nutrient availability in the soil.

IT_NAT2_WATER_PAY

Regulatory ES: sustainable soil management thus reduction of soil erosion, biodiversity and habitat conservation. Cultural ES: a healthy and fertile soil allows to preserve the historical, cultural and enogastronomic heritage of a territory. Many farms of the sandy soil district are part of the Natura 2000 site of the Po Delta Park, that since 2015 is recognized as UNESCO MAB (Man and the Biosphere).

IT_GREENING

Those practices take the form of simple, generalized, non-contractual and annual actions that go beyond cross-compliance and that are linked to agriculture, such as crop diversification, the maintenance of permanent grassland, including traditional orchards where fruit trees are grown in low density on grassland, and the establishment of ecological focus areas. Those practices can provide ecosystem services, such as storing and cycling nutrients, regulating climate, water retention, increasing resilience to natural hazards, sequestering carbon, and conserving soils.

IT_REFORESTATION

The incentive is financed by part of the revenues from the auctioning of CO₂ emission quotas. There is increasing evidence of urban green infrastructure (UGI) to reduce the effects of climate change and enhance resilience and sustainability. UGI can provide ecosystem services, such as cleaning the air, filtering, and cooling water, storing and cycling nutrients, regulating climate, sequestering carbon, maintaining hydrologic regimes, conserving and generating soils.

IT_ORGANIC_PROVISIONS

Organic farming can contribute by improving soil fertility through the application of organic matter inputs in the form of green manures, compost and farmyard manure; adopting cover crops and crop rotations and intercropping and by implementing low soil disturbance tillage; integrating crops and animals, reducing overgrazing and facilitating nutrient recycling on the farm; improving water infiltration and retention capacity through high levels of organic matter and permanent soil cover, such as cover crops or mulch.

IT_NAT_FOREST_STR

The expansion of forests has the effect of reducing the effects of climate change and enhance resilience and sustainability. Forests can provide ecosystem services, such as cleaning the air, filtering, and cooling water, storing and cycling nutrients, regulating climate, sequestering carbon, maintaining hydrologic regimes, conserving and generating soils.

IT_NATURAL_DISASTERS

Restoration of agricultural production potential damaged by natural disasters and catastrophic and introducing appropriate prevention measures, acting on erosion (and consequently, loss of soil fertility) and against landscape degradation.

IT_FOREST_AREA_INV

Investments in the development of forest areas, and in improving the profitability of forests, to enhance the potential of the forest as an environmental, economic, and social resource. These investments serve the growth of rural areas and the inter-region. The protection of forests from the causes of decay positively affects the increase of CO₂ absorption capacity and in general the containment of climate-altering gas emissions."

IT_INTEGR_SUPPLY_CHAIN

Integrated Supply Chain Projects (Progetti Integrati di Filiera (PIF)), Italian rural policy tools funded in the framework of EU's Rural Development Policy, can integrate supply chain innovation and territorial integrated strategies, fostering a multifunctional development of marginal rural areas towards a newly discovered identity. PIFs are based on "multi-measure" tender notices, which have to be jointly applied for by specific partnerships. Regional administrations may decide to activate different measures, according to their regional strategies. Depending on the measures activated, the effects on ecosystem services will be different (an example is one the Italian case study).

IT_INTEGR_TERRITORIAL_PROJECTS

Integrated Territorial Project are projects implemented by the subjects participating to a Territorial Agreement, according to the modalities provided for in the call, with the aim of finding a solution to specific environmental problems of a local character, to the implementation of strategies aimed at mitigation or adaptation to climate change in the context of the following themes: soil and hydrogeological instability, management and protection of water resources, biodiversity, landscape, energy. Depending on the project, the effects on ecosystem services will be different.

5.3.7 Latvia

All 10 Latvian incentives enhance soil quality (figure 36). The strong influence is evaluated on water quality, climate regulation in terms of carbon storage, air quality and resilience to natural hazards.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 36 Areas of the Latvian incentives' enhancement

The way the application of this incentive improves these ecosystem services is as follows:

LV_ESH_DPAY_ROT

These Eco schemes contribute positively to microbiological activity in soil, diversity of microorganisms, and help to fight against soil erosion.

LV_ESH_DPAY_NOPPP

This eco scheme positively contributes to reduction of plant protection product usage, increases organic matter in soil, ensures soil cover in most sensitive periods, and reduces the need for fertilizer inputs.

LV_ESH_DPAY_TILLAGE

This measure reduces GHG emissions from soil, increases organic matter content in top layer of soil, and enhances the soil structure and particle drainage capabilities.

LV_ESH_DPAY_BUFFER

This measure ensures soil cover along watercourses, which ensures that no surface nutrient or ppp leakage is present.

LV_ESH_DPAY_PREC

This measure provides reduction in fertilizer and ppp inputs, reduces ghg emissions.

LV_PERM_GRASS_ANALYSIS

This measure provides reduction in fertilizer and ppp inputs, reduces ghg emissions.

LV_PERM_GRASS_MAINTAN

Reduction of soil erosion, preservation of organic matter, improvement of soil structure and quality.

LV_PERM_GRASS_PEST_MANG

Preservation of organic matter, improvement of soil quality, CO2 sequestration, enhances biodiversity.

LV_PERM_GRASS_LIMING

Reduction of nutrient leakage, CO2 sequestration, enhances biodiversity.

LV_AGRF_FORESTRY

Turning degraded areas to forestry promotes CO2 sequestration, enhances biodiversity.

5.3.8 Netherlands

Out of 76 Dutch incentives, 60 enhance carbon storage, 57 soil quality and 36 biodiversity (figure 37). Eight incentives affect other ecosystem services.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 37 Areas of the Dutch incentives' enhancement

The way that the application of this incentive improves these ecosystem services is as follows:

NL_TRIM_AGRIScheme

Cutting or shearing hedges contains different packages:

- Package a: 100% of the habitat under management is pruned annually;
- Package b: At least 20% to a maximum of 50% of the habitat under management is pruned annually;
- Packages a and b: Pruning debris has been removed or placed on rills in the element/or clippings have been removed;
- Packages a and b: Livestock damage is safeguarded from January 1 to December 31.

The area is pruned (cut/shaved), pollarded or trimmed in a cycle of at least once every 3 years and no more than once a year in the period from January 1 to March 14 and from July 16 (see packages). After cutting or shearing, the hedge has a minimum height of 0.8 meters. Chemical weed control is not permitted, except for localized control of field thistle, dock sorrel and Jacobs' wort (only in new elements). Unwanted wood species, such as American bird cherry, American oak, Robinia and Ratelpopu lily may be controlled via excavation, mechanical or stump treatment. Protect against damage caused by grazing or tillage on adjacent lands. Grid may not be attached to the element. Ditch cuttings, dredges, grass clippings and garden waste may not be processed in the management unit. Fertilization is not allowed. No burning in, or in the immediate vicinity of the element. Regular pruning can be considered a measure to maintain soil quality, as erosion is reduced by dense hedges and shrubs.

NL_TREEROWS_AGRIScheme

Cutting of trees, rows of trees and similar vegetation.

Management requirements of different packages include:

- Package a: At least 5% to a maximum of 40% of the habitat under management is annually pruned
- Package a: A minimum of 5% to a maximum of 35% of the habitat under management is cleaned and/or mowed annually
- Package a: Trimmings have been removed or placed on rills in the element and/or clippings have been removed. Regular pruning can be considered a measure to maintain soil quality, as erosion is reduced by dense hedges and shrubs."

NL_INSECTRICH_AGRIScheme

Management requirements of different packages include at least 4 different indicator species from a list are present in transect during the period from April 1 to October 1 (growing season).

Additional management requirements include the following: The area is not grazed. The grass crop is harvested in the period September 15 to January 1 on at least 40 to maximum many times 50% of the area. Every year 50% of the plot is mowed in the period from September 15 to January 1, with the clippings being

removed. The following year, the other 50% of the area is mowed between September 15 and January 1, and the clippings are also disposed of. Mowing is not allowed outside the specified period. The grassland may not be torn, milled, ploughed or re-seeded. Chemical weed control is not allowed, with the exception of localized control of field thistle, sorrel, hedgerow weed, horsetail bindweed, horsetail, cleavers and Jacobs' wort. Grazing is not allowed. The area is not fertilized, and no dredging is applied. The measure reduces nitrogen leakages increases soil organic matter, reduces erosion by providing a vegetational cover and is thus expected to increase soil health. Additionally, the measures reduce ploughing and thus leads to carbon storage.

NL_SOIL_DEGR_AGRISCHHEME

Management requirements:

- At least 4 different indicator species from a list are present in transect in period from April 1 to October 1
- The crop is mowed and removed at least once a year
- Package a: Only use of chemical pesticides on max 10% of the surface area
- Package a and b: Fertilization with rough farmyard manure is mandatory
- Package c: Crop residues (e.g. grass clippings, straw), whether applied or not, are under-worked within 2 weeks of application

Additional management requirements: Parcel a: Fertilization is not allowed with the exception of rough manure; Package a: The rough manure is applied in a single operation between 1 February and 1 September; Package a and b: At least 10 and no more than 20 tons of rough manure per hectare is applied to the area; Package b and c: Between February 1 and September 1, the rough manure is applied and directly undercut. Crop residues are applied in a single pass between February 1 and September 1 and tilled under within two weeks of application; Packages a, b and c can only be concluded in areas agreed with the Province and Water Board within Category Water.

All packages are described so as to lead to improved soil quality by increasing soil organic matter:

- Soil improvement grassland with rough manure
- Soil improvement on arable land with rough manure
- Soil improvement on arable land with crop residues, including straw & green manures".

NL_HERBRICH_AGRISCHHEME

Management requirements

- Package a to g: At least 90% of the area from June 1 to August 15 consists of one of the following crops or crops: grass, cereals (other than corn or

grain stubble), in-seeded herbs, protein crops (alfalfa, red clover), green fallow or a combination of these.

- Package h: At least 90% of the area from July 15 to October 1 consists of one of the following crops or crops: grass, cereals (other than corn or grain stubble), sown herbs, protein crops (alfalfa, red clover), green fallow or a combination of these.
- Package i: At least 90% of the area from January 1 to June 15 consists of one of the following crops or crops: grass, cereals (other than corn or grain stubble), sown herbs, protein crops (alfalfa, red clover), green fallow or a combination of these.
- Parcel j: At least 50% of the area from June 1 to August 15 consists of one of the following crops or crops: grass, cereals (other than corn or grain stubble), sown herbs, protein crops (alfalfa, red clover), green fallow or a combination of these.
- Parcel k: At least 50% of the area from July 15 to October 1 consists of one of the following crops or crops: grass, cereals (other than corn or grain stubble), sown herbs, protein crops (alfalfa, red clover), green fallow or a combination of these.
- Package l: At least 50% of the area from January 1 to June 15 consists of one of the following crops or cultivations: grass, cereals (other than corn or grain stubble), sown herbs, protein crops (alfalfa, red clover), green fallow or a combination of these. All packages are described to lead to improvements in soil health by increasing soil organic matter, provision of a vegetation cover, additionally protein crops are grown that bind nitrogen and thus lower amounts of fertilizer are necessary."

NL_ARABLE_HAMSTERS_AGRISCHEME

Management requirements:

- Package a: At least 90 % of the area from June 1 to December 31 consists of one of the following crops or crops: cereals (other than maize or grain stubble), alfalfa, leafy radish, sown herbs, protein crops (clover or vetch) or a combination of these;
- Package b: At least 90% of the area from June 1 to December 31 consists of one of the following crops or crops: cereals (other than corn or grain stubble), sown herbs, or protein crops (clover or vetch) or a combination of these;
- Parcel c and d: At least 40% of the area from May 1 to July 1 consists of the crop cereals (other than corn), alfalfa, sown herbs, or protein crops (clover or vetch) or a combination of these; [9]

Additional management requirements.

- Seeding densities are targeted to protect Hamster (guideline: Oats 110-140 kg; Wheat 130-200 kg and Rye 120-180 kg/ha);
- Seed (of all crops) is not treated with insecticides

- Chemical weed control is only possible on a spot-by-spot basis in accordance with the Protocol for Use of Herbicides in Open Cropland, published on the SCAN Protocol Chemical Control website;
- Mechanical control of weeds is permitted throughout the year in spots (in consultation with the Collective);
- The perennial cereals, alfalfa and leaf radish shall be dredged annually in spring (February or March) to provide a suitable seed bed, in the case of perennial alfalfa for proper emergence and regrowth, or when dredged in fall for winter cereal sowing;
- Tillage shall not be deeper than 25 cm;
- The management unit will not be grazed.
- In consultation between participant and field worker, activities can be adjusted in the meantime. This will be done on the basis of new insights regarding the ecological goal range gained during the management period by both the participant and the collective. The participants in the collective work together to gain and share insights and knowledge.
- Package c
 - Lucerne may be harvested until August 1. Harvesting is done in strips of max 25 m wide and per plot strips are harvested about 3 weeks apart.
 - The grain is harvested, with the recommendation to leave the stubble, or to sow an after-wash, in consultation with field staff;
 - Use of culm shortener is permitted;
- Package d
 - Harvesting is permitted provided a cover crop is present or developing within 2-3 weeks.
 - Leave stubble with seed mixture/under crop on management unit at least through September or until next spring. The measures includes reduced tillage and thus improves soil health and increases carbon storage."

NL_BIRDFIELD_AGRIScheme-

Vogelakker Management requirements

- Package a: At least 90% of the area from June 1 to December 31 consists of one of the following crops : cereals (other than corn or grain stubble), sown herbs, protein crops (alfalfa, red clover), green fallow, leafy radish, grass or a combination of these
- Parcel b and c: At least 90% of the area from June 1 to November 15 consists of one of the following crops or crops: cereals (other than corn or grain stubble), sown herbs, protein crops (alfalfa, Red clover), green fallow, leafy radish, grass or any combination of these

Additional management requirements:

- A maximum of 50% of the uncultivated area (fallow) is mowed annually, and after August 1.

- Chemical weed control is only possible in accordance with the 'Protocol for the use of herbicides on open arable land' in agricultural nature management.
- Package a: The grain remains until March 15 of the following calendar year and then has to be ploughed or mowed and then ploughed under or removed if a summer cereal is sown. If a winter cereal is sown in succession, the cereal should remain in place until July 1 of the following calendar year and then be ploughed or mowed and then worked under or removed, after which the winter cereal should be sown between October 1 and December 1.
- The protein crops are mowed and removed at least once a year.
- The sections with protein crops, fallow and grain are grown in strips next to each other.
- The grain is sown in usual densities in the usual period and may not be harvested.
- Parcel a and c: The area may be fertilized only on the part with protein crop-sen, and within 2 days after a mowing. If fertilized, only cattle manure is allowed. Other forms of animal manure and fertilizer are not allowed.
- Parcel a is not grazed from 1 June to 31 December
- Parcels b and c are not grazed from 1 June to 15 November. The scheme improves soil health as a side effect because a vegetational cover is provided, it decreases leakages, erosion and improves soil organic matter."

NL_WIN_FOOD_FIELD

Winter food plot:

- Parcel a, b and c: At least 90% of the area from date x to date y (see described under packages) consists of summer cereal, winter cereal, leafy radish or a combination of these crops.
- Package d: At least 90% of the area from date x to date y (see described under packages) consists of an appropriate catch crop or crop residues of an appropriate catch crop.

Additional management requirements:

- A rest period is maintained during the presence of the winter food. Acreage operations and fertilization are only permitted in consultation with the collective
- Winter cereals cannot be grown on the same plot for two consecutive years. One should continue on another field.
- The management unit should be sown annually between March 16 and April 30 (package a) or between June 1 and October 1 (packages b and c) with a usual seeding density, as far as summer cereals or leafy radish are concerned. If a combination of crops is chosen, they should be grown in strips side by side.

- Variant d: flail catch crop only if seed is set and only if target species forage on the bottom.
- Chemical weed control is only possible in accordance with the 'Protocol for the use of herbicides on open arable land'.
- Collective draws up a list of suitable catch crops based on the list 'The catch crops from the Pillar 1 list of ecological focus areas'. The scheme improves soil health as a side effect because a vegetational cover is provided, it decreases leakages, erosion and improves soil organic matter."

NL_BOT_GRASSLAND

Botanically valuable grassland:

- Packages a through g: Use of chemical weed control only on max. 10% of area.
- Packages a to g: At least 4 different indicator species from list b are present in transect in the period from April 1 to October 1 (growing season)
- Package a : From March 1 to October 1, grazing is allowed with maximum livestock density 2 LU/ha
- Packages b, c, d, e, f and g: The crop is mowed and removed at least once a year. [
- Packages e, f and g: A rest period is observed from date x to date y (see described under packages).

Additional management requirements.

- The management unit shall not be fertilized or dredged.
- The grassland may not be torn and/or milled.
- Clearing is not allowed.
- Package a: Supplementary feeding is not allowed.
- Package b: Grazing is not allowed from March 1 to August 1.
- Packages c and d: Edges are on the outside of the field.
- Package d: Grazing is not allowed from 1 January to 31 December
- Packages e, f and g: No tillage or grazing is allowed in the area during the rest period. The scheme reduces tillage, provides a vegetational cover and includes extensified grazing and making it beneficial for soil health."

NL_ROUGH_MOST

Mandatory fertilisation with rough manure.

- A minimum of 10 and a maximum of 20 tons of rough stable manure per hectare is applied to the management unit in a calendar year.
- The rough stall manure is applied at once between February 1, or at the start date of the rest period of the relevant agricultural management

package, or from the day following the end date of the rest period of the relevant agricultural management package until September 1. Fertilization with rough manure increases soil organic matter and thus improves soil health.

NL_EXTE_GRAZED_GRASS

Management requirements:

- Grazing is mandatory from date x to date y with minimum a and maximum stocking density b (LU/ha). The period and the density varies by management parcel.

Additional management requirements.

- Parcel a and c: From April 1 to June 15, agricultural operations are not allowed.
- Parcel b: No agricultural practices are allowed from 1 April to 15 October
- Agricultural operations not permitted include mowing, rolling, dragging, tearing, milling, (re)seeding, overseeding and fertilizing. The use of chemical pesticides is not permitted during the above period.

Packages:

- a) obligatory grazing from May 1st to June 15th, minimum 1 and maximum 1,5 LU/ha.
- b) obligatory grazing from 1 May to 15 October, minimum 0,15 and maximum 0,5 LU/ha
- c) Grazing obligatory from May 1 to June 15, minimum 1 LU/ha and maximum 3 LU/ha. The scheme reduces permits tillage and includes extensive grazing, these requirements lead to increased soil organic matter and carbon storage."

NL_GREENFALLOW_ESCHEME

Green fallow on arable land: at least 80% visibly covered from May 31 to August 31. For example, by sowing an herb mixture or spontaneous emergence. This eco-activity can also be applied on a field edge. The field edge is at least 3 meters wide. Chemical plant protection products and manure are prohibited in this scheme, as are grazing, and harvesting. Green fallow can increase soil health by reducing erosion, additionally the vegetational cover increases the organic matter."

NL_HERBS_GRASS_ESCHEME

Buffer strip with herbs (along grassland). With a buffer strip with herbs increases biodiversity and improve water quality, additionally buffer stripes

are not harvested and increase soil organic matter - all of these aspects improve soil health.

Required is a buffer strip with herbs along arable land (except temporary grassland) or along a plot of permanent crops. The buffer strip is minimum 3 and maximum 12 meters wide. From April 1 to October 1, at least 25% of the buffer strip is visibly covered. And evenly distributed with herbs and leguminous crops. Fertilization of the buffer strip or use chemical plant protection products is not allowed. Grazing and harvesting the buffer strip is also prohibited. Mowing and draining is allowed."

NL_HERBS_PERMANENT_ESCHEME

Buffer strip with herbs (along arable land and permanent crops). With a buffer strip with herbs, you increase biodiversity and improve water quality. Additionally, buffer stripes are not harvested and increase soil organic matter - all of these aspects improve soil health.

Required is a buffer strip with herbs along arable land (except temporary grassland) or along a plot of permanent crops. The buffer strip is minimum 3 and maximum 12 meters wide. From April 1 to October 1, at least 25% of the buffer strip is visibly covered. And evenly distributed with herbs and leguminous crops. Fertilization of the buffer strip or use chemical plant protection products is not allowed. Grazing and harvesting the buffer strip is also prohibited. Mowing and draining is allowed."

NL_GRAZING_DAYNIGHT_ESCHEME

Extended grazing - day and night grazing: By grazing cows reduce ammonia emissions and improve the quality of the landscape.

The dairy cows graze a minimum of 6 hours a day from May 1 to September 30. Animals may be kept indoors if they are sick, dry or have calved no more than 14 days ago, and the humidity is high.

Farmers keep a grazing calendar with the date and time. Offer dairy free access is also allowed but then a maximum of 25% of dairy cattle will be in the barn during the recorded grazing hours. In this scheme cows are also outside during night hours. Grazing is considered beneficial for biodiversity, especially with low livestock densities. Additionally, the cows provide organic manure which increases soil organic matter. Even if the livestock units are not restricted benefits for soil health are possible."

NL_GRAZING_DAY_ESCHEME

Extended grazing - daytime grazing: By grazing cows reduce ammonia emissions and improve the quality of the landscape.

The dairy cows graze a minimum of 6 hours a day from May 1 to September 30. Animals may be kept indoors if they are sick, dry or have calved no more than 14 days ago, and the humidity is high.

Farmers keep a grazing calendar with the date and time. Offer dairy free access is also allowed but then a maximum of 25% of dairy cattle will be in the barn during the recorded grazing hours. Grazing is considered beneficial for biodiversity, especially with low livestock densities. Additionally, the cows provide organic manure which increases soil organic matter. Even if the livestock units are not restricted benefits for soil health are possible."

NL_UNDERSEEDING_ESCHEME

When growing the main crop, a catch crop is also sown. Underseeding allows the catch crop to develop better. Immediately after the harvest of the main crop the field is visibly covered with the catch crop. This catch crop is a different crop than the main crop. The catch crop stays until at least December 1, the plot must be at least 80% visibly covered. Chemical crop protection is forbidden. Catching crops reduces nitrogen leakages, improve soil organic matter and thus carbon storage.

NL_GREEN_COVER_ESCHEME

Keeping plots covered increases organic matter content and improves soil quality, additionally erosion is reduced.

The field is visibly covered at least 80% from January 1 to March 1. This is done with the catch crop or green manure crop. Plant protection products on a maximum of 10% of the plot may be used. The catch crop is underworked with machinery for the main crop. It is not allowed to spray or burn the catch crop prior to underworking.

NL_EARLY_HARVEST_ESCHEME

Harvest crop early (no later than August 31). Harvesting crops early allows to work on soil with less structural decay. This also provides a good period and suitable soil for sowing a catch crop. The crop needs to be harvested no later than Aug. 31.

NL_NITROGENFIXING_ESCHEME

A protein crop for fertile soil, increased nitrogen uptake and improved biodiversity is grown.

A mixture of nitrogen fixing crops is allowed. A mixture of a nitrogen fixing crop with other crops is not allowed. Except with corn if the nitrogen fixing crop is more than 50%.

NL_DORMANT_ESCHEME

Growing a dormant crop improves soil structure. It provides more organic matter and moisture in your soil and fewer crop diseases.

A rest crop is grown at the field level in a rotation of at least 1 to 3. This means a rest crop is the main crop on the plot at least once every 3 years. The plot is visibly covered, and you may harvest, mow or graze."

NL_WET_CROP_ESCHEME

Wet cultivation reduces CO₂ emissions and increases biodiversity. Wet cultivation is suitable for areas with a high-water table, such as peatlands. The plot is visibly covered and harvested at least once a year. Cultivation must be on land that was in use as farmland between 2015 and 2022."

NL_PERENNIAL_CROP_ESCHEME

By growing perennial crops, the soil has more time to rest. Additionally, more organic matter is generated, and better soil structure is achieved.

A perennial crop needs to be the main crop on the plot for at least 2 years in a row. The crop must remain in place during the winter. The plot is visibly covered. This activity only accounts for the eco-scheme from the 2nd year. In 2023, this means that the crop can count if that crop was also the main crop in 2022.

NL_PERM_GRASSLAND_ESCHEME

With long-term grassland builds up organic matter in the soil. This is good for soil structure. Perennial grassland from January 1 to December 31 needs to visibly cover the plots. Light tillage is allowed if the cover remains visible, ploughing is not allowed. Plant protection products on up to 10% of the plot can be used.

NL_GRASSLAND_HERBS_ESCHEME

Grassland with herbs provides deeper rooting and better soil structure. From April 1 to October 1:

- the plot contains at least 25% herbs and leguminous crops (sown or spontaneous emergence);
- and at least 25% grass. The practice leads to increases soil organic matter, thus positively affects soil structure. Additionally, it leads to soil cover and less run-off and soil erosion."

NL_GRASS_COVER_ESCHEME

Sowing grass-clover reduces or eliminates the use of fertilizer. From April 1 to July 1, the plot contains at least 25% grass and at least 25% clover. The practice leads to reduced chemical fertilizer usage, increases soil organic matter, thus positively affects soil structure."

NL_A3_PRECISION_FARMING

Up to 40 % of investment subsidies are granted for investments in targeted irrigation (sensors and dripping techniques). A maximum of 150,000 euros is paid out per company. The subsidy has an indirect effect on soil health: Targeted irrigation reduces nutrient losses; furthermore, targeted trough irrigation can reduce the number of tank truck passes and avoid compaction of soils

NL_A2_PRECISION_FARMING

up to 40 % of investment subsidies are granted for investments in targeted organic fertilization (sensors and targeted application). A maximum of 150,000 euros is paid out per company. The subsidy has an indirect effect on soil health: Organic fertilization is beneficial for soils especially when phosphorus over fertilization is avoided. This might be ensured by using sensors that measure the nutrient content of the fertilizer, and by dosing fertilizers correctly, and by row fertilization, or partial area specific fertilization).

NL_B4_DIGITALISATION

Up to 40 % of investment subsidies are granted for investment in measuring and monitoring water lens thickness and depth and measuring soil compaction, among other things. A maximum of 150,000 euros is paid out per company. The subsidy has a direct effect on soil health: more information on soil compaction helps to choose appropriate measures (reduction of crossings).

NL_C1_DRAINAGE

Up to 40 % of investment subsidies are granted for investment climate adaptive, level-controlled, controllable drainage. A maximum of 150,000 euros is paid out per company. The subsidy influences soil health because standing water leads to denitrification and can affect soil negatively.

NL_E2_CROP_ROT

Up to 40 % of investment subsidies are granted for investment in trip-till (reduced tillage), harvesters for protein crops (legumes), and for machines seeding cover crops between rows. A maximum of 150,000 euros is paid out per company. The subsidy influences soil health because as cover crops cover organic matter. Additionally, strip till and reduced tillage is important as tillage increases oxygen in the soil, stimulates microbial activity and leads to a decomposition of soil organic matter. It further disrupts soils aggregates.

NL_E3_HERB_GRASS

Up to 40 % of investment subsidies are granted for investment in the cultivation of woody crops (trees and shrubs) combined with livestock, vegetables, or arable farming on the same plot of agricultural land (Agroforestry). A maximum of 150,000 euros is paid out per company. Agroforestry systems present a less intensive use of land, the cultivation of trees is beneficial for organic matter (leaves), additionally grazing provides organic matter. Since the grazing area needs to consist of permanent pasture and a mix of leguminous plants that make nitrogen available, a reduction of additional mineral fertilizer amounts can be achieved.

NL_E4_SOIL_COMPACTIION_REDUCTION

Up to 40 % of investment subsidies are granted for investment in systems, machines, implements aimed at and used for non-till, shallow soil preparation and surface mixing of crop residues (possibly in combination with direct seeding, planting or planting), among others (non-soil related machines)

machine to incorporate manure are also subsidized under this scheme. Additionally, machines that increase air pressure in wheels to lower soil structural damages are subsidized. A maximum of 150,000 euros is paid out per company. Tillage increases oxygen in the soil, stimulates microbial activity and leads to a decomposition of soil organic matter. Tillage also disrupts soils aggregates.

NL_E6_ORGANIC_RESIDUES

Up to 40 % of investment subsidies are granted for investments specifically intended for the processing of organic residues (other than manure at farm level) with the aim of increasing soil quality. These investments include machines for mowing and collecting equipment, and machines for applying cut material and compost. Soil organic matter is decisive for the cation exchange capacity and increases the carbon stored in soils.

NL_E7_NONDIG_GRAZING

Up to 40 % of subsidies are granted for investments such as crosswalks, spring grids or cow tunnels - thus measures supporting grazing. Soil organic matter is decisive for the cation exchange capacity and increases the carbon stored in soils.

NL_E7_COMPOST

Up to 40 % of subsidies are granted for investments in storage of crop residues, solid manure, or compost. The aim is to increase soil quality (organic matter content and soil structure).

NL_ORG_FARM

Farmers certified as organic have to dedicate a share of their land to nature (biodiversity), additionally chemical fertilizers and pesticides are banned (increases biodiversity), using organic fertilizer increases soil organic matter and CO₂ sequestration. After a period of 2-3 years, they can apply for certification and after being certified sell their plant products as organic. In animal husbandry the conversion period takes between 6 months and 2 years, this depends on the animal species. Farmers can get subsidies over the transitions NPLG, the omschakelprogramma Duurzame Landbouw, the GLB - NSP programme which translates the CAP into national law, the knowledge and innovation (kennis en innovatie) funds.

NL_AGRO_FORESTRY

A subsidy of 75 % of investment costs is granted for investments in agroforestry. Agroforestry is an agricultural system in which trees and shrubs are deliberately combined with arable, vegetable or livestock farming. There are various forms, such as strip farming, forest meadows, riparian strips, forage hedges, shade trees and food forests. Trees and shrubs can make farmland less vulnerable to the effects of climate. They affect the landscape, contribute to biodiversity, retain carbon, and allow water to soak into the soil and retain water.

NL_NAT_INCLUSIVE_CIRC_AGRI

The Province of Gelderland considers it important that farmers in Gelderland receive support in the development of their agricultural enterprise towards nature-inclusive and/or circular agriculture with a sustainable earnings model. Agricultural entrepreneurs can be supported in this by an advisor who is an expert in this field. This consultant can be reimbursed the costs of the advice for a fixed amount of €1,500 through this scheme. Farmers seeking advice for sustainable land use, how to increase biodiversity, on how to reduce emission among others qualify for the subsidy. The maximum amount is 1,500 Euro.

NL_NEW_FORESTS

Gelderland strives for new forests on agricultural land, to increase biodiversity and slow down biodiversity loss. The subsidy is paid for farmers converting their land into forests. The subsidy is intended to cover the loss of land value. The maximum amount of payment is 15,000 per hectare and should cover 100 % of the value losses.

NL_NO_DRUG_WASTE

The removal of soil contaminated by drugs is subsidized.

NL_AGRIFOOD_INNOV

Subsidies are granted for companies seeking to produce innovative agrifood. Investments in assets (e.g., machinery), market research or product design, knowledge transfer and education can be subsidized. Furthermore, projects need to contribute to at least two of the following aspects to qualify: sustainability of the physical living environment (soil, water, air, nature); marketing products and services of the agricultural business through new revenue models or innovative market concepts; appreciation from society for the agricultural sector or the appeal of agricultural entrepreneurship. In addition, the project must: be innovative, have a good chance of success, be feasible in practice and suitable for large-scale applications.

In the project plan farmers must indicate how they will make the project known to sector colleagues and how they will make the results of the project accessible to them. The share of subsidies varies by subsidy objective from 40-60 %, the maximum is 35,000 Euro. Overall, subsidies for the marketing of soil friendly products or the investment in machinery might be granted through this scheme."

NL_KWELDERBEHER

A subsidy of 98 Euro per hectare is granted for grazing on salt marshes. This is to restore the variety of plants and animals (biodiversity) on the Groninger kwelders and to protect them against nuisance from seaweed (grass species). Grazing increases soil organic matter and thus increases carbon storage. Additionally, grazing is considered beneficial for biodiversity.

NL_CLEAR_DRUG_WASTE

The removal of soil contaminated by drugs, other chemical substances and the removal of waste is subsidized.

NL_FOREST_WOOD_200K

Groningen supports the planting of trees either the planting of forests (up to 200,000 Euros), the planting of lines of trees (up to 100,00 Euros) or the planting of rather singular elements (up to 50,000 Euros). Trees help to reduce soil erosion. Additionally, soil organic matter increases through leaves.

NL_NATURE_QUALITY_SKNL

Farmers located in nature protection areas are compensated if they are willing to develop their area into a nature reserve. As this could potentially lead to more extensive grassland, or peat meadow flooding, a sequestration of CO₂ is expected. The subsidy should cover the value losses.

NL_REGIO_FARMER_EXPERIMENTS

Farmers interested in nature inclusive farming can qualify for subsidies. The idea of implementing an idea / technique should contribute to the nature conservation ideas of Veenkolonien, Westerwolde and Oldambt. Measures that improve soil health are listed as techniques that qualify for subsidies, marketing efforts for more sustainable products are also listed (min. amount 5,000 Euro, max. 25,000 Euro).

NL_IMPLM_SCH_NATURE

Farmers interested in nature inclusive farming on peat meadows can qualify for subsidies. The idea of implementing an idea/ technique should contribute to nature conservation ideas. Measures that improve soil health are listed as techniques that qualify for subsidies, among others herb rich grassland (leads to fewer plowing and renewal) and growing crops under wet conditions is listed (min. amount 5,000 Euro, max. 25,000 Euro).

NL_REG_ORGANIC_FARM_EXPERIMENTS

Organic farmers interested in further developing production practices qualify for subsidy. Organic farming uses organic manure only, additionally legumes binding nitrogen are grown, thus organic farming might lead to higher CO₂ sequestration. Having additional funding available might make it more attractive for farmers to switch (min. 5,000 Euro, max 15,000 Euro).

NL_FARM_EXPER_FRISIAN

Subsidies are granted for partnerships of two or more agricultural entrepreneurs in the Frisian Clay Meadow whether or not together with area parties such as land managers or chain parties. Hereby an agricultural entrepreneur must act as a leader. New cooperations should promote sustainable practices - such as enriching soil life. Increasing knowledge and space for experiments and new forms of cooperation is the aim of the scheme.

NL_PARCEL_EXCHANGE

The province makes subsidies available for parcel exchanges until the end of the budget or until the end of 2023. The subsidy consists of reimbursing process costs, such as notary fees, land registry fees and a limited reimbursement for consultant fees. This can potentially lead to better chances for the province to set up larger scale carbon storage projects: as parcels where the water level is raised usually need to be connected (in other words if within a group of peat parcel one parcel is drained, this lowers water levels on other parcels as well and thus the carbon storage capacities).

NL_QUALITY_SCHEME_IMPULSE

The province of Fryslân is committed to the development and realization of nature. This involves the permanent conversion of agricultural land into nature and the establishment of these areas within the NNN (Nature Network Netherlands). Landowners are encouraged to participate in nature development. The amount of this subsidy is determined based on the appraised agricultural value. The province offers compensation for 85 % of the loss of land values. Nature reserves are not intensify used. Additionally, the scheme might lead to increases in grassland and thus lower tillage densities or even bans on tillage.

NL_IND_SCHEME_ADVICE_ALDEBOARN

The Province of Groningen considers it important that farmers receive support for the development of their agricultural enterprise towards nature-inclusive practices. Agricultural entrepreneurs can be supported in this by an advisor who is an expert in this field. The maximum amount is 1,500 Euro.

NL_FARM_EXPER_WESTERWOLDE

Farmers interested in nature inclusive farming can qualify for subsidies. The idee of implementing an idea / technique should contribute to the nature conservation ideas of Veenkolonien, Westerwolde and Oldambt. Measures that improve soil health are listed as techniques that qualify for subsidies, marketing efforts for more sustainable products are also listed (min amount 5,000 Euro, max 25,000 Euro).

NL_LAND_AQUISITION_SUBS

The province of Drenthe is committed to the development and realization of nature. This involves the permanent conversion of agricultural land into nature and the establishment of these areas within the NNN (Nature Network Netherlands). Landowners are encouraged to participate in nature development. The amount of this subsidy is determined by the province. Converting land into nature may lead to lower usage intensities, for instance, reduced tillage or even bans on tillage.

NL_SOIL_REMED_SUBS

The removal of contaminated soil is subsidized under this scheme.

NL_CLEANING_DRUG_SUBSIDY

The removal of soil contaminated with chemicals is subsidized (the amounts up to 200,000 Euro).

NL_FUT_ORIENTED_GRANT

Farmers interested in nature inclusive farming can qualify for subsidies. The province of Drenthe wants to encourage agribusiness farmers and entrepreneurs (SMEs) to innovate, modernize, become more sustainable and share knowledge. Projects related to these goals qualify for subsidies.

NL_FOREST_WOOD_70K

Overijssel supports the planting of trees or the planting of forests (up to 70,000 Euros for the loss of soil value and 20,000 Euros for planting and planting materials). Trees provide additional soil organic matter by leaves, additionally they lower soil erosion.

NL_PERM_GRASSLAND

A plot on which farmers grow grass for at least 5 consecutive years becomes permanent grassland in the 6th year. Permanent grassland is one of the greening requirements. Nationally, this may not fall by more than 5% compared to 2012. Additional conditions apply to ecologically vulnerable permanent grassland. Grassland needs to be grazed or mowed at least once a year. This must be done by October 31 at the latest. It may not be treated up and reseeded if the land is ecologically sensitive permanent grassland (ploughing ban). Farmers may only overseed and lightly till the soil. This means that you must not damage the surface and that covering vegetation remains visible.

NL_CONDITIONALITIES

Part of the EU's common agricultural policy is the green-blue architecture, it strives to enhance biodiversity, ensure good water quality, and improve soil health. Farmers receive a basic premium (220 Euro per hectare, with decreasing amounts) and payments for eco-schemes (heights depending on farmers engagement are granted in the Netherlands). The conditionality requirements seek to ensure a sustainable redirection of agriculture. In the Netherlands the conditionality (good agricultural and environmental conditions - GAEC) requirements strongly seek to fulfill the countries National action plan (NSP), and often address nitrogen surpluses. Measures reducing nitrogen leakages and other measures that directly affect soil health are: 1) Maintenance of permanent grassland, 2) minimum protection of wetland and peatland at latest by 2024, 3) ban of burning arable stubble, except for plant health reasons as this burns organic matter, 4) Establishment of buffer strips along water courses (as soil cover reduces erosion and increases organic matter), 5) Tillage management or other appropriate techniques to limit the risk of soil degradation, taking into account the land gradient, 6) Minimum soil cover in period(s) and areas that are most sensitive, 7) Crop rotation or other practices aimed at preserving the soil potential, such as crop diversification and 8) the requirement for farm set-asides (a share of area needs to be non-

productive or needs to be used for growing catch crops or nitrogen fixing crops), 9) Ban on converting or ploughing of permanent grassland in Natura 2000 sites. The requirements listed here under 5, 6, and 7 are mostly addressing soil. The measures 1,2,3 are described to be climatic change actions, while 8 and 9 are mostly seeking to protect biodiversity and landscapes

NL_PEATLANDS_WETLANDS_PROT_GLMC2

When peat is not in contact with the outside air, carbon dioxide and nutrients remain in the soil.

Non-free-draining peat soil that is below one meter of the Normal Amsterdam Level may not deviate from the established water level in the area."

NL_NO_STUBBLE_BURN_GAEC 3

Leaving stubble in place keeps organic matter in the soil. This improves soil quality and biodiversity.

After harvesting and mowing the stubble cannot be burnt. However, exceptions can be granted for diseased."

NL_EROSION_CONT_GAEC 5

Less erosion means better soil fertility.

This standard applies only in a designated area in the Limburg region. Erosion causes more runoff of water and soil. In the long run, this is not good for soil fertility.

To prevent erosion, these measures, for example, are mandatory:

- till the soil to at least 15 centimetres.
- erase tractor tracks.
- use a plot with a slope of 18% or more exclusively as grassland.
- on fields with a slope percentage of 2% or more: shallow plough, apply the mulching system and report measures and buffer provision."

NL_SOIL_COVER_MIN_GAEC 6

With minimal ground cover, you protect the soil and ensure nutrients stay in the soil.

In summer, a green manure crop no later than 31 May needs to be sown. This should be done in a field that has been taken out of production. This green manure crop stays until at least 31 August. Another option is to cover the soil with crop residues between 31 May and 31 August. In autumn and winter, there are 3 rules for soil cover:

- On clay, covering 80% of the arable land for at least 8 weeks between 1 August and 30 November is necessary.

- From 16 September to 1 February, grassland or permanent crops may not be touched. There are exceptions, for example if farmers grow flower bulbs.
- It is compulsory to grow a catch crop after maize on sand and loess until 1 February. From 2024, this will also be compulsory for designated clay and peat soils."

NL_CROP_ROT_GAEC 7

Crop rotation is good for soil health, it prevents diseases and improves soil structure. Due to the war in Ukraine, this standard only takes effect since 2024.

- on at least 1/3 of the arable land, a different crop each year as the main crop (different crop code) needs to be grown. Farmers need to grow a different crop as the main crop on their parcels once every 4 years;
- it is compulsory to grow a rest crop as main crop once every 4 years on sandy and loess soil. From 2027, this will become once every 3 years.
- a follow crop after the main crop in the same year is also considered crop rotation. For follow-on cultivation, a different crop type, with a crop code needs to be chosen.
- for fallow, wet cultivation, perennial crops, grasses and herbaceous forage not crop rotation requirements apply.

Additionally, exception on arable land apply:

- when more than 75% of the total arable land is for e.g. grasses, herbaceous forage, fallow and/or leguminous crops;
- when more than 75% of all the arable land is permanent pasture, grasses, herbaceous forage or wetland crops;
- for organic farmer (with certification and not in conversion);

Is your plot located in the Oldambt or Hoeksche Waard region? Do you grow winter wheat, winter barley, winter rape or winter turnip seed? Then you are exempt from the annual rotation if you adhere to the crop diversification requirement. You adhere to crop diversification if you have at least 3 crops on your arable land. The main crop is on at most 75% of your arable land. The third crop is on at least 5% of your arable land. But again, this does not take effect until 2024.

NL_BUFFER_STRIPS_GAEC 4

On a buffer strip, farmers are not allowed to use manure or plant protection products. By doing so, they contribute to surface water quality; additionally buffer strips reduce soil erosion and provide organic matter. There are four rules:

- The buffer strip is 5 metres wide along watercourses of ecologically sensitive watercourses.
- The buffer strip is 5 metres along watercourses covered by the Water Framework Directive (WFD).
- The buffer strip is 3 metres wide along other watercourses.

- The buffer strip is 1 meter wide along ditches that are dry between 1 April and 1 October (GAEC 10).

Moreover, this is subject to several additional rules:

- In ecologically sensitive watercourses, the buffer strip is never smaller than 5 meters wide.
- For watercourses from the WFD, the buffer strip can be reduced from 5 meters to 3 meters. This is only possible if the buffer strips together on a plot cover more than 4% of the surface area of the plot. Are the buffer strips together still more than 4% of the plot after that? Then the buffer strip can also be reduced to 1 meter. But this is only possible for WFD aquifer ditches of up to 10 meters wide.
- For other watercourses, the buffer strip can be reduced from 3 meters to 1 meter. This is only possible if the buffer strips together cover more than 4% of the plot. Do the buffer strips together still exceed 4% of the plot? Then the buffer strip can also be reduced to 0.5 meters.

NL_NONPROD_ARABLE_LAND_GAEC8

Non-productive arable land creates habitats for animals and plants. This improves biodiversity. The different elements have diverse effects on soil health, wooded area reduces erosion, other measures such as wild grass directly reduce ploughing. The obligation is to leave 4% of arable land non-productive. This has been postponed for a year (due to the war in Ukraine).

These standards do go into effect immediately in 2023 are:

- maintain landscape elements.
- ban on pruning in the breeding period.

Farmers can participate in the eco-scheme and use green set-aside and/or buffer strips as eco-activity. There are 3 ways to leave your arable land non-productive:

- Fill in 4% with landscape elements, such as ditches, wooded banks, rows of trees. Or with other non-productive elements such as field edges, buffer strips or green fallow.
- leave 7% of your arable land non-productive. You can then fill in 4% with the eco-activities non-productive arable land.
- leave 7% of your arable land non-productive. You can then fill in 4% with nitrogen-fixing crops without using plant protection products.

Farmers are exempt from the obligation of 4% non-productive and a maximum of 96% maize or soya if:

- more than 75% of the arable land is for e.g. grasses, herbaceous forage, fallow and/or leguminous crops.
- more than 75% of your arable land consists of permanent pasture, grasses and other herbaceous forage or wetland crops.
- if farmers are organic farmers (with certification and not in conversion) and have up to 10 hectares of arable land."

NL_RABO_CARBON_BANK

The Dutch Rabobank supports farmers in developing sustainable business models (e.g., by offering financing solutions and agronomic advice). These business models seek carbon reductions by switching towards regenerative farming practices. Practices include reductions in chemical fertilizers and pesticides, improvements in crop rotation, adding cover crops, and rising water levels. The carbon reduction achieved by these practices is verified, and carbon credits are sold by the bank. The bank operates internationally. Three-year trials for the described 'Rabo Carbon Bank' currently run in the US and the Netherlands with dairy and arable farmers. The generated carbon credits are sold to large companies such as Vattenfall.

NL_UDEA_CARB_FARMING

UDEA set up the project, it is a trading company for organic groceries, and other sustainably produced goods. UDEA is seeking to make their business carbon neutral and thus compensates farmers for carbon sequestration measures. The scheme is only offered to organic farmers. They seek to scale the scheme up and offer it to more organic farms in the future. The applied carbon storages techniques are not further described.

NL_ZLTO

The project links farmers and other supply chain actors. (Chain) parties can, for instance, make their product more sustainable or offset their CO₂ emissions by storing carbon with a farmer in the region. Farmer or horticulturist are compensated for the efforts. Carbon storage should be achieved by using manure, less to no ploughing, applying crop rotation and agroforestry.

NL_CARBON_FARMERS

Carbon farmers is a company by a collective of agricultural entrepreneurs who seek making the Dutch agricultural sector more sustainable. They focus on soil improvement and seek linking them to new earning models for their members. They explore the potential of carbon certificates or carbon credits as an additional source of income. Companies seeking to offset their last bit of emissions can buy carbon credits. With the proceeds, farmers can adapt their farming practices and store carbon, thereby reducing CO₂ in the air, improving nature and soil fertility. Ongoing projects for carbon storage are growing elephant grass, or bamboo.

NL_CLOSE_FARM

The collective sells carbon credits generated by their members over the ZLTO project. The project links farmers and other supply chain actors: (Chain) parties, for instance, seek to make their product more sustainable or offset their CO₂ emissions by storing carbon with a farmer in the region. Farmer or horticulturist are compensated for the efforts. Carbon storage should be achieved by using manure, less to no ploughing, applying crop rotation and agroforestry.

NL_ECOLABEL

Het Milieukeur is a certificate for farmers that produce sustainably. The certificate is granted in the agro-food sector, applicants need to fulfil requirements for biodiversity and landscape, fertilisation and soil fertility, provide higher animal welfare and prevent damages from chem. pesticides. The measures are controlled twice per year.

NL_PIG_PRODUCTION_RIGHTS

The production permits for pigs determine how many pigs Dutch farmers may keep. The production permits are tradeable. For areas with high intensities (East and South Netherlands) production rights must be traded within that area and additional rights cannot be bought in from other areas. According to the FAO 9% of carbon emissions come from livestock husbandry. Limiting livestock husbandry and farmers' chances to grow in this branch of production directly reduces carbon emissions.

NL_WARM_REHABILITATION_PIG_FARMING

The Dutch government offers farmers close to nature reserves and in areas with intensive production of pigs a buyout from production. Farmers receive market-based compensation for the barns and the production quotas for pigs. The scheme was originally introduced for pigs but is now offered to dairy and poultry producers close to nature protection areas as well. According to the FAO 9% of carbon emissions come from livestock husbandry. Reducing livestock husbandry reduces carbon emissions.

5.3.9 Spain

Ten Spanish incentives were analysed (figure 38), and they had the greatest impact on enhancing the following ecosystem services: soil quality, biodiversity, and landscape and scenery. They were followed by climate regulation, cultural heritage, and climate regulation in terms of carbon storage.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 38 Areas of the Spanish incentives' enhancement

The application of these incentives improves ecosystem services in the following ways:

ES_ECOSCH_PD31

The practice of extensive grazing, with appropriate stocking rates and organic matter contribution to the soil, leads to increased carbon absorption in pastures. This not only improves soil quality and composition but also helps offset the carbon footprint generated by agriculture and livestock. Implementing suitable stocking rates avoids overuse of these areas, which can cause environmental damage, and promotes sustainable resource utilization by the national livestock population.

ES_INTP_ROD

Integrated production refers to agricultural systems that maximize the use of natural resources and production mechanisms while ensuring long-term sustainability. It involves incorporating biological and chemical methods of control and other techniques that balance societal demands, environmental protection, and agricultural productivity. The specific management requirements of these systems contribute to increasing organic matter in the soil, carbon sequestration, and improving soil structure. Additionally, the use of covers helps protect the soil from erosion and promotes biodiversity.

ES_CUST_TER

The implementation of land stewardship models provides legal protection to initially degraded areas or areas with potential biodiversity value. It also encourages the creation of green areas. Actions focused on soil and species recovery improve soil health, enhance the landscape, and increase biodiversity.

ES_HERCR_10.1.4

Implementation and management of multifunctional margins (flower strips). The realization of direct sowing, accompanied by the maintenance of the remains of dry herbaceous crops on the ground. Participation in a technical monitoring and verification system of agri-environmental commitments, accredited through an integrated production certification entity, recognized for this purpose. The applicant must be part of an Integrated Production Group of the eligible crop, duly registered in the Integrated Production Registry of Andalusia.

ES_AGROIND_10.1.5

Establishment of an organic amendment through a leguminous crop as green manure, once in the commitment period (1/5); This commitment may be carried out in one year on the entire surface area committed or in several years as long as the entire area is reached. This crop must be sown throughout the autumn, after the cotton and/or beet cultivation and must remain in the ground until the flowering stage, and at least until February 28, and it will be incorporated into the soil with a tillage. In cases where the competent authority establishes it, regarding officially recognized situations, exceptions may be made. VOLUNTARY COMMITMENTS: Likewise, the following voluntary commitment is established, eligible only for farms with less than 15 hectares committed, and in addition to the previous ones. Establishment of a natural amendment by means of a cruciferous culture for its green burial, once in the commitment period (1/5); This commitment may be carried out in one year on the entire surface area committed or in several years as long as the entire area is reached. This crop must be sown throughout the autumn, after the cotton and/or beet cultivation, and must remain on the ground until February 28 and will be fully or partially incorporated into the soil with tillage. It cannot be established in the same agricultural campaign as the green manure with legumes. In cases where the competent authority establishes it, regarding officially recognized situations, exceptions may be made. The applicant must be part of an Integrated Production Group of the eligible crop, duly registered in the Integrated Production Registry of Andalusia.

ES_WOODY_10.1.6

The agricultural plots declared in the payment request with crops eligible for this operation must obtain the certification in Integrated production.

General commitments relating to the implementation and maintenance of the vegetable cover, spontaneous or sown:

- Coverage will be maintained between October 15 and March 15 of the following year.
- Its average minimum width will be 1.80 meters. In the vine, the cover will be implanted in alternate streets and with a minimum average width of 1.80 meters.
- The management of the vegetation covers to limit the competition for water and nutrients will be carried out at the end of winter or in spring

by mechanical means through at least one annual pass of a mechanical mower, or by tine harvesting. If necessary, only two herbicide applications may be used and only one per year throughout the five-year duration of the operation in order to avoid undesirable species; Said applications, when appropriate, will be carried out after the mechanical mowing of the roof. Efforts will be made to establish good management practices in the covers that allow the self-sufficiency of an own seed bank, especially to improve the implantation of the cover in the years that planting is not carried out.

- It is prohibited to till the roofs, except those superficial works to adapt the land for planting them.

Specific commitments in the case of sowed covers: The implementation will be carried out at least three times during the commitment period (five years), one of which must be carried out in the first year of the commitment period.

Voluntary commitment for the cultivation of the almond tree: Shredding and distribution of pruning remains. At least two prunings will take place during the commitment period. This commitment will not be made when phytosanitary problems are observed, duly justified by means of a technical report and/or analytical results."

ES_OLIVE_10.1.7

The agricultural plots declared in the payment request with crops eligible for this operation must obtain the certification in Integrated production.

1. Average slope of the plot higher than 8%.
2. Located in basins that flow into reservoirs for human consumption or in the Natura 2000 Network. La implantación y el mantenimiento de una cubierta vegetal espontánea o sembrada:

Commitments:

The implantation and maintenance of a spontaneous or sown vegetation cover:

- Coverage will be maintained between October 15 and March 15 of the following year
- Its average minimum width will be, depending on the type of plantation, 1.80 meters, in the case of narrow vegetation covers, and 3.60 meters, in the case of wide vegetation covers.
- The management of vegetation covers to limit competition for water and nutrients will be carried out at the end of winter or in spring by mechanical means. - It is prohibited to till the covers, except for those superficial works to adapt the land for planting them.
- In the case of seeded covers:

The implementation will take place at least three times during the commitment period (five years), one of which must be carried out in the first year of the commitment period.

Fertilization will be applied to help optimal implantation of the cover (only in the years in which it is implanted).

Voluntary commitment:

Shredding and distribution of pruning remains, taking into account that at least two prunings will be carried out during the commitment period. This commitment will not be made when duly justified phytosanitary problems are identified through a technical report or analytical results. Those superficial works to adapt the land for planting them.

ES_BIRDS_10.1.8

Actions in SPA

1. Stubble maintenance: It is about keeping the remains of the cereal crops in the field, once the production has been collected. The commitments will be the following:

1.1 It is prohibited to remove the remains of cereal crops once harvested until October 1.

1.2 The straw must be kept on the ground forming cords after harvesting, prohibiting its chopping.

1.3 The entry of cattle is not allowed until August 15, inclusive.

1.4 No ground performances will be allowed until October 1st.

1.5 The maintenance of stubble will only affect the enclosures that in their specific agricultural campaign are planted with cereal. In any case, he will be obliged to cultivate in at least 3 years of the 5 commitment period in the compromised enclosures.

2. Maintenance of fallows: Fallow is understood as the maintenance of crop remains in the field during the following agricultural season. The commitments will be the following:

2.1 Permanence in the field: from the harvest of the crop until September 1 of the following year.

2.2 Agricultural work or the application of phytosanitary products will not be allowed, except for an application of herbicide if necessary.

2.3 The entry of cattle is not allowed between January 1 and August 15 of the fallow year.

2.4 The fallow maintenance will be obliged to carry it out, in at least 1 year of the 5 of the commitment period in the compromised enclosures. In the ZEPA of Alto Guadiato it will be 2 years out of 5.

Actions in rice fields.

1. Participate in a system for technical monitoring and verification of agri-environmental commitments, accredited through an Integrated Production certification entity recognized for this purpose.
2. Flood in mosaic until December 15 at least 1/3 of the compromised surface. In farms of 30 hectares or less, this commitment may be made in one year on the entire surface area committed or in several, provided that the entire area is reached.

ES_CHESTNUT_10.1.10

Chestnut

1. Ban on tilling the soil. Between February 1 and May 31, superficial tillage will be allowed as long as the soil disturbance does not exceed 20 cm. AND
2. Control the adventitious flora, preventing the development of perennial species and facilitating adequate soil protection to reduce water erosion. Said control will be carried out through clearing, avoiding leaving the soil unprotected.
3. Prohibition of the use of herbicides to control adventitious flora.

Raisin

1, Make pools at the base of the vines. The commitment would extend to the vines of at least 20% of the area of the plot per year, so that in the 5 years of commitment, pools have been created in 100% of the plot. The first work ("fragar") is allowed from December 1, of the year in which the aid application is submitted, until January 15, of the following year. The second ("clothing") from March 1 to April 15, of the year following the presentation of the aid application.

ES_LIMESTONE_10.1.13

1. Soil amendment with calcium sulfate (agricultural gypsum), calcium carbonate or calcium-magnesium carbonate (dolomite): To control phytophthora cinnamomi and reduce its effect on quercus, limestone soil amendments are proposed, which In addition, it promotes a greater development of the roots of the plants and improves the absorption of some elements such as phosphorus, which favors a greater number of legumes in the botanical composition of the grass and, therefore, greater soil nitrification. The specific commitments of this action will be the following:

- Incorporation of agricultural gypsum, calcium carbonate or dolomite in the pasture formation surface where the environmental commitment is made, between September 15 and December 15 of the year of payment request. The aid commitment period will be one year. After this period, there may be annual extensions to achieve or maintain the envisaged environmental benefits, prior justification of the need, in which case, a review of the commitments will be carried out. The quantity of limestone amendment is

1,500 kg/ha, a dose that does not generate sudden changes in the characteristics of the soil, nor excess calcium.

5.3.10 United Kingdom

Out of 31, 22 incentives enhance the soil quality (figure 39). It was followed by the influence on biodiversity, water quantity, and climate regulation-carbon storage.

Source: Own calculations

Figure 39 Areas of the English incentives' enhancement

The way that the application of this incentive improves these ecosystem services is as follows:

UK_LENS-

The Landscape Enterprise Network (LENs) approach develops integrated, place-based marketplaces for ecosystem functions. It allows corporations and government agencies who are interested in incentivizing nature-based solutions and realizing landscape-level outcomes to establish trading contracts with farmers, farmer cooperatives and landscape managers who are able to provide aggregated ecosystem services (e.g., water quality management, soil carbon sequestration, flood risk management, resilient and sustainable production of crops, biodiversity outcomes, etc.)

UK_ABI

Sowing a grass-free, pollen- and nectar-rich flower seed mix (containing shorter-lived legumes and longer-lived wild flower species) which is cut or grazed in the winter, in preparation for regrowth during the spring, contributes to:

- delivering an extended supply of pollen and nectar from late spring through to the autumn for beneficial insects such as bees, butterflies, hoverflies and moths, and food for farmland birds throughout the summer breeding period;
- integrated pest management;
- enhancing wildlife and biodiversity;
- promoting atmospheric nitrogen fixation, adding organic matter to the soil, and promoting circulation of soil nutrients and water retention.

UK_AB2 and UK_AB6

Maintaining basic over-winter stubble contributes to:

- providing winter food and shelter for a range of birds and other wildlife;
- establishing integrated pest management;
- linking non-crop habitats like hedgerows, ponds and field margins;
- reducing soil runoff, which improves water quality and soil health (soil nutrient retention).

UK_AB7

Planting whole crop cereals contributes to:

- reducing runoff and soil erosion;
- ensuring fields do not lose fertile topsoil and nutrients, like nitrogen and phosphorus;
- ensuring water is cleaner, as less soil, pesticides and nutrients reach water bodies;
- reducing flood risk, as the flow of water into water bodies is slowed;
- increasing soil water availability, as it infiltrates the soil more easily.

UK_AB8

Establishing flower-rich margins and plots contributes to:

- providing important habitat and foraging sites for invertebrates, including wild pollinators such as bumblebees, solitary bees, butterflies and hoverflies, and birds;
- integrated pest management;
- promoting atmospheric nitrogen fixation, adding organic matter to the soil, and promoting circulation of soil nutrients and water retention (if legumes are incorporated).

UK_AB15

Maintaining a two-year sown legume fallow contributes to:

- providing food for birds and wildlife, such as pollen and nectar for pollinators including bumblebees, solitary bees, butterflies and hoverflies;
- reducing and controlling blackgrass populations (if part of a rotation);
- establishing integrated pest management;
- promoting connectivity of habitats;
- promoting atmospheric nitrogen fixation, adding organic matter to the soil, and promoting circulation of soil nutrients and water retention.

UK_AB16

Planting autumn sown bumble bird mix contributes to:

- providing important habitat and foraging sites for invertebrates, including wild pollinators such as bumblebees, solitary bees, butterflies and hoverflies, and birds;
- establishing integrated pest management;
- promoting atmospheric nitrogen fixation, adding organic matter to the soil, and promoting circulation of soil nutrients and water retention (if legumes are incorporated).

UK_BE3

Management of hedgerows contributes to:

- enhancing above- and below-ground biodiversity (increasing earthworm diversity, hosting distinct arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi communities, promoting connectivity of habitats; providing food for overwintering birds and nectar and shelter for invertebrates);
- establishing integrated pest management;
- promoting infiltration and storing runoff;
- mitigating climate change by sequestering and storing atmospheric CO₂.

UK_BN3

Creating earth banks contributes to:

- conserving and enhancing landscape character;
- enhancing biodiversity and providing a valuable connected wildlife habitat;
- reducing the velocity of runoff and soil erosion;
- retaining water behind the bank and promoting infiltration.

UK_BN4

Establishing earth banks and soil bunds contributes to:

- conserving and enhancing landscape character;
- enhancing biodiversity and providing a valuable connected wildlife habitat;
- reducing the velocity of runoff and soil erosion;
- retaining water behind the bank/bund and promoting infiltration.

UK_BN5

Laying hedgerows contributes to:

- enhancing above- and below-ground biodiversity (increasing earthworm diversity, hosting distinct arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi communities, promoting connectivity of habitats; providing food for overwintering birds and nectar and shelter for invertebrates);
- establishing integrated pest management;
- promoting infiltration and storing runoff;
- mitigating climate change by sequestering and storing atmospheric CO₂.

UK_BN7

Gapping-up hedgerows creates a continuous length of hedge that contribute to:

- enhancing above- and below-ground biodiversity (increasing earthworm diversity, hosting distinct arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi communities, promoting connectivity of habitats; providing food for overwintering birds and nectar and shelter for invertebrates);
- establishing integrated pest management;
- promoting infiltration and storing runoff;
- mitigating climate change by sequestering and storing atmospheric CO₂.

UK_BN11

Planting new hedges contributes to:

- enhancing above- and below-ground biodiversity (increasing earthworm diversity, hosting distinct arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi communities, promoting connectivity of habitats; providing food for overwintering birds and nectar and shelter for invertebrates);
- establishing integrated pest management;
- promoting infiltration and storing runoff;
- mitigating climate change by sequestering and storing atmospheric CO₂.

UK_GS2

Maintaining permanent grasslands with very low inputs (outside Severely Disadvantaged Areas) contributes to:

- enhancing above- and below-ground biodiversity (inclusion of flowering grasses and wildflowers will provide food supply for birds and nectar and shelter for invertebrates);
- establishing integrated pest management;
- promoting infiltration and storing runoff;
- mitigating climate change by sequestering and storing atmospheric CO₂.

UK_GS4

Establishing vigorous mixed sward of grasses, legumes, herbs and wildflowers, suitable for productive cattle and sheep, contributes to:

- providing habitat and food for invertebrates, including crop pollinators;
- establishing integrated pest management;
- improving soil structure and water infiltration;
- mitigating climate change by sequestering and storing atmospheric CO₂.

UK_GS6

Managing species-rich grassland contributes to:

- providing habitat and food for invertebrates, including crop pollinators;
- establishing integrated pest management;
- improving soil structure and water infiltration;
- mitigating climate change by sequestering and storing atmospheric CO₂.

UK_GS7-Restoring grasslands towards species-rich grassland contributes to:

- providing habitat and food for invertebrates, including crop pollinators;
- establishing integrated pest management;
- improving soil structure and water infiltration;
- mitigating climate change by sequestering and storing atmospheric CO₂.

UK_GS8

Creating species-rich grassland contributes to:

- providing habitat and food for invertebrates, including crop pollinators;
- establishing integrated pest management;
- improving soil structure and water infiltration;
- mitigating climate change by sequestering and storing atmospheric CO₂."

UK_LOT1

Organic land management (improved permanent grassland) contributes to:

- providing habitat and food for invertebrates, including crop pollinators;
- integrated pest management;
- improving soil structure and water infiltration;
- mitigating climate change by sequestering and storing atmospheric CO₂.

UK_LOT3

Organic land management (rotational land), whereby rotational land is converted from conventional to organic management, contributes to:

- adding organic matter to the soil, improving soil structure and water infiltration.
- mitigating climate change by sequestering and storing atmospheric CO₂.

UK_SW1 and UK_SW2

Establishing a 4m to 6m buffer strip on cultivated land contributes to:

- preventing sediment and nutrients from being transported in surface water runoff.

UK_SW3

Establishing in-field grass strips contributes to:

- reducing the quantity of sediment, nutrients and pesticides transported through surface runoff water, both within fields and from field to field;
- mitigating climate change by sequestering and storing atmospheric CO₂.

UK_SW8

Managing intensive grassland adjacent to a watercourse, by reducing stocking density and fertilizer inputs on improved grassland, contributes to:

- reducing soil compaction, surface run-off and risk of diffuse pollution to the watercourse;
- reducing surface runoff may help to reduce the risk of flooding;
- reducing the risk of nitrate loss to ground and surface water if it is used with SW14 - Nil fertilizer supplement."

UK_SW9

Seasonal livestock removal on intensive grassland, from fields adjacent to a watercourse that are prone to waterlogging, compaction or poaching, contributes to:

- improving soil structure, surface runoff and risk of diffuse pollution to the watercourse;
- reducing surface runoff may help to reduce the risk of flooding.

UK_SFI

The arable and horticultural soils standard focuses on improving soil health, structure, organic matter, and biology. There are introductory and intermediate level actions, which equate to:

- Action 1: Completing a soil assessment and produce a soil management plan;
- Action 2: Testing soil organic matter;
- Action 3: Adding organic matter to all land in the standard at least once during the 3-year SFI standards agreement;
- Action 4: Maintaining green cover on at least 70% of land in the standard over winter or have green cover (introductory level);
- Action 4: Maintaining green cover on at least 50% of land in this level of the standard over winter and multi-species cover crops on an additional 20% of the land (intermediate level)."

UK_RUR_GR_PAY

The slurry infrastructure grant focuses on enhancing soil health by incentivizing farmers to replace, build additional or expand existing slurry stores (i.e., tanks, lagoons and concrete stores fitted with impermeable covers and large permanent bags) to provide storage capacity for six months. It contributes to:

- improving the use of organic nutrients on farms;
- reducing nutrient pollution;
- reducing greenhouse gases;
- improving water quality;
- improving air quality;

- restoring natural habitats.

UK_ENVIR_PERM

The Environmental Permitting (England and Wales) Regulations 2016 and, specifically, the standard rules (SR2010 No4 Mobile plant for landspreading; SR2010 No 5: mobile plant for the reclamation, restoration or land improvement; and SR2010 No 6: mobile plant for landspreading of sewage sludge) contribute to soil health by:

- improving the use of organic nutrients on farms;
- reducing nutrient pollution and greenhouse gases;
- improving water quality;
- improving air quality;
- restoring natural habitats.

UK_LANDF_TAX

The Landfill tax which covers waste disposal at any site - including those where excavated soil has been re-used without implementation of a suitable waste permitting exemption or under a fully compliant and declared CL:AIRE Definition of Waste Code of Practice (DoWCoP) Materials Management Plan - contributes to soil health by:

- complementing existing penalties and sanctions for illegal waste disposal;
- improving waste disposal by facilitating its recovery and conversion to a non-waste.

UK_CC CODE_SOILS_CONSTSITES

The DEFRA Code of Practice guides the construction sector to better protect soil resources and contributes to soil health by outlining:

- how a Soil Resource Plan should be developed (where and which type of type of topsoil and subsoil can be stripped and how/where it can be stockpiled);
- how soil resources can be used to create a landscape, habitat or garden (to promote aeration, drainage, and root growth);
- how construction activities can adversely impact soils (through sealing; contamination; over-compaction; and mixing of topsoil with subsoil or with construction waste/contaminated materials, resulting in landfill disposal).

6 Conclusion

In agricultural ecosystems, incentives influence ecosystem services through motivating changes in land use and management. This chain of influence is complex because incentives can cause multiple intended and unintended changes in land use and management, each potentially having co-benefits and trade-offs across multiple ecosystem services.

In this research are identified and assessed the incentives that can help the business model to become sustainable from the point of view of the soil health. That goal is accomplished by exploring the incentives that drive farmers to take action towards improving soil health. These factors (incentives) are then applied to the business model canvas (BMC). By consolidating these incentives into a map, a comprehensive overview is created to understand how they contribute to the current state of the business model and the improvement of soil health. Through this process, we aim to address the question of how soil health business models can effectively contribute to the maintenance of sustainable and competitive agriculture. By reviewing and assessing the key incentives for soil health, we produce a provisional set of critical incentives, mapped onto the BMC.

To perform the analysis of existing incentives, it was prepared a survey questionnaire for incentives evaluation and description for the period 2014-2022. The first part of the questionnaire (Q1 – Q6) are common questions about the surveying organization and country, identification of the incentive, land use classification and NUTS level. The second part of the questionnaire (Q7 – Q15) gather information if the incentive is policy driven or voluntary, the national policies that support the application of this type of incentives, and the policies that support financially the application of the incentive. The relation between case study incentives and with the main goals of 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development objectives and the key objectives of the new CAP 2023-2027. The last part gathers information about ecosystem services and the relation with the incentives.

In terms of the relation between the incentives and sustainability, measured by sustainable development goals (SDG), the significant number of incentives are focused on SDG 15. Protect, restore, and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss. Other important goals are SDG6. Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all and SDG13. Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts.

Additionally, there was analysed the influence of the incentives related to the case studies to the 10 key objectives, which focus on economic, social, and environmental goals, which are the base of the new CAP 2023-2027. The incentives enhanced the most landscape and biodiversity preservation and environmental care. Climate change action and food and health quality protection are affected.

The analysis of the influence of the incentive over the soil health strategies show that 45.8% of the incentives have influence over the remediation soil health strategy. Respectively 54.2% have influence over fertilization strategy. Although the number of incentives covers both main soil health strategies, more incentives can influence the fertilization strategy.

The incentives mapping aims to categorize incentives that have been conducted on the social, economic, and environmental building blocks of soil health business models within the agricultural and forestry sector. The incentives mapping was divided into four phases: identifying, analysing, visualizing and prioritizing.

It was collected and analysed 223 incentives in 10 countries participating in the NOVASOIL project. The countries were classified into three groups according to the number of incentives. The first group includes Bulgaria, Denmark, Estonia, Latvia, and Spain with a range from 8 to 10 incentives. The second group consist of Germany, England, France, and Italy, with a range from 16 to 30 incentives. The third group consists only from Netherlands, with 76 incentives. The Netherlands stands out with a high number of predominantly policy-driven incentives. In contrast, countries like Germany, England, France, and Italy have a considerable number of voluntary incentives. The other countries in the dataset have a smaller number of incentives, and their distribution is relatively balanced between policy-driven and voluntary approaches.

For the purpose of mapping are used the case studies in the project that evaluates the incentives that have direct influence on the case studies' business model. It was identified a total of 61 incentives in 7 countries. The incentives were assessed and placed on a coordinate system with nine quadrants. Fourteen (23%) from the incentives are in top right quadrants (VI, VIII and IX) and have the highest influence over socio-economic indicators and soil health.

Only 1 (16.7%) of the incentives in Business Models - Value chain is situated in the top right quadrants. From that point of view, incentives are not efficient enough. BM Collective and value chain have 6 (50%) incentives in top right quadrant that have high degree of influence on soil health strategies. The effectiveness of the incentives here is much higher than in BM – Value chain. In Business Models - Agricultural production 6 (25%) incentives are in top right quadrants. The main characteristic of this business model is that there are many incentives present. In Business Models - Agricultural production/value chain there is none incentive in the top right quadrants, which means that effectiveness of the incentives is low.

This work is the first step to identify and define all the existing incentives in Europe by the cooperation and collaboration with the sister projects. The methodology proposed can be adapted to other land use types if the business model has been identified. For that, once this report will be submitted, sister projects will be notified in order to facilitate the coherence and avoid overlapping among the three projects, InBestSoils, SoilValues and NOVASOIL.

7 Annexes

7.1 Annex 1 - List of the incentives

No	Code	Title of the incentives described
1	FR_RDNF001_C3	2014FR06RDNF001/COUVER_03/Grassing under perennial woody crops (Arboriculture - Viticulture)(Code: M10.0008)
2	FR_RDNF001_C4	2014FR06RDNF001/COUVER_04/Covering of vineyard inter-rows by spreading bark (Code: M10.0009)
3	FR_RDNF001_C6	2014FR06RDNF001/COVER_06 - Creation and maintenance of a perennial grass cover (grass strips or plots) (Code: M10.0011)
4	FR_RDNF001_C11	2014FR06RDNF001/ COUVER_11 Maintenance of natural cover on vineyard inter-rows. Code- M10.0014
5	FR_RDNF001_C16	2014FR06RDNF001/ COUVER_16 Crushing and Burying Rice Straws (Code: M10.0020)
6	FR_RDNF001_H4	2014FR06RDNF001/HERBE_04 Adjustment of grazing pressure during certain periods (parcel loading on remarkable environment) (Code: M10.0023)
7	FR_RDNF001_H11	2014FR06RDNF001/HERBE_11Absence of grazing and mowing in winter on grasslands and wetland habitats (Code: M10.0029)
8	FR_RDNF001_IR9	2014FR06RDNF001/IRRIG_09 - Maintenance of submerged irrigated crops favourable to biodiversity (level 2)(Code: M10.0072)
9	FR_RDNF001_L1	2014FR06RDNF001/ LINEA_01 - LINEA_01 - Maintenance of localized hedges (Code: M10.0039)
10	FR_RDNF001_L5	2014FR06RDNF001/LINEA_05 - Mechanical maintenance of grassed slopes within cultivated plots (Code:M10.0043)
11	FR_RDNF001_L9	2014FR06RDNF001/LINEA_09 - Maintenance of tree hedges (Code: M10.0083)
12	FR_RDNF001_PH8	2014FR06RDNF001/PHYTO_08 - Installation of a vegetable or biodegradable mulch on market gardening crops (Code: M10.0068)
13	FR_RDNF001_SGC1	2014FR06RDNF001/SGC_01 - Arable crop systems operation (Code: M10.0006)
14	FR_RDNF001_SGC2	2014FR06RDNF001/SGC_02 - Arable crop systems operation adapted to intermediate zones (Code: M10.0007)
15	FR_RDNF001_SGC3	2014FR06RDNF001/SGC_03 - Arable crop systems operation adapted to areas with a high proportion of vegetable or industrial crops vegetable or industrial crops (Code: M10.0071)

No	Code	Title of the incentives described
16	FR_RDNF001_SOL1	2014FR06RDNF001/SOL_01 - Conversion to direct seeding under cover (Code: M10.0085)
17	FR_RDNF001_SPE3	2014FR06RDNF001/SPE_03 - Operation polyculture-monogastric farming systems (Code: M10.0005)
18	FR_RDNF001_M11_1	2014FR06RDNF001/- Conversion to organic farming (Code: M11.0001)
19	FR_RDNF001_M11_2	2014FR06RDNF001/Maintenance of organic farming (Code: M11.0002)
20	FR_RDNF001_M10_42	2014FR06RDNF001/LINEA 04-Maintenance of groves (Code: M10.0042)
21	FR_RDNF001_SHP1	2014FR06RDNF001/SHP_01- Individual operation grassland and pastoral systems - maintenance (Code:M10.0078)
22	FR_RDNF001_SHP2	2014FR06RDNF001/SHP_02- Collective operation grassland and pastoral systems - maintenance (Code: M10.0079)
23	ES_ECOSCH_PD31	1PD31001806V1 - Eco-scheme
24	ES_INTP_ROD	Integrated Production
25	ES_CUST_TER	Custody of the territory
26	UK_LENS	Landscape Enterprise Networks (LENS)
27	UK_AB1	Countryside Stewardship AB1: Nectar Flower Mix
28	UK_AB2	Countryside Stewardship AB2: Basic overwinter stubble
29	UK_AB6	Countryside Stewardship AB6: Enhanced overwinter stubble
30	UK_AB7	Countryside Stewardship AB7: Whole crop cereals
31	UK_AB8	Countryside Stewardship AB8: Flower rich margins and plots
32	UK_AB15	Countryside Stewardship AB15: Two year sown legume fallow
33	UK_AB16	Countryside Stewardship AB16: Autumn sown bumblebird mix
34	UK_BE3	Countryside Stewardship BE3: Management of hedgerows
35	UK_BN3	Countryside Stewardship BN3: Earth bank creation
36	UK_BN4	Countryside Stewardship BN4: Earth bank restoration
37	UK_BN5	Countryside Stewardship BN5: Hedgerow laying
38	UK_BN7	Countryside Stewardship BN7: Hedgerow gapping-up
39	UK_BN11	Countryside Stewardship BN11: Planting new hedges
40	UK_GS2	Countryside Stewardship GS2: Permanent grassland with very low inputs (outside Severely Disadvantaged Areas)
41	UK_GS4	Countryside Stewardship GS4: Legume and herb-rich swards
42	UK_GS6	Countryside Stewardship GS6: Management of species-rich grassland

No	Code	Title of the incentives described
43	UK_GS7	Countryside Stewardship GS7: Restoration towards species-rich grassland
44	UK_GS8	Countryside Stewardship GS8: Creation of species-rich grassland
45	UK_OT1	Countryside Stewardship OT1: Organic land management – improved permanent grassland
46	UK_OT3	Countryside Stewardship OT3: Organic land management – rotational land
47	UK_SW1	Countryside Stewardship SW1: 4m to 6m buffer strip on cultivated land
48	UK_SW2	Countryside Stewardship SW2: 4m to 6m buffer strip on intensive grassland
49	UK_SW3	Countryside Stewardship SW3: In-field grass strips
50	UK_SW8	Countryside Stewardship SW8: Management of intensive grassland adjacent to a watercourse
51	UK_SW9	Countryside Stewardship SW9: Seasonal livestock removal on intensive grassland
52	UK_SFI	Sustainable Farming Incentive (SFI) – Arable and horticultural soils standard
53	UK_RUR_GR_PAY	Rural grants and payments – Slurry infrastructure grant
54	UK_ENVIR_PERM	The Environmental Permitting (England and Wales) Regulations 2016 - artificial and agricultural areas
55	UK_LANDF_TAX	Landfill tax (waste disposal) - artificial and agricultural
56	UK_CCODE_SOILS_CONSTSITES	Construction Code of Practice for the Sustainable Use of Soils on Construction Sites - Artificial surfaces, Agricultural areas
57	DE_A_CKERWERT	A.ckerwert The A.ckerwert project aims to make people aware that land tenants share responsibility for the way their land is managed. By paying a fair rent, they can give the farmer financial leeway to pursue new ways of cultivation that protect both land and nature. The project aims to provide land leasers with assistance in assuming this responsibility. A.ckerwert supports landlords of agricultural land to include sustainability aspects in lease agreements. The project is a platform to bring people together and find solutions that are a win-win for all parties involved: Farmers, landowners and nature.
58	DE_AGORA_NATURA	AgoraNatura
59	DE_KULAP_B10	KULAP B10 Organic farming
60	DE_KULAP_B19	KULAP B19/20/21 Extensive grassland use for rough grazers.
61	DE_KULAP_B30	KULAP B30
62	DE_KULAP_B32	KULAP B32/33/34 Watercourse and erosion control strips

No	Code	Title of the incentives described
63	DE_KULAP_B35	KULAP B35/36 Winter greening
64	DE_KULAP_B37	KULAP B37 Mulch sowing for row crops
65	DE_KULAP_B38	KULAP B38 Stripe-/Direkt sowing for row crops
66	DE_KULAP_B43	KULAP B43/44/45 Diverse crop rotation with flowering species, protein plants or large grain legumes
67	DE_SOIL_PROT_LAW	Soil Protection Law and accompanying Soil Protection Directive (Gesetz zum Schutz vor schädlichen Bodenveränderungen und zur Sanierung von Altlasten - BBodSchG, Bundes-Bodenschutz- und Altlastenverordnung - BBodSchV). General law on soil protection, for issues that are out of the scope of special laws such as fertilizer law. Governs a wide range of aspects such as soil remediation, soil testing, materials and chemicals deposited in soils, good agricultural practice (prevention of erosion, fertilization, preserving soil humus).
68	DE_BIO_BODEN	Bio Boden
69	DE_BODENFRUCHTBARKEITSFONDS	Bodenfruchtbarkeitsfonds - The fund is based on donations. These are used to create spaces for participating farmers to enable land management that increases soil fertility.
70	DE_CLIM_FRI_LAND_USE	Climate Friendly Land Use and Development of Organic Soils, Förderprogramm moorschonende Bewirtschaftung
71	DE_CO2_LAND	CO ₂ – Land - CO ₂ is sequestered in arable soils through scientifically proven methods. The climate certificates generated in this way can then be purchased. With the proceeds of the certificates, farmers are (partially) compensated for their additional efforts.
72	DE_FER_DIR_AGR	Fertilizer directive (Verordnung über das Inverkehrbringen von Düngemitteln, Bodenhilfsstoffen, Kultursubstraten und Pflanzenhilfsmitteln - DüMV). Directive on fertilizers, additives, substrates etc..
73	DE_FER_LOW_PAST	Fertilizer Directive (Düngemittelverordnung – DüV) and Fertilizer Law (Düngegesetz – DüngG).
74	DE_FAKT1_D1	FAKT 1, D1 – No chemical-synthetic pesticides and fertilizer.
75	DE_FUL13	FUL Nr. 13 10 Years set-aside
76	DE_GRE_CROP_DIV	Greening Crop diversification. Farms up to 30 ha must grow at least two crops. The main crop must not exceed 75% of the cultivated area. Farms of 30 ha or more must grow at least three crops, of which the main crop must be grown on up to 75% of the area and the two largest crops together up to 95%.

No	Code	Title of the incentives described
77	DE_PRES_PERM_GRAS	Preservation of permanent grassland No conversion of grassland in Fora-Fauna-Habitat areas (FFH areas), in remaining areas exists an individual farm authorization system. According to this system, conversion of permanent grassland to other uses will essentially only be possible if new permanent grassland is established elsewhere in its place. This will stabilize the total area of ecologically valuable permanent grassland.
78	DE_VNP_H11	VNP H11 Extensive cropland use for field breeders and field wild herbs. No cultivation of corn, sugar beets, potatoes, clover, clover-grass, alfalfa, field grass and clover-alfalfa mixture. Refrain from the use of chemical pesticides.
79	DE_VPN_H12	VNP H12-14 Following on arable land with self-vegetation for species protection reasons. Renunciation of the use of chemical pesticides. Combination with fertilizer waiver possible.
80	DE_VPN_H20	VNP H20 Conversion of arable land to grassland.
81	DE_VPN_H30	VNP H30 Result-based grassland use. Combination possible with no fertilizer, pesticides / insect-friendly mowing.
82	DE_MOOR_FUT	MoorFutures
83	DE_PAULA_CULT_BREAK	PAULa Cultivation break - when growing sugar beet, potatoes (except early potatoes), sunflowers, rapeseed or grain legumes, a cultivation break of at least 3 years must be observed - for maize a cultivation pause of at least 2 years
84	DE_AUKM	AUKM - Promotion of Cooperative Measures to Improve Climate Protection and Biodiversity on Agriculturally Used Land
85	DE_REG_AG_CIT	Regionalwert AG Citizens can buy a citizen share for an amount of 625 euros or more. The money flows into regional partner businesses in agriculture, regional logistics, gastronomy, consulting and production facilities that meet the initiative's sustainability criteria of operating in an ecological, social and future-oriented manner.
86	DE_TIRE_PRESS_CSYS	Subsidy for the purchase of a tire pressure control system.
87	BG_CSOILER_GRAREAS	control of soil erosion - conversion of arable agricultural lands into permanently grassed areas
88	BG_CSOILER_PERMPLANT	control of soil erosion - weeding the rows between the vines and permanent plantings
89	BG_CSOILER_DRAINAGE	control of soil erosion - construction and maintenance of drainage furrows and across the slope

No	Code	Title of the incentives described
90	BG_BUF_STRIPS	create and maintain buffer strips with honeydew grass vegetation
91	BG_CROP_ROTATION	a more distinct alternation of trench crops with a crops with fused surface, perpendicular to the slope
92	BG_SOILEROS_PLANTCOVER	protection of the soil from erosion by providing a plant cover with a fused surface in the cultivated areas
93	BG_SOILEROS_WEEDING	protection of the soil from erosion by weeding or tillage perpendicular to the slope
94	BG_SOILPROT_PROHBURNING	protection of the soil from erosion by burning of stubble is prohibited.
95	BG_CROP_DIV	Crop diversification
96	BG_PERM_GRASS	Maintenance of existing permanent grass areas
97	NL_TRIM_AGRISCHHEME	Knip- of scheerheg (Agrarisch Natuur & Landschapsbeheer, Agri-environmental scheme)
98	NL_TREEROWS_AGRISCHHEME	Beheer van Bomenrijen/ Struweelrand / Struweelhaag/ Hakhoutbeheer/ Haakbosje / Griendje (Agrarisch Natuur & Landschapsbeheer, Agri-environmental scheme)
99	NL_INSECTRICH_AGRISCHHEME	Insectenrijke graslandranden (Agrarisch Natuur & Landschapsbeheer, Agri-environmental scheme)
100	NL_SOIL_DEGR_AGRISCHHEME	Bodemvervetering (Agrarisch Natuur & Landschapsbeheer, Agri-environmental scheme)
101	NL_HERBRICH_AGRISCHHEME	Kruidenrijke akkerranden (Agrarisch Natuur & Landschapsbeheer, Agri-environmental scheme)
102	NL_ARABLE_HAMSTERS_AGRISCHHEME	Bouwland voor hamsters (Agrarisch Natuur & Landschapsbeheer, Agri-environmental scheme)
103	NL_BIRDFIELD_AGRISCHHEME	Vogelakker (Agrarisch Natuur & Landschapsbeheer, Agri-environmental scheme)
104	NL_WIN_FOOD_FIELD	Wintervoedselakker (Agrarisch Natuur & Landschapsbeheer, Agri-environmental scheme)
105	NL_BOT_GRASSLAND	Botanisch waardevol grasland (Agrarisch Natuur & Landschapsbeheer, Agri-environmental scheme)
106	NL_ROUGH_MOST	Ruige meest (Agrarisch Natuur & Landschapsbeheer, Agri-environmental scheme)
107	NL_EXTE_GRAZED_GRASS	Extensief beweid grasland (Agrarisch Natuur & Landschapsbeheer, Agri-environmental scheme)
108	NL_GREENFALLOW_ESCHHEME	Eco-scheme - Groene Braak
109	NL_HERBS_GRASS_ESCHHEME	Eco-scheme - Bufferstrook met kruiden (langs grasland)
110	NL_HERBS_PERMANENT_ESCHHEME	Eco-scheme - Bufferstrook met kruiden (langs bouwland of blijvende teelt)
111	NL_GRAZING_DAYNIGHT_ESCHHEME	Eco-scheme - Verlengde Weidegang: dag en nacht beweiding

No	Code	Title of the incentives described
112	NL_GRAZING_DAY_ESCHEME	Eco-scheme - Verlengde Weidegang: overdag beweiding
113	NL_UNDERSEEDING_ESCHEME	Eco-scheme -Onderzaai vanggewas
114	NL_GREEN_COVER_ESCHEME	Eco-scheme -Groenbedekking
115	NL_EARLY_HARVEST_ESCHEME	Eco-scheme - Vroeg oogsten Rooigemest
116	NL_NITROGENFIXING_ESCHEME	Eco-scheme - Stikstofbindend gewas/eiwitgewas
117	NL_DORMANT_ESCHEME	Eco-scheme – Rustgewas
118	NL_WET_CROP_ESCHEME	Eco-scheme - Natte teelt
119	NL_PERENNIAL_CROP_ESCHEME	Eco-scheme -Meerjarige teelt
120	NL_PERM_GRASSLAND_ESCHEME	Eco-scheme - Langjarig grasland
121	NL_GRASSLAND_HERBS_ESCHEME	Eco-scheme - Grasland met kruiden
122	NL_GRASS_COVER_ESCHEME	Eco-scheme – Grasklaver
123	NL_A3_PRECISION_FARMING	Categorie A Precisielandbouw en Smart farming A3 Precisieberekening en -irrigatie (Regeling Europese EZK- en LNV-subsidies)
124	NL_A2_PRECISION_FARMING	Categorie A Precisielandbouw en Smart farming A2 Precisiebemesting (Regeling Europese EZK- en LNV-subsidies)
125	NL_B4_DIGITALISATION	Categorie B Digitalisering B4 EC meters en monitoringssensoren (Regeling Europese EZK- en LNV-subsidies)
126	NL_C1_DRAINAGE	Categorie C Water, droogte, verzilting C1 Klimaat-adaptieve, peilgestuurde drainage (Regeling Europese EZK- en LNV-subsidies)
127	NL_E2_CROP_ROT	Categorie E Natuurinclusieve landbouw en Kringlooplandbouw. E2 Mengteelten zoals strokenteelt/pixelteelt en nieuwe teelten zoals eiwitten (Regeling Europese EZK- en LNV-subsidies)
128	NL_E3_HERB_GRASS	Categorie E Natuurinclusieve landbouw en Kringlooplandbouw. E3 Agroforestry en meerjarig kruidenrijk grasland (niet op veengrond) (Regeling Europese EZK- en LNV-subsidies)
129	NL_E4_SOIL_COMPACTATION_REDUCTION	Categorie E Natuurinclusieve landbouw en Kringlooplandbouw. E4 Vermindering bodemverdichting door ondiepe, niet kerende grondbewerking, vaste rijpaden en mechanische onkruidbestrijding (niet op veengrond) (Regeling Europese EZK- en LNV-subsidies)
130	NL_E6_ORGANIC_RESIDUES	Categorie E Natuurinclusieve landbouw en Kringlooplandbouw. E6 Verwerken en toepassen van organisch restmateriaal (Regeling Europese EZK- en LNV-subsidies)
131	NL_E7_NONDIG_GRAZING	Categorie E Natuurinclusieve landbouw en Kringlooplandbouw. E7 Niet digitale voorzieningen voor weidegang (Regeling Europese EZK- en LNV-subsidies)

No	Code	Title of the incentives described
132	NL_E7_COMPOST	Categorie E Natuurinclusieve landbouw en Kringlooplandbouw. E8 Opslagplaatsen ten behoeve van verwerking organische materiaal tot compost (Regeling Europese EZK- en LNV-subsidies)
133	NL_ORG_FARM	Organic Farming
134	NL_AGRO_FORESTRY	Agroforestry
135	NL_NAT_INCLUSIVE_CIRC_AGRI	Adviezen voor natuurinclusieve kringlooplandbouw
136	NL_NEW_FORESTS	Aanleg nieuw bos buiten het Gelders Natuurnetwerk
137	NL_NO_DRUG_WASTE	Drugsafval verwijderen
138	NL_AGRIFOOD_INNOV	Innovatie Agrifood
139	NL_KWELDERBEHER	Kwelderbeher
140	NL_CLEAR_DRUG_WASTE	Opruiming Drugsafval
141	NL_FOREST_WOOD_200K	Bos en hout
142	NL_NATURE_QUALITY_SKNL	Kwaliteitsimpuls Natuur en Landschap (SKNL)
143	NL_REGIO_FARMER_EXPERIMENTS	Boerenexperimenten in de Veenkoloniën, Westerwolde en Oldambt (Regio Deal Natuurinclusieve Landbouw)
144	NL_IMPLM_SCH_NATURE	Uitvoeringsregeling natuurinclusieve experimenten Friese veenweide (Regio Deal Natuurinclusieve Landbouw)
145	NL_REG_ORGANIC_FARM_EXPERIMENTS	Boerenexperimenten biologische landbouw provincie Groningen
146	NL_FARM_EXPER_FRISIAN	Boerenexperimenten in de Friese Kleiweide (Regio Deal Natuurinclusieve Landbouw)
147	NL_PARCEL_EXCHANGE	Kavelruil
148	NL_QUALITY_SCHEME_IMPULSE	Openstelling Subsidieregeling Kwaliteitsimpuls Natuur en Landschap
149	NL_IND_SCHEME_ADVICE_ALDEBOARN	Subsidieregeling onafhankelijk advies boeren Aldeboarn – De Deelen
150	NL_FARM_EXPER_WESTERWOLDE	Boerenexperimenten in de Veenkoloniën, Westerwolde en Oldambt (Regio Deal Natuurinclusieve Landbouw)
151	NL_LAND_AQUISITION_SUBS	Subsidie Grondverwerving Natuur Netwerk Nederland (NNN) & Subsidie Verplaatsing grondgebonden agrarische bedrijven
152	NL_SOIL_REMED_SUBS	Subsidie Financiële bepalingen bodemsanering
153	NL_CLEANING_DRUG_SUBSIDY	Subsidie Opruiming drugsafval
154	NL_FUT_ORIENTED_GRANT	Subsidie Toekomstgerichte Landbouw
155	NL_FOREST_WOOD_70K	Bos en hout
156	NL_PERM_GRASSLAND	Blijvend grasland (Oppervlakte blijvend grasland gelijk houden (GLMC 1), Ecologisch kwetsbaar blijvend grasland beschermen (GLMC 9))
157	NL_CONDITIONALITIES	De conditionaliteiten (summary)
158	NL_PEATLANDS_WETLANDS_PROT_GLM C2	Veenweiden en wetlands beschermen (GLMC 2)

No	Code	Title of the incentives described
159	NL_NO_STUBBLE_BURN_GAEC 3	Stoppels niet verbranden (GLMC 3)
160	NL_EROSION_CONT_GAEC 5	Erosie tegengaan (GLMC 5)
161	NL_SOIL_COVER_MIN_GAEC 6	Bodem minimaal bedekken (GLMC 6)
162	NL_CROP_ROT_GAEC 7	Gewassen op bouwland roteren (GLMC 7)
163	NL_BUFFER_STRIPS_GAEC 4	Bufferstroken langs waterlopen (GLMC 4)
164	NL_NONPROD_ARABLE_LAND_GAEC8	Niet-productieve bouwland, landschapselementen en snoeien (GLMC 8)
165	NL_RABO_CARBON_BANK	Rabo Carbon Bank by Rabobank
166	NL_UDEA_CARB_FARMING	Udea Carbon farming
167	NL_ZLTO	ZLTO
168	NL_CARBON_FARMERS	Carbon Farmers / NL groen
169	NL_CLOSE_FARM	Dicht bij de boederij
170	NL_ECOLABEL	Het Milieukeur
171	NL_PIG_PRODUCTION_RIGHTS	Productierechten Varkens
172	NL_WARM_REHABILITATION_PIG_FARMING	Warme Sanering Varkenshouderij
173	EE_REG_SOILP_SUPPORT	Regional soil protection support Piirkondlik mullakaitse toetus
174	EE_ENV_FRE_ECOPLAN	Environment friendly production eco plan (specify). Main activities: crop rotation and cultivation of leguminous crops; use of certified seed (15% cereal seed); glyphosate restriction; winter vegetation (30% of eligible land); soil samples and fertilization plan; grass strips (flowering strips); education. Additional activities: additional water protection (50% winter vegetation); promoting pollinators; promoting field birds (not mowing permanent grassland) -support from CAP Varem KSM, edaspidi Keskkonnasõbraliku tootmise ökokava (täpsustada)
175	EE_CONT_ORG_FARM	Support for the transition to organic farming and support for continuing with organic farming Mahepõllumajandusele ülemineku toetus ja mahepõllumajandusega jätkamise toetus (kuni 2022?)
176	EE_SINGLEA_PAYScheme	Single Area Payment Scheme + green direct payment. Ühtne pindalatoetus (ÜPT) + Kliimat ja keskkonda säästvate põllumajandustavade toetus (rohestamine) ROH.
177	EE_NATURA_FOREST	NATURA forest NATURA mets

No	Code	Title of the incentives described
178	EE_SEMINAT_BIOTIC_COMM	Payment of support for the maintenance of semi-natural biotic communities. Poolloodusliku koosluse hooldamise toetus - PLK
179	EE_WATER_ACT	Water Act Veeseadus
180	IT_QUALSCHEME_AGRIPROD	Quality schemes for agriproducts and foodstuffs
181	IT_SQNPI_LABEL	SQNPI label (National quality system for integrated production)
182	IT_GLOBAL_GAP_IFA	GLOBAL GAP IFA (Good Agricultural Practices - Integrated Farm Assurance) label
183	IT_ORG_FARM_LABEL	ORGANIC FARMING LABEL
184	IT_ORG_FARM_DISTRICTS	BIODISTRETTI (organic farming districts)
185	IT_AGR_ENV_CLIM_PAYMENT	Agri-environmental-climate payments
186	IT_ORG_FARMING	Organic farming
187	IT_NAT2_WATER_PAY	Natura 2000 and Water Framework Directive payments
188	IT_GREENING	Greening
189	IT_REFORESTATION	Actions for the reforestation
190	IT_ORGANIC_PROVISIONS	Provisions for the protection, development and competitiveness of organic agricultural, agribusiness and aquaculture production
191	IT_NAT_FOREST_STR	National Forest Strategy (Italy)
192	IT_NATURAL_DISASTERS	Natural disasters: restoring production potential and preventing damage
193	IT_FOREST_AREA_INV	Investments in forest area development and improvement of the viability of forests
194	IT_INTEGR_SUPPLY_CHAIN	Integrated projects supply chain - Progetti integrati di filiera (PIF) - Tuscany 2014-2020
195	IT_INTEGR_TERRITORIAL_PROJECTS	Integrated territorial projects - Progetti integrati territoriali (PIT) - Tuscany
196	DK_BIODIVERSITY_IN_FOREST	Biodiversity in Forest
197	DK_ORG_FARMING	Organic farming
198	DK_Peat_areas_Climate	Taking organogenic/Peat areas out of production
199	DK_Grass and nature	Taking care of grass and nature areas (5 years)
200	DK_SET_A_SIDE	Taking area out of production (Ecoscheme GLM 8)
201	DK_Climate Grass	Keeping grass in rotation for longer
202	DK_Extensive grass	Ekstensive grassproduction on area with more than 6% carbon
203	DK_Crop diversification	Increase area with crops which that are selvom cropped (greening)
204	DK_Soil_CA	Improved Censervation Agriculture
205	DK_Cover_P	Improve grass cover to reduce phousphrous loss
206	LV_ESH_DPAY_ROT	Enhanced crop rotation and winter cover

No	Code	Title of the incentives described
207	LV_ESH_DPAY_NOPPP	Ecological focus areas without the use of PPPs
208	LV_ESH_DPAY_TILLAGE	Eco-scheme - Minimal soil tillage technologies
209	LV_ESH_DPAY_BUFFER	Buffer strips
210	LV_ESH_DPAY_PREC	Precision agriculture
211	LV_PERM_GRASS_ANALYSIS	Soil agrochemical analysis
212	LV_PERM_GRASS_MAINTAN	Maintenance of existing grasslands
213	LV_PERM_GRASS_PEST_MANG	Integrated pest management
214	LV_PERM_GRASS_LIMING	Soil liming
215	LV_AGRF_FORESTRY	Agroforestry transition to forestry/optimising farm economy during transformation degraded land to forestry
216	EE_LAND_MELIORATION	Support for land melioration. (Investment support for the development and maintenance of agricultural and forestry infrastructure)
217	ES_HERCR_10.1.4	Sustainable Systems of rainfed herbaceous crops
218	ES_AGROIND_10.1.5	Sustainable Systems of agroindustrial crops
219	ES_WOODY_10.1.6	Sustainable Systems of woody crops
220	ES_OLIVE_10.1.7	Sustainable Olive Systems
221	ES_BIRDS_10.1.8	Agricultural Systems of special interest for the populations of steppe birds and bird of the Andalusian rice fields
222	ES_CHESNUT_10.1.10	Maintenance of singular systems: Chesnut trees and Raisin
223	ES_LIMESTONE_10.1.13	Limestone soil amendment for the prevention and control of root rot in woodland formations

7.2 Annex 2 - List of analysed sustainable development goals

- SDG1. End poverty in all its forms everywhere.
- SDG2. End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture.
- SDG3. Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages.
- SDG4. Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.
- SDG6. Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all.
- SDG7. Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy for all.
- SDG8. Promote sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work for all.
- SDG9. Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation.
- SDG10. Reduce inequality within and among countries.
- SDG11. Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable.
- SDG12. Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns.
- SDG13. Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts.
- SDG15. Protect, restore, and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss.
- SDG17. Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development.

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